

DELIVERABLE 2.2

Detailed assessment of the potential for deploying I-US based on a detailed assessment of promising EU regions and H4Cs.

WP2 – Regional/municipal analysis of H4C potential

T2.2 – Detailed analysis for a selection of most promising regions/cities for I-US

T2.3 – Replication analysis for H4C innovative value chains across Europe

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Abbreviations

AAM	Alkaline activated materials
ADES	Acidic Eutectic Solvents
ARRRA	Antwerp-Rotterdam-Rhine-Ruhr Area
BMU	Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety
BRTA	Basque Research and Technology Alliance
CCI	Chamber of Commerce and Industry
CCU	Carbon Capture and Usage
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
COR	Committee of the Regions
CPNL	the Circular Plastics Programme
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs
DESNZ	Department for Energy Security and Net Zero
DREAL	Regional Directorate for Environment; land planning and housing
DREETS	Regional Directorate for economy, work and employment and solidarity
EBZ	Economic Board of South Holland
EEA	European Environment Agency
EFA	The Efficiency Agency NRW
EKZ	Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate
EP	Equivalent population
E-PRTR	The European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF+	European Social Fund
FRATRI	Regional Funds for Accelerating the 3rd Industrial Revolution
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GPPD	Global Power Plant Database
GVA	Gross Value Added
Gwh	Gigawatt Hour
I-US	Industrial-urban symbiosis
IETF	Industrial Energy Transformation Fund
IPO	Association of Dutch Provinces
IS	Industrial symbiosis
IS	Industrial Symbiosis
JTF	Just Transition Fund
LANUV	The State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection
LEPs	Local Enterprise Partnerships
LRAs	Local and Regional Authorities
MCCA	Mayoral Combined County Authority
MMIPs	Multi-annual Mission Driven Innovation Programs
MRDH	Metropol Rotterdam Den Haag

MSI	Made Smarter Innovation
MSW	Municipal Solid waste
MUNV	Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Transport
NCEP	The Dutch National Circular Economy Program
NISP	National Industrial Symbiosis Programme
NRW	North Rhine–Westphalia
NWO	Dutch Research Council
OECD	Organisation of Economic Cooperation and Development
OEM	original equipment manufacturers
ONS	Office for National Statistics
OVAM	Flemish Waste Agency
PARP	The Polish Agency for Enterprise Development
R&D	Research and Development
REforMM	Resource Efficiency for Materials and Manufacturing
REP	German Resource Efficiency Programme
RRF	The Belgian Recovery and Resilience Plan
RRF	Resilience and Recovery Fund
RVCTI	Basque Science and Technology Network
RVO	Netherlands Enterprise Agency
SITC	Standard International Trade Classification
SMEs	Small and Medium Size Enterprises
SPRI	SPRI-Basque Business Development Agency
UA	Urban Area
UK	United Kingdom
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
UWWTP	Urban Wastewater Treatment Plant
VDI-ZRE	The German Centre for Resource Efficiency
VLAIO	Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship
WEEE	Waste from Electrical and Electronic Equipment
WIKE	Ministry of Economy, Industry, Climate Protection and Energy
WMCA	West Midlands Combined Authority
WRAP	Waste and Resources Action Programme
WWTP	Waste water treatment plant

Executive summary

The transition from linear industrial production systems to more sustainable models, such as industrial symbiosis (IS) and industrial-urban symbiosis (I-US), is critical for promoting a circular economy in Europe. Traditional linear production systems follow a "take-make-dispose" model, which results in significant resource waste, environmental degradation, and economic inefficiency. In contrast, I-US fosters a closed-loop system where waste from one industrial process becomes a resource for another, integrating industrial processes with urban areas to maximize resource efficiency, reduce waste, and minimize environmental impact. The H4C European Community of Practice (H4C ECoP) project is collaborating with the H4C Europe project to contribute to the promotion, identification, creation, and development of H4Cs. However, identifying and developing regions with the highest potential for implementing Hubs for Circularity (H4C) presents significant barriers identified in H4C ECoP's Task 1.3 Mapping of Non-technological barriers/enablers for 4 models of I-US implementation:

- Policy & Regulation
- Information flows
- Skill & Capabilities
- Behaviour & Stakeholder engagement
- Financial
- Organisational & Governance
- Commercial & Market

In this report, and in the context of Task 2.2 Detailed analysis for a selection of most promising regions/cities for I-US, the H4C European Community of Practice (H4C ECoP) project, aims to address these challenges by analysing, giving context, and describing various aspects of five promising regions for I-US previously identified in Task 2.1 EU Wide assessment of the regional potential for I-US:

- Basque Country (Spain)
- Flanders (Belgium, The Netherlands, and France)
- Midlands (United Kingdom)
- North Rhine-Westphalia (Germany)
- Silesian Voivodeship (Poland)

These aspects include the local context, geographical landscape, social landscape, economic and industrial landscape, policy analysis, material flows analysis, infrastructures for I-US, and symbiosis opportunities. In Task T2.2, the detailed analysis of the five regions revealed significant insights into their potential for I-US development:

- Comprehensive understanding of the local economic, social, industrial, and geographical contexts.
- Review of local policies affecting I-US and H4C initiatives.
- Analysis of industrial resource flows and mapping of key I-US infrastructures.
- Identification of symbiosis opportunities within each region

Additionally, Task 2.3 Replication analysis for H4C innovative value chains across Europe complements the earlier tasks by analysing the potential for replicating H4C innovative value chains across Europe. This task investigates where similar sets of industries exist that could replicate the synergies demonstrated in the European projects SYMSITES, WaterProof, and AshCycle. By mapping

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these sets, locations of potential replicated pilots, their distribution in European countries and examples of results are provided for developing exploitation strategies, helping to identify the best areas for replicating successful value chains.

The findings from these analyses offer valuable information to local actors, enabling them to implement I-US projects effectively and replicate existing projects. By providing in-depth insights into the potential and opportunities within these regions, local stakeholders can develop tailored strategies for establishing H4Cs.

1. Introduction

1.1 H4C ECoP Project

Hubs for Circularity (H4C) are at the heart of the implementation of a circular economy in Europe and the acceleration of the transition from linear industrial production systems to industrial symbiosis (IS) and industrial-urban symbiosis (I-US). The H4C European Community of Practice (H4C ECoP) project is collaborating with the H4C Europe project to contribute to the promotion, creation, and development of H4Cs. This is done in a series of activities, individual and collaborative amongst the two projects, that have the objective of developing tools and knowledge for actors involved in this activity. H4C ECoP activities include the development of a network of H4C stakeholders, a Key Performance Indicators methodology and adapted business models, identification, and promotion of funding opportunities for H4Cs and the generation of knowledge on the European potential for I-US, amongst others.

As part of the generation and publication of knowledge that facilitates the identification of opportunities for H4C and replication of I-US projects, Work Package 2 of the H4C ECoP project is dedicated to the analysis of the potential for H4C in European Regions and Municipalities. Work on this began at the start of the project with T2.1 EU Wide assessment of the regional potential for Industrial-Urban Symbiosis. The work in the task identified regions that showed the formation of industrial clusters that, due to the industrial activity present and their proximity to urban areas, could be fit to become H4Cs. This process had as a result the identification of 13 regions across Europe that showed high potential according to the parameters mentioned. The methodology used and results of this task were reported in Deliverable 2.1 on November 2023.

As explained, T2.1 was the start of a process of H4C high potential identification that is continuing with Task 2.2 “Detailed analysis for a selection of most promising regions/cities for I-US” and Task 2.3 “Replication analysis for H4C innovative value chains across Europe”. This deliverable is dedicated to the results of those tasks.

1.2 Task 2.2 Detailed analysis for a selection of most promising regions/cities for I-US

Task 2.2 is a collaborative task of the H4C ECoP project where Strane Innovation, ISQ, ISL, ICLEI, ACR+, and Climate-KIC combined their individual expertise to provide a more in-depth analysis for I-US promising European regions. This task builds directly on the results of Task 1.1 by performing an in-depth assessment of 5 of the 13 regions identified as high potential regions. The 5 regions analysed are:

1. Basque Country – Spain
2. Flanders – Belgium, The Netherlands and France
3. Midlands – United Kingdom
4. North Rhine-Westphalia – Germany
5. Silesian Voivodeship – Poland

The analysis of each region will provide a preliminary understanding on their I-US potential in a deeper sense than what was performed in T2.1, where only industrial activity and urban presence were analysed. This study has a descriptive vocation that will provide information to local actors in a public deliverable. The analysis is not meant to be prescriptive or to demonstrate H4C potential, but rather is meant to provide a landscape of the state of different I-US aspects to be considered for regional

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development (focused on I-US rather than CE), as well as provide clues for I-US perspectives and opportunities. T2.2 will include a literature review of the economic, social, industrial, and geographic context, followed by an analysis of the local policies concerning I-US and H4C, an industrial resources flow analysis and maps of the region's industrial activity, as well as some I-US key infrastructures. Each analysis section was performed by the partners applying a different methodology that will be explained in Section 2 "Methodology T2.2 Regional Analysis".

1.3 Task 2.3 Replication analysis for H4C innovative value chains across Europe

Task 2.3 complements T2.1 and T2.2 by focusing on the potential for replication of technologies at the centre of the H4C demo projects that H4C ECoP collaborates with as part of Work Package 3 tasks. Based on the I-US value chains that are proposed by the European projects SYMSITES, WaterProof and AshCycle, this task wants to answer the question: "Where in Europe can we find locations with similar set of industries that would make this synergy replicable?". By mapping the potential for replication, Strane Innovation will provide the projects' consortia with valuable information for their exploitation strategy.

To perform this task, ECoP worked with the projects to gather the information needed for the analysis, such as emitting industry, receiving industry, resource valorised or mutualised and technology used for a comprehensive understanding of the innovative value chains. Based on the provided I-US information and the geo-localized data collected in T2.1 and T2.2, Strane mapped every location in Europe with the same set of industrial facilities as in the mentioned H4C demos. This will help identify the greatest potential for value chain replication (in terms of number of locations with similar characteristics). Finally, the results will be cross-fertilised with the findings from T2.1 and in T2.2 on the most promising regions.

2. Methodology for T2.2 Regional Analysis

The Regional Analysis was a collaborative work amongst 6 different partners, and it was performed by studying very different aspects of the regions to describe it in I-US terms. The different aspects are described in the following sections of the present document:

1. Local context
 - a. Geographical landscape
 - b. Social landscape
 - c. Economic and Industrial landscape
2. Policy analysis
3. I-US potential analysis
 - a. Material flows mapping
 - b. I-US infrastructure mapping
4. Regional readiness assessment for I-US

Different methodologies were applied to describe such regional aspects. They are all described in this section.

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2.1 Local Context

2.1.1 Geographical landscape

The geographical landscape analysis was conducted through a qualitative and quantitative study of the region's characteristics obtained from online research and literature review. Data was sourced from regional reports, official government websites, as well as statistical offices and academic papers. The main areas of study are geographical positioning, population density, agricultural and industrial practices, as well as climate, relief, and soil factors.

The review research analysis focuses on five regions: the Silesia region, where the analysis is focused on the Silesia Voivodeship, not including the lower Silesia; secondly, in the Flanders region, the study covers the Belgium, French and Dutch parts of Flanders; thirdly, The Basque Country, also called the Basque Autonomous Community; thirdly, the Midlands region, including the West and East Midlands, although a focus was placed on the West Midlands due to its industrial relevance; and the state of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), where the analysis is outlined in the parts located in Western Germany, bordering Belgium, and the Netherlands.

2.1.2 Social landscape

The development of the social landscape analysis is based on comprehensive qualitative and quantitative data obtained through desktop research and a literature review. This review focused on the social profiles of the five regions under study, covering the following key areas:

- Population size
- Ethnicity
- Age
- Immigration patterns
- Education
- Healthcare
- Social Capital
- Safety and Security

Data was sourced from regional reports, including the regional innovation strategy, as well as statistical offices and academic papers.

2.1.3 Economic and Industrial landscape

The industrial and economic section were considered jointly due to the scope of the analysis, where the main goal was to develop a general overview of the industrial landscape and related economic influence on selected regions. Under this analysis the following subjects were covered:

- Industry composition (typology of industries, most relevant sectors, industrial trends)
- Industry transition and impact on the regional economy
- Employment and unemployment rates/ Workforce composition
- Technology and innovation regional economic data

Previously to the analysis, a challenge had to be overcome, the challenge related to the region's coverage, in some cases crossing the country's borders. In the case of the Silesian region, the analysis was focused on the Silesian Voivodeship, not including the lower Silesia.

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In the Flanders region, the analysis included the Belgium, French and Dutch parts of Flanders.

The Basque Country also called the Basque Autonomous Community, included this autonomous community in northern Spain.

The Midlands region included the West and East Midlands, although a focus was placed on the West Midlands due to its industrial relevance.

The state of North Rhine–Westphalia (NRW) analysis was outlined as the part located in western Germany, bordering Belgium, and the Netherlands.

Once the areas of the five regions were defined, the analysis process included a desktop research based on keywords for the compilation of a list of potentially relevant documents, that were screened to meet the proposed analysis objectives. The research key words included industrial composition, industry, economy, workforce, smart specialisation strategy, circular economy, technology, innovation, green economy, industrial trends, manufacturing, regional economy, industrial transition, economic sectors, I-US and IS for each region. The obtained content was written with the objective to compile and present the industrial and economic landscape in a clear and easy to understand way, focused on the region's most relevant sectors and its economic importance to the region.

Mapping

The database used for the mapping of industrial sites in each region was the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) database¹. The E-PRTR mainly lists the largest industrial sites in Europe, so smaller sites may be omitted from the analysis. Despite its limitations, it provides a uniform source of important data (around 50 000 industrial sites in Europe) that is easy to use. The reporting years of the facilities vary from 2007 to 2017, with the average year being 2015.

Industrial sectors have been classified according to the nomenclature used by Eurostat in the survey “Generation of waste, by waste category, hazardousness and NACE Rev. 2 activity [env_wasgen]”². This classification (detailed in Annex 1: NACE nomenclature used for the segmentation of the industrial landscape and the I-US potential analysis) makes it possible to respect the specificities of waste generation profiles by industrial sector, while at the same time providing a clear picture of the industrial structure of the regions concerned.

Finally, the mapping was carried out using the opensource software Qgis. Database processing, graphics plotting, and other manipulations were performed using Python algorithms developed by Strane. The images used for the map symbology come from the icons8 website³.

¹ « European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) - Microsoft Access Database and Text Format – European Environment Agency », <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/member-states-reporting-art-7-under-the-european-pollutant-release-and-transfer-register-e-prtr-regulation-23/european-pollutant-release-and-transfer-register-e-prtr-data-base>

² Eurostat, 2020, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/env_wasgen/default/table?lang=en&category=env.env_was.env_wasgt

³ Icons8 website: <https://icons8.com>

2.2 Policy Analysis

Unit of analysis: from clusters to administrative units

The high-potential regions are based on industrial activity. They are not necessarily within the same city and at times, they are crossing country borders. This created a challenge when looking into the contextual dimensions for each region. When talking about policy, one is referring to a governance level that designs and implements it. As a rule, that is a governmental authority (national, regional, or local). Further, policies are designed at different government levels depending on their competence but rarely at cross-country level. It became apparent; early on, that a correspondence/conversion exercise was necessary to be able to make sense of the policy analysis. Practically speaking, the regions identified contain a number of cities within each country, but they can also be scattered in several different regions. The scope of the study does not permit an analysis at city level. That would mean to analyse hundreds of cities separately. Further, such an approach would not be very meaningful as policies shaping industrial activity usually stem from region and national levels. We therefore started the analysis from the country level and complemented it with regional level where it was relevant/possible. The table below presents the territories that are included in the analysis for each cluster.

It is important to note that there are numerous local contexts with associated governance and financing models, which cannot be addressed within the scope of this report. A limitation of this analysis is therefore the lack of consideration of these local models, which may, in some cases, be more suitable when developing a policy or financing strategy.

Table 1 Clusters selected for in-depth analysis and the territorial/administrative coverage.

High potential cluster	Scope of the policy analysis
Flanders	The cluster encompasses 3 countries: BE, NL and FR. Both national and regional policy was included for all three regions. For The Netherlands, South Holland, for Belgium, Flanders and for France, Region Haut-de-France was analysed. For NL and FR, national policy was included and complemented by regional policy.
Basque Country	The analysis covers policies at the regional level of the Basque Autonomous Community in Spain and one policy at the city level of Vitoria-Gasteiz.
Midlands	The analysis covers policy at national level and the West Midlands region. Initial policy screening within the East Midlands was also carried out.
North Rhine-Westphalia	The analysis includes the state of North-Rhine-Westphalia, located in Germany, as well as national policy.
Silesian V. Region	Only the Silesian Voivodship is included in the analysis, although the historical Silesian region covers a bigger territory, including parts of Czechia.

Process

Once the scope was established, we started to compile a long list of potentially relevant documents (see Annex 2: List of the documents screened for policy analysis section for the full list of documents). This included policies directly related and/or potentially related to circular economy, such as industrial policies, climate strategies, European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), Smart Specialisation Strategy, circular economy action plans and waste management plans. This long-list of documents were then screened using multiple keywords in order to really focus on industrial symbiosis rather than staying generic on 'circular economy' level (e.g. industry, manufacturing, waste stream, valorisation. See the full list of keywords in the Annex 3: List of keywords used for screening/selecting the documents for in-depth analysis in the policy section). Screening of these documents with these keywords provided a first general understanding about whether they are directly related to I-US. If the answer was yes, we included the document in the short list. If not, we kept the record but did not analyse the document in detail.

If the initial documents referred to other documents/initiatives, these were added to the list and the keyword screening process was repeated.

Using the research questions, we conducted a review of these documents and pulled out the relevant text that was identified as relevant using an excel file. We then synthesised the text in order to draft the descriptive and critical part of the policy section. The research questions were:

- What is the policy framework: what are the latest existing policy initiatives to support I-US in the territory (National and regional policies)?
- Does the document mention any known/identified challenges to I-US?
- Are there any funding/financial support mechanisms set up by these initiatives?
- Are there any public I-US support hubs, programmes, support bodies to foster I-US set up by these initiatives? If yes, what are they? Do they target specific industries or not?
- For the multi-country site: does the National/regional documents mention the cross-border nature of the industrial activities? If yes, how?
- For initiatives identified, what roles are regional/city actors taking in implementing/facilitating them?
- Does the approach fit to a governance model as identified in the previous research?

Figure 1: The process, illustrated.

2.3 I-US potential analysis

The following methodology was employed in the production of each regional industrial symbiosis opportunity analysis.

Flow Mapping

The purpose of identifying the major flows, is that these commonly represent those of the greatest economic value and environmental impact. From these flows we then moved to assessing each for industrial symbiosis matching potential, highlighting those that are known to be scalable at industrial level from knowledge of global reported case study examples and delivery experience.

Sufficient data is available on industry type and NACE sector code, industry distribution and waste volumes by sector and end point to be able to conduct a very high-level appraisal. Data on industrial sectors, industrial sites and waste volume and treatment are extracted from the E-PRTR database⁴.

Sources of data used from the E-PRTR were as follows:

- Industries (NACE)
- Total waste, hazardous waste, and disposal destination (by NACE)
- Industrial sites

Using the available data, three prioritised lists were created:

- Industry type by number
- Total volume of waste produced
- Total amount of waste being disposed

⁴ « European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) - Microsoft Access Database and Text Format — European Environment Agency ». <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/member-states-reporting-art-7-under-the-european-pollutant-release-and-transfer-register-e-prtr-regulation-23/european-pollutant-release-and-transfer-register-e-prtr-data-base> .

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In the above, disposal volume being distinct from reuse, recovery and recycle end points as materials that are likely to attract the highest associated cost, be responsible for the highest environmental impact and therefore likely to be the most interesting and commercially viable for industrial symbiosis opportunities in any given region.

Where industries repeatedly appeared across these filtered lists then they were taken forward as a priority sector for the region.

I-US infrastructure mapping

A review of each regional landscape analysis was concluded to ensure no obvious infrastructure barriers could be identified in creating industrial symbiosis synergies. Where available information on existing or planned waste management infrastructure was also considered, along with any potential connectivity issues for transporting resources from A to B.

For each region, the transport infrastructures were investigated, including the motorway and railway network. The data on roads and railways was extracted from OpenStreetMap^{5 6} using Overpass-turbo API⁷. Energy infrastructures were also mapped using the Global Power Plant Database (GPPD)⁸. Excess heat from industrial sites and wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) and heat demand from urban area (UA) has also been analysed using the modelling data from the Heat RoadMap Europe project⁹.

3. Regional analysis: Basque Country - Spain

3.1. Local Context

3.1.1. Geographical landscape

The Basque Country, known as Euskadi in Basque and País Vasco in Spanish, is a region in northern Spain. It is situated at the western end of the Pyrenees Mountain range, which separates it from the Basque Country of France to the northeast. The region is bounded by the Bay of Biscay to the north, Navarra to the east, La Rioja to the south, and Cantabria and Burgos to the west. It consists of the provinces of Biscay, Guipuzkoa, and Álava, covering an area of 7,234 km²¹⁰.

Major rivers in the Basque Country include the Nervión, which flows through Bilbao, and the Ebro, forming part of the region's southern boundary. These rivers have historically been important for transportation, agriculture, and industry. Although natural lakes are less common, the region has several reservoirs, such as Ullibarri-Gamboa and Lareo, which are crucial for water supply and recreation.

⁵ Railways—OpenStreetMap Wiki. (s. d.). <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Railways>

⁶ Highway—OpenStreetMap Wiki. <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:highway>

⁷ Overpass turbo – OSM API. (s. d.). <https://overpass-turbo.eu/>

⁸ Global Energy Observatory, Google, KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm, Enipedia, World Resources Institute. 2018. Global Power Plant Database. Published on Resource Watch and Google Earth Engine; <http://resourcewatch.org/> <https://earthengine.google.com/>

⁹ Heat RoadMap project : <https://heatroadmap.eu/>, shapefiles from : <https://s-eenergies-open-data-euf.hub.arcgis.com/>

¹⁰ Gobierno Vasco, Conocer el País Vasco, 2009, Accessed: Junio 10, 2024, Available; chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfefindmkaj/https://www.euskadi.eus/contenidos/noticia/presentacion_pais_08/es_p_pais/adjuntos/conocer_pais_vasco_es.pdf

The main mountain range forms the watershed between the Atlantic and Mediterranean basins. The highest point in the range is the Aizkorri massif at 1,551 meters. The region is divided into three main areas:

- **Atlantic Basin:** Characterized by many valleys with short rivers, such as the Nervión, Urola, and Oria, flowing from the mountains to the Bay of Biscay. The coast is rugged, with high cliffs and small inlets. Key coastal features include the Bilbao Abra Bay, the Estuary of Bilbao, the Urdaibai estuary, and the Bidasoa-Txingudi Bay, which forms the border with France. This slope in the north is densely populated and industrialized, having exploited its extensive resources of iron and timber since the late Middle Ages¹¹.
- **Middle Section:** This area is mainly occupied by a high plateau called Llanada Alavesa (the Álava Plains), where the capital Vitoria-Gasteiz is located. Rivers in this area, including the Zadorra and Bayas, flow south from the mountains to the Ebro River. This area is suitable for cultivating cereals and grapes, counting with smaller populations and more isolated villages around¹². However, and despite its agricultural roots, Vitoria-Gasteiz, has seen significant industrialization since the early 1950s.
- **Ebro Valley:** Extending from the southern mountains to the Ebro River, the Rioja Alavesa area shares the Mediterranean characteristics of other Ebro Valley zones and is notable for producing some of Spain's Rioja wine.

The Basque Country's climate is temperate and generally rainy, with annual precipitation ranging from 2,000 mm in humid areas to 500 mm in the Ribera del Ebro. The region's mountains create distinct microclimates: subalpine in the Pyrenean zone; Atlantic or temperate-humid along the coast, characterized by mild temperatures and high rainfall; and continental Mediterranean in southern Álava and central and southern Navarra, with greater temperature variations. This varied climate supports diverse vegetation, including lush, green landscapes in the Coastal areas, while inland regions support both temperate forests and alpine flora at higher elevations.

3.1.2. Social landscape

The Basque Country, an autonomous community within Spain, is distinguished by its unique cultural, linguistic, and historical identity, alongside a strong sense of regional pride. Governed by its own parliament and government, the Basque Country exercises significant self-governance in education, industry, culture, health, and social services.

With a population of 2,201,462 and a density of 304.3 inhabitants per square kilometer, the Basque Country's demographic distribution is as follows: 15% in Álava, 52.2% in Bizkaia, and 32.8% in Gipuzkoa¹³.

Historically, immigration to the Basque Country originated from other parts of Spain, particularly Galicia and Castile and León during the 20th century. In recent years, however, most immigrants come from abroad. As of January 1, 2021, 28.7% of the Basque Country's residents were born outside the

¹¹ Britannica, Basque Country, 2024, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Basque-Country-region-Spain>

¹² Euskadi, Geography, Accessed June 10, 2024, Available: <https://tourism.euskadi.eus/basque-country-guide/geography/>

¹³ Eustat. Censo de población y viviendas. Estructura de la población, 2024, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: https://www.eustat.eus/estadisticas/tema_268/opt_1/temas.html

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region, with 39.2% of these individuals born abroad. The leading countries of origin are Morocco (11.4%), Colombia (10.9%), Romania (6.4%), and Nicaragua (6.1%)¹⁴.

The Basque Country actively promotes the integration of immigrants and social cohesion while preserving its cultural identity through language programs and cultural initiatives. However, social polarization remains a challenge, with both full integration and severe exclusion growing, reducing intermediate social categories¹⁵.

Demographically, the Basque Country presents a fertility rate that is notably low compared to other European countries, with an average of 1.20 children per woman in 2020, below the European average of 1.5. Furthermore, it faces a decline in its youth population, driven by challenges in youth employment and talent retention, while the number of older residents increases. In 2021, only 18.2% of the population was under 20 years old, whereas 23% were aged 65 and over¹⁶.

The Basque Country's official languages are Spanish and Euskera (or Basque language), the latter being one of the oldest and most unique languages in Europe. The Sociolinguistic Survey reveals that between 1991 and 2021, the number of Basque speakers increased by over 261,000, thanks to the language's strong presence in education, culture, society, and digital media. In 2021, 45.3% of the population above age 16 spoke only Spanish, 36.2% spoke Basque, and 18.6% were passive speakers. In Gipuzkoa, 51.8% of the population speaks Basque, followed by Biscay at 30.6%, and Álava at 22.4%¹⁷.

The Basque Country is home to several universities, including the University of the Basque Country (EHU/UPV), which plays a pivotal role in higher education and research. Numerous research institutions contribute to the region's reputation for innovation and technological advancement.

Around 200,000 people in the Basque Country are affected by excessive housing expenses poses the most significant challenge for residents, affecting 15.2% of the population. serious job instability (13.8%); unemployment of all people of active age residing in the home (9.7%); economic difficulties in purchasing medicines or following medical treatments (9.2%) and limitations on political participation (8.6%)¹⁸.

¹⁴ Eustat, Panorama demografico 2022, 2023, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfefindmkaj/https://www.eustat.eus/elementos/ele0019900/panorama-demografico/inf0019909_c.pdf

¹⁵ Fundacion Foessa, Informe sobre exclusion y desarrollo social en Euskadi 2022, 2023, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfefindmkaj/https://www.foessa.es/main-files/uploads/sites/16/2022/02/Informes-Territoriales-2022.-EUSKADI.pdf>

¹⁶ Gobierno Vasco, Inkesta Soziolinguistikoa 2021, 2023, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfefindmkaj/https://www.euskadi.eus/contenidos/informacion/eas_ikerketak/eu_def/adjuntos/VII.-INKESTA-SOZIOLINGUISTIKOA_laburpena.pdf

¹⁷ Eustat, Panorama demografico 2022, 2023, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfefindmkaj/https://www.eustat.eus/elementos/ele0019900/panorama-demografico/inf0019909_c.pdf

¹⁸ Fundacion Foessa, Informe sobre exclusion y desarrollo social en Euskadi 2022, 2023, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgiclfefindmkaj/https://www.foessa.es/main-files/uploads/sites/16/2022/02/Informes-Territoriales-2022.-EUSKADI.pdf>

Remarkably, the Basque Country is noted for its high social spending. Following Asturias, it registers the highest per capita spending on social protection, equating to 135% of the average per capita spending of Spain as a whole¹⁹.

3.1.3. Economic and Industrial landscape

The Basque Country is recognized as one of the most industrialized regions in Spain. As a highly industrialized region, its manufacturing sector makes up to 10.5% of all industrial output in Spain and contributes 21.4% to the country's GDP. In 2022, the GDP per capita reached €35,832, the second highest in Spain. The Basque Country has been a crucial industrial hub, specialized in sectors such as iron and steel, shipbuilding, transport equipment, and machinery. In 2022, export goods originating from the region's industrial activity represented 41% of its GDP (79.359 billion euros), with the most significant exports being automobiles, iron and steel, and industrial machinery^{20 21}.

The industrial landscape and industrial sectors distribution of the Basque Country is detailed in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Industrial clusters are mainly concentrated in the North of the region around the cities of Bilbao and San Sebastian. The sector of "Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment" represents 49% of the industrial landscape in terms of number of facilities. Among this sector, three activities are predominant:

- Treatment and coating of metals (37 sites)
- Casting of iron (25 sites)
- Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys (20 sites)

The next major industrial sectors with the number of sites as a percentage of the total number of sites are as follows:

- Manufacture of chemical, pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic products (11%)
- Waste collection, treatment, and disposal activities; materials recovery (10%)
- Manufacture of paper and paper products, printing, and reproduction of recorded media (7%)
- Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, electrical equipment, motor vehicles and other transport equipment (6%)

Transitioning from heavy industry to environmentally sustainable and digitized structures, the region embarked on a green and digital transformation process over three decades ago. Presently, it stands among Europe's wealthiest regions and continues to invest in green innovation²⁰.

The transport and mobility sectors have been very important to the Basque Country development, whether by sea, land, or air, sustaining industrial growth and contributing to exports. The Basque Country, which has closely connected traditions to maritime activities, has an economy heavily influenced by the maritime industry. The Basque automotive sector contributes almost 45% of the total production volume of the Spanish automotive industry, thus demonstrating its competitiveness, importance, and weight in the local economy, with 100.000 jobs created and 300 companies in the region in 2024. One of the critical sectors in the Basque Country is the aeronautics industry, which is

¹⁹ Irekia, 2019, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available: <https://www.irekia.euskadi.eus/es/news/58850-beatriz-artolazabal-inclusion-social-mejorado-notablemente-euskadi>

²⁰ CaixaBank Research. (2024). Autonomous Community Outlook, Basque Country. Accessed: May 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.caixabankresearch.com/sites/default/files/content/file/2024/01/22/34454/f-ccaa-pais-vasco-en.pdf>

²¹ European Cluster Collaboration Platform. (n.d.). *Cluster GAIA, Basque Country, Spain. Digital, Green and Social Transition in the Basque Country*. Accessed: May 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://clustercollaboration.eu/content/cluster-gaia-basque-country-spain>

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renowned for producing highly skilled jobs (14.586 jobs in 2024) and high-value products. The vast industrial experience, concentration of suppliers, significant technology plans and R&D initiatives, and a high degree of internationalization contribute to the region being a centre of excellence in aeronautics. To support such robust industrial activity, the railroad sector provides solutions and services tailored to the specific needs of each operator and project. The industries strong commitment to innovation and technological developments has been a key factor in this highly internationalized region^{22 23}.

The machine-tool industry in the Basque Country has a crucial role in producing various components for aeronautical and automobile manufacturers. With 90% of the country's machine-tool production and 7.489 jobs created, the Basque Country is not only a national, but also an international powerhouse, being the third largest producer in Europe and the ninth largest in the world. This international expansion was very much due to centres like the Institute of Training and Innovation in Machine Tools (IMH), Invema (research institute), and the AFM cluster contributing to industry growth relying on innovation and technological development. These centres and clusters are an example of the strong commitment to innovation and technological development^{22 23}.

Acting in the energy sector, EVE (Basque Energy Board) from the Basque Government Agency is responsible for developing projects and initiatives with companies in line with the policies defined by the government. These companies have a robust scientific-technological support infrastructure promoting a strategic commitment to offshore wind power, marine energy, smart grids, energy storage and transportation^{22 23}.

The Basque bioregion, also known as BioBasque, with 7.300 jobs created and 150 companies, in 2024, is an example of cooperation between the medical community, academia, and business, bolstered by an extensive infrastructure network and an entrepreneurial-friendly state administration. The economic sector in the bioregion benefits from the convergence of multiple technological and knowledge domains. Deep roots in engineering, manufacturing, microtechnology, electronics, robotics, and automation, as well as the latest developments in nanotechnology, all contribute to the competence in biologics^{22 23}.

The food industry has a relevant role in the Basque Country, with strong investments in the agri-food sector originating 6.286 jobs, in 2024. Predominant in the inner Basque Country, the food industry is particularly represented by the meat, milk, confectionery, and fish sectors, preserving a long gastronomic tradition^{22 23}.

²² ICEX, Invest in Spain. (2020). The Basque Country/Euskadi. Key industries. Accessed: May 20, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.investinspain.org/en/regions/pais-vasco/industrias-destacadas>

²³ SPRI Group. The Basque Business Development Agency. (2024). Invest in Basque Country. Accessed: May 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.spri.eus/en/invest-in-basque-country/>

Figure 2: Mapping of industrial sites in the Basque Country (icons from icons8.com).

Figure 3: Industrial sectors distribution and zoom into the Bilbao cluster (icons from icons8.com).

3.2. Policy Analysis

Overview

The relationship between the environmental policies of the Spanish government and those of the Basque Government is shaped by Spain's decentralized political structure, which grants significant autonomy to its regions. In Spain, each autonomous community, including the Basque Country, has its own Statute of Autonomy, which defines the scope of its self-governing powers. The Basque Statute of Autonomy grants the Basque Government significant control over environmental policy within its territory.

As for regional legislation, the Basque Government has the authority to develop and implement its own environmental policies and regulations, provided they meet or exceed the minimum standards set by national and EU laws. The Basque Government is then responsible for the implementation and enforcement of both national and regional environmental laws within its territory. This includes managing natural resources, pollution control, waste management, and other environmental issues.

The Basque Government often goes beyond the minimum standards set by the central government, implementing more stringent environmental measures to address specific regional challenges. This proactive approach reflects the Basque Country's commitment to sustainability and environmental protection. Overall, the Basque Government adopts and adapts Spanish policies within its regional context, ensuring compliance with national and EU standards while leveraging its autonomy to address local environmental challenges effectively and with higher ambition.

Policies specifically targeting IS and/or I-US and their origins

There is not a specific policy dedicated to IS and/or I-US in the Basque country nor in Spain, but industrial symbiosis principles and resource efficiency narrative appear in several policies and guiding documents.

At the national level, the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy and Action Plan gives a superficial definition of Industrial Symbiosis as “*a business strategy that consists of connecting various industries in order to reduce the need for virgin raw materials and waste disposal, thus closing the material loop, a fundamental characteristic of the circular economy and a driver for green growth and eco-innovative solutions. It can also reduce emissions and energy use and create new revenue streams*”²⁴. For this and the reason explained in the introduction, relevant policy documents were identified only at the regional level using the methodology outlined above, of which 10 were selected for in-depth analysis based on key word screening. To provide a more comprehensive overview, the analysis also included five sectoral reports on key sectors potentially relevant for industrial symbiosis, and a relevant strategy at the city level.

- Overarching Strategies
 - Basque Circular Economy Strategy 2030
 - Basque Energy Strategy 2030

²⁴ Gobierno de España, 2020, Estrategia Española de Economía Circular, España Circular 2030, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at:<https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/calidad-y-evaluacion-ambiental/temas/economia-circular/estrategia.html>

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- Climate Change Strategy 2050 of the Basque Country
- Bultzatu 2050: The Urban Agenda of the Basque Country
- Relevant frameworks specific to certain policy fields
 - Environmental Framework Program of the Basque Country 2030
 - Basque 2030 Science, Technology, and Innovation Plan
 - Industrial development and internationalization plan 2021-2024
 - Basque Waste Prevention and Management Plan 2030
 - Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024
 - Basque Transition Plan and Climate Change 2021-2024
- Reports on key sectors in the circular economy
 - Sectoral report on the chemical sector
 - Sectoral report on the food and beverage sector
 - Sectoral report on the means of transport sector
 - Sectoral report on the metal sector
 - Sectoral report on the construction sector
- City-level strategy
 - Industry Support Plan 2021-2024, Victoria-Gasteiz

Main Actors with work relevant for industrial-urban symbiosis

In the Basque Government, the two main Ministries responsible for the disposition of the policies considered in the analysis are the 1) *Department of Environment, Territorial Planning and Housing* (Estrategia de Economía Circular de Euskadi 2030; Bultzatu 2050: La Agenda Urbana de Euskadi;) and 2) the *Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment of the Basque Government* (Plan de desarrollo industrial e internacionalización 2021-2024; Plan de Prevención y Gestión de Residuos de Euskadi 2030; Plan De Economía Circular Y Bioeconomía 2024; Programa Marco Ambiental De Euskadi 2030; Plan de Transición Energética y cambio Climático 2021-2024; Estrategia Energética de Euskadi 2030).

The implementation and monitoring of many of the initiatives set-up by the policies often lies with the **public environmental management company of the Basque Government, Ihobe**. Its objective is to support the Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment in the development of environmental policy and in the extension of the culture of environmental sustainability in the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country. Ihobe's purpose is to improve the environment, integrating environmental criteria into sectoral policies as an element of sustainable competitive value. It is an exemplary and innovative public organization that promotes environmental improvement in the Basque Country, in collaboration with public administrations, companies and citizens, as well as at the international level to position the Basque Country as an advanced region in improving the environment and sustainability. Ihobe manages relevant initiatives, among which three are particularly relevant in the I-US context:

- **Basque Eco-design Center:** it is a private-public partnership promoted by 9 large companies and 2 public societies, with the aim of fostering the conceptualization and execution of innovative eco-design projects for the generation of knowledge and subsequent transfer to the Basque industrial fabric. Its main lines of activity consist of the integration of life cycle thinking in partner organizations and their supply chains, the environmental evaluation and

improvement of organizations, products and buildings with a life cycle approach, the research and piloting of new circular business models and use of circular materials, the development of projects aimed at generating a change in the consumption model, and the prevention and optimal management of waste, including food waste.²⁵

- **Basque Circular Hub:** it is an initiative whose objective is to offer advanced circular economy services in Euskadi. The hub aims to facilitate implementation of circular economy projects in Basque companies, to serve as the Circular Economy Observatory of the Basque Country, to provide advanced training in circular economy and to offer technical tools to companies.²⁶
- **Udalsarea 21:** it is the Basque Network of Municipalities towards Sustainability, a cooperation forum that energizes the Local Agendas 21 of the Basque municipalities and integrates 200 municipalities together with different areas of the Government.²⁷

Another entity created by the Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment of the Basque Government to promote the Basque industry is the **SPRI-Basque Business Development Agency**. It supports, promotes, and contributes to the competitive improvement of Basque companies, thereby collaborating with the generation of wealth in Euskadi and the improvement of the well-being of its citizens, within the scope of the Economic Promotion Policy of the Basque Government²⁸. As part of the SPRI Group, the **Basque Digital Innovation Hub** has been created to act as a connected network to provide Basque companies with assets and advanced manufacturing services for training, research, testing and validation of technology. The network provides SMEs with the technological capabilities they need to rise to the challenges of smart industry, energy, and health, and to be able to grow in a more digital and sustainable environment²⁹. Also, the SPRI Group supported the creation of the **Bind 4.0 program**, a public-private accelerator program that guarantees access for international technological start-ups to leading Basque client companies of the highest level, through projects incorporating technology and innovative solutions³⁰. The BIND 4.0 program aims to support the startups selected by accelerating their development and growth through an intense working program in the Basque Country that lasts 24 weeks.

Other type of relevant actors for I-US in the region are research associations and institutes that operate in collaboration with other organizations to ensure the competitiveness of the industry and regional technological advancements. Among these, some notable actors are:

- The **Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA)**, established to tackle the industrial challenges of the Basque Country and to compete with leading international research and technology organizations. This alliance aims to be the forefront of Basque research in Europe

²⁵ Basque Ecodesign Center Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.basqueecodesigncenter.net/>

²⁶ Basque Circular Hub Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.basquecircularhub.eus/>

²⁷ Udalsarea 21 Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.udalsarea2030.eus/>

²⁸ SPRI Group Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.spri.eus/en/>

²⁹ Basque Digital Innovation Hub Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://bdih.spri.eus/en/>

³⁰ Gobierno Vasco, 2020, Plan de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/pcti-2030/web01-a2pcti30/es/>

and globally. Formed through a collaboration agreement, BRTA includes 16 technology centres and 4 cooperative research centres from the Basque Network of Science, Technology, and Innovation, alongside the Basque Government, the Provincial Councils of Álava, Bizkaia, and Gipuzkoa, and the SPRI Group. The main goals of BRTA are to enhance cooperation among members of the Basque Science and Technology Network (RVCTI), to develop a coordinated scientific-technological agenda that addresses the challenges and needs of Basque companies, and to improve their international standing.³¹

- The **Orkestra, Basque Institute of Competitiveness** is an initiative of the University of Deusto, through the Deusto Foundation, for the study of competitiveness and regional development through different lines of research, with three goals: 1) Contribute to the improvement of the Basque Country's competitiveness, 2) Promote the improvement of citizens' wellbeing and 3) Create knowledge of regional competitiveness. It promotes transformative research and cooperates with several networks, businesses, governments, and institutions.³²
- The **Cluster GAIA** is the Association of Industry of Knowledge and Applied Technologies (ICTA) from the Basque Country, a private and professional non-profit organisation, established in 1983, currently made up of 301 companies that offer products and services in the field of electronics, information technology, consulting, engineering, and telecommunications. The ICTA Basque Country sector constitutes a competitive advantage to accelerate the transformation of companies, territory, and society with the aim of positioning Euskadi in the Basque Country.³³

Funding Mechanisms and other support instruments

The Basque Regional government offers many grants and aid programmes to companies in the region, and those dedicated to the Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment amount to a total of 284 different programmes (a complete list can be found at the Euskadi website³⁴). The most relevant funding programmes offered or reinforced within the context of the analysed policies are:

Pyme Circular: launched at the end of 2021 through Ihobe, it is a specific line of aid to support the Euskadi 2030 circular economy strategy by financing the development of projects that correspond to any of the following typologies:

- Identification of circular opportunities through market surveillance, or diagnosis in circular economy, or with reflection and an action plan to face new challenges.
- Life cycle approach and differentiation in the market to determine the environmental impacts of a product, organization, or service, obtaining recognition such as environmental footprints, eco-labels, etc.

³¹ Basque Research and Technology Alliance Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.brta.eus/en/home>

³² Orkestra Basque Institute of Competitiveness Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.orkestra.deusto.es/en/>

³³ GAIA Website, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://gaia.es/>

³⁴ Euskadi Website – Trámites, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/tramites-servicios/?r01kQry=tT:ayuda_subvencion;cA:r01e00000ff26d46212a470b845ecb637861b7081;mA:documentLanguage.EQ.es,procedu reCollection.EQ.0;pp:r01PageSize.20;p:Inter,Inter_portal&r01SearchEngine=meta

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- Environmental improvement and anticipation of circular regulations with the implementation of environmental improvements in products and services.
- Sustainability of the value chain and brand reputation to respond to the green requirements of large client organizations.
- Creation of new circular strategies related to extending the useful life of products, materials, and components (reuse, recycle and recover, repair, recondition, remanufacture); with servitization (transformation from product to service); **industrial symbiosis**; or new models based on rental and shared use of products and services, in electronics and sustainable transport and mobility.

As for the sectors, the call is aimed primarily and in a non-exclusive manner at the value chains of the sectors identified in the European Circular Economy Action Plan and the Basque Circular Economy Strategy 2030: Transport sector (automotive, railway, aeronautical, naval); Auxiliary equipment, machinery and machine tool sector; Electrical-electronic sector aimed at the renewable market (including equipment and components); Metal sector; Chemical sector; Construction sector; Food sector; Recycling and environmental remediation sector; Packaging design and manufacturing sector³⁵.

Berpiztu: Approved by the Basque Government Council in 2020, Berpiztu is the ‘Program for the Economic Reactivation and Employment of Euskadi (2020-2024)’ in whose timeframe are included policies such as the PCTI2030 and the Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024. This programme is structured into two large vertical axes of action that are deployed in 12 policies and 60 lines of action that constitute the reference framework for different measures and instruments in terms of recovery and stimulation of employment and the economy to be developed during the period of scope of the Program. Likewise, a third axis or transversal area is defined related to improving the quality of employment, which constitutes the thirteenth policy of the Program. In all the previous policies and lines of action, as well as in all its programs and measures, the gender perspective is incorporated.

Euskadi Next: The Euskadi Next 2021-2026 Program is the investment program for the recovery, transformation, and resilience of Euskadi that the Basque Government, in coordination with the three Provincial Councils and the City Councils of the three Basque capitals. It represents a clear commitment to economic transformation and to enhance the strengths of Euskadi in the use of European funds from the Recovery and Resilience Mechanism (MRR). It brings together a coherent and consistent set of public and public-private initiatives designed to address the challenges of the energy-ecological transition, the digital transition and social cohesion, and circular economy constitutes one of the eight components tackled through the programme. Euskadi Next includes specific projects that could have a total investment impact of 18,286M/€ -European funds and public and private own resources. In addition to this Program, companies and other private organizations can

³⁵ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Programa de ayudas PYME Circular 2021 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.ihobe.eus/euskadi/programa-ayudas-pyme-circular-2021>

access these funds collected in the budgets of the different Administrations through public tenders and calls for subsidy programs.³⁶

Gauzatu Industria: This program supports the promotion of Industrial SMEs or those that are related to the industry and have a technological and/or innovative base, with the purpose of increasing their impact on the technological development and innovation. Total budget allocated for this programme is 28,000,000 euros and the support is provided in the form of reimbursable aid, proportional to the investments made and with a maximum of 200,000 euros per job created or 150,000 euros for the maintenance of the initial workforce. Applications are granted based on competitive competition criteria and taking into account the technological and/or innovative base of each company. In this way, the sector in which the company works will be analysed, prioritizing those with high levels of technology such as Energy, Advanced Manufacturing and Bioscience or Biohealth. In addition, the resources invested in R&D and technological innovation will also be taken into account, as well as the ability to transfer this knowledge to new products or processes that will be introduced into the market.³⁷

Hazitek: The Hazitek 2024 R&D aid program has been designed to promote Research and Development Projects, both in SMEs, large companies, and associations of Basque companies. Regulated by the Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment of the Basque Government through the SPRI group, it aims to support companies to 1) Develop new products, processes, and services, 2) Investigate how to improve the services or products offered, or 3) Improve the competitiveness through R&D. The program's budget for 2024 is 92,500,000 euros and the aid offers non-refundable grants to provide the necessary resources for Industrial Research or Experimental Development and its budget is divided into two groups depending on the competitive or strategic nature of the projects.³⁸

Fast Track Innobideak: This programme, managed through the SPRI Group, was created to accelerate the development of innovation projects that promote the competitiveness, specialization and diversification of Basque industrial SMEs and services related to the industry. Through technologies and business models that respond to the priorities and transitions included in the RIS3 Euskadi framework, it also contributes to the systematization process of innovation. Over the last 7 years, the programme has approved more than 700 projects and provided 46,800,00 euros of direct monetary investment.³⁹

BASQUE INDUSTRY 4.0: Implemented by the Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment of the Basque Government, it is an aid program to support R&D projects that lead to

³⁶ Euskadi Website - Euskadi Next / Programas, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/euskadi-next-programas/web01-a2ogafon/es/>

³⁷ SPRI Group Website - Gauzatu Industria 2024, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.spri.eus/es/ayudas/gauzatu-industria/>

³⁸ SPRI Group Website - Hazitek 2024, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.spri.eus/es/ayudas/hazitek/>

³⁹ SPRI Group Website - Fast Track Innobideak 2024, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.spri.eus/es/ayudas/fast-track-innobideak/>

the transfer of technology from "technological testers" (as, for example, RVCTI agents) to industrial companies and advanced services, having a demonstration effect and thus allowing to accelerate the transfer to the market of the results of R&D projects in TEICs⁴⁰.

Cluster Policy

In the early 1990s, the Basque Country introduced an innovative industrial policy focused on clustering. These cluster associations are location-based partnerships that act as dynamic agents to boost the competitiveness of associated companies through collaborative strategic projects as all partners in a Basque cluster work cooperatively, to improve competitiveness and meet demands for internationalisation, innovation, and sustainability. Since 2000, the Basque government has increased its oversight of funding for these associations. Nearly two decades later, twelve clusters, representing 6% of companies, now contribute to 28% of the region's employment and 32% of its added value, and additionally, six new pre-clusters have been supported by the Basque Government since 2009^{41,42}.

Clusters get support from a network of Strategic Sector Observatories, an idea from the Department of Industry, Innovation, Trade and Tourism of the Basque Government for identifying the knowledge needs of Basque companies, facilitating access to strategic information, offering supervision or prospective mechanisms, and empowering priority clusters as key elements in the innovation system. The Industrial development and internationalization plan 2021-2024 identifies clusters as key facilitators of collaborative dynamics that encourage cooperation around one or several value chains and allow companies to adapt and position themselves in the opportunities and new value chains that arise around the three transitions (energy-climate, technical-digital, and demographic-social) and thus directs its competitiveness and cooperation levers axis to the promotion of cluster programs as a source of product and market diversification as well as engine for technological development and internationalization of our industry⁴³.

A critical reading of the policies

General context

The Basque Country is characterized by its high degree of self-governance and significant contributions to Spain's GDP through sectors such as automotive, aeronautics, and energy. Its industry is robust and innovative, and it benefits from a well-educated workforce, extensive research institutions, and a strong tradition of technological advancement. However, the region faces unique challenges: the transition towards sustainable and digital industries requires balancing economic growth with environmental preservation. The region's industrial heritage, particularly in iron and steel, shipbuilding,

⁴⁰ Gobierno Vasco, 2020, Plan de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/pcti-2030/web01-a2pcti30/es/>

⁴¹ Aragón Amonarriz, C., Aranguren, M. J., & Iturrioz Landart, C., 2010, Evaluación de políticas clúster: el caso del País Vasco. *Evaluación de políticas clúster: el caso del País Vasco*.

⁴² Aranguren Querejeta, M. J. (2010). Política clúster del País Vasco: lecciones aprendidas y retos. *Revista EAN*, (68), 86-99.

⁴³ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de desarrollo industrial e internacionalización 2021-2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/06-plan-estrategico-de-desarrollo-industrial-e-internacionalizacion/>

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and transport equipment, necessitates continuous innovation to remain competitive and the environmental pressures pose challenges on resource use. To address these factors, it is necessary to take a multifaceted approach, integrating competitiveness, innovation, and sustainability to ensure the region's continued prosperity and resilience. Coordinated efforts among various industrial clusters and administrations, and a focus on circular and smart specialization strategies are essential to addressing these challenges effectively.

Industrial symbiosis as a pathway to resource efficiency and competitiveness

The need for making the Basque industrial sector more circular is a driving force for the introduction of symbiosis principles in policies and it is seen as a means to make the industry less reliant on increasingly scarce resources – and thus less reliant on materials import and extraction – and more competitive. Even when the industrial symbiosis concept is not explicitly mentioned, several policies address the importance of the industry's transition towards models of increased resource efficiency and creation of high value products by taking a full lifecycle approach to production and post-life treatment.

The Basque Circular Economy Strategy 2030 is probably the most relevant policy in this sense. It specifically identifies Industrial Symbiosis as a key action to be pursued by 2025 in the 'Waste and Secondary Raw Materials Management' pillar⁴⁴. Despite no further definition of the IS concept is given in the strategy, the line of action 10 'Secondary raw materials' argues it is crucial to establish mechanisms that guarantee the stability of the supply and encourage demand from the most intensive sectors, and thus proposes measures, such as implementing a landfill tax or requiring the use of a recycled percentage of CDW or steel aggregate, which can lead to boosting symbiotic relations across value chains⁴⁵. This is a strategy stemming from the acknowledgment that the Basque Country is highly dependent on imports of materials (77% of the raw materials of Basque industry are imported), mainly fossil fuels, metallic minerals, biomass, and non-metallic minerals, and thus increasing material productivity allows to decouple economic growth from material consumption⁴⁶.

In preparation to the strategy, the Basque Circular Economy Diagnosis concluded that the industrial sector of Euskadi is seen as the pillar on which to articulate the transformation towards a more circular economy⁴⁷. This sector contributes almost 25% to the GDP of the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country, it is the most intensive sector in consumption of materials (mostly imported) and in waste generation and presents interesting opportunities for improvement linked to eco-design, remanufacturing, and advanced repair, servitization and recovery of metals and plastics. Within the industrial sector, the opportunities associated with the sub-sectors of metal, automotive, machinery-

⁴⁴ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Claves de la Estrategia de Economía Circular del País Vasco 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/documentacion/2020/estrategia-de-economia-circular-de-euskadi-2030/web01-a2ingkut/es/>

⁴⁵ Gobierno Vasco, 2019, Estrategia de Economía Circular de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/documentacion/2020/estrategia-de-economia-circular-de-euskadi-2030/web01-a2ingkut/es/>

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*

⁴⁷ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Economía Circular en la Industria del País Vasco - Diagnostico [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: https://www.euskadi.eus/contenidos/documentacion/economia_circular/es_def/adjuntos/EstrategiaEconomiaCircular2030.pdf

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tools, other means of transportation and energy and other electrical equipment stand out⁴⁸. Moreover, the Diagnosis document states that it is important to reduce the pollution that occurs in water, to reduce the energy consumed and the quantity and danger of the waste generated and that although water reuse has not been considered a priority for action, its potential development in urban and industrial areas must be considered⁴⁹.

Acknowledging this marked industrial character in the Basque Country, the Basque Country Waste Prevention and Management Plan 2030 also presents industrial symbiosis as a way to generate economic value at the local level between companies that generate considerable industrial waste⁵⁰.

The Industrial development and internationalization plan 2021-2024 structures the renewal of competitiveness in the region upon two principles, including ‘systemic and strategic value chains perspective’ which argues for an integrated management throughout and between value and supply chains⁵¹. To enable the energy-climate transition, it identifies two key levers that could be prompted by symbiotic industrial relations, such as:

- The lever ‘*Bet on technology and innovation*’ which aims to launch an innovation centre on circular economy and establish a specific plan aimed especially at the industrial sector to increase material efficiency by 30%, through the improvement and development of new production models and the strengthening of eco-design of industrial products. Additionally, it argues for the development of new ecological and sustainable technologies in the treatment, recovery, and reuse of wastewater⁵².
- The lever ‘*Support for diversification, consolidation and business growth*’ which aims to develop a support program for SMEs called Pyme Circular – which will mention industrial symbiosis as a new circular strategy and a priority thematic action – implement, circular economy initiatives especially focused on the correct management of industrial waste and strengthen interaction between Basque leading companies from all sectors and international technology startups through the Bind 4.0 program⁵³.

The Basque Environmental Framework Programme 2030 addresses circularity in value chains through its 4th project which aims to involve companies in the same value chain to develop demonstrator projects of digital tools for the capture, sharing and analysis of data on the use of raw materials and

⁴⁸ Ibidem

⁴⁹ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Economía Circular en la Industria del País Vasco - Diagnostico [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: https://www.euskadi.eus/contenidos/documentacion/economia_circular/es_def/adjuntos/EstrategiaEconomiaCircular2030.pdf

⁵⁰ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de Prevención y Gestión de Residuos de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/documentacion/2021/plan-de-prevencion-y-gestion-de-residuos-de-euskadi-2030/>

⁵¹ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de desarrollo industrial e internacionalización 2021-2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/06-plan-estrategico-de-desarrollo-industrial-e-internacionalizacion/>

⁵² Ibidem

⁵³ Ibidem

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life cycle, which facilitate decision making aimed at reducing the environmental footprint⁵⁴. Industrial symbiosis can thus be fostered by this projects' objectives to 1) develop a solution based on an information and communication platform that can be used in other value chains or sectors, 2) promote collaboration between companies within the same value chain and between them and service providers, 3) generate new knowledge and innovation on the circular economy, use and life cycle of materials and energy, 4) identify specific areas of action for increasing material productivity, adopting innovative solutions and technological development, and 5) promote resource savings and waste reduction⁵⁵.

Sectors targeted by the policy documents relevant for IS and U-IS

Throughout the analysed policies, a few industrial sectors stand out for the opportunities associated to their circular transition, and these are consistent with the industrial sectors most important to the Basque economy.

The **metal sector**, including iron, steel, ferro-alloys, and foundry operations, is recurrently mentioned in the policies, for its potential associated to the energy and material import savings. More than a third of gas consumption in the industrial sector corresponds to the steel and foundry sector, in heating processes and thermal treatment of parts⁵⁶. In the Basque Country Waste Prevention and Management Plan 2030 it is argued that an improved management of metal waste, in all the flows where these materials appear, could produce significant savings in the purchase of raw materials, employment and added value in their recycling⁵⁷. An estimation in the Basque Circular Economy Diagnosis refers that if more circular innovative solutions were undertaken, it would be possible to achieve on average a 6% reduction of raw materials consumption and thus around 2,000 million euros of savings in the Basque industry, in which the metal (steel, foundry, metal products) and mobility (automotive, aeronautical) sectors would accumulate 49% of the potential savings in the Basque industry⁵⁸.

The **transport sector** (automotive, railway, aeronautical and naval), the **electrical-electronics** products and the **auxiliary equipment, machinery and machine tool** sector are also addressed by many of the policies, with particular emphasis on the importance of greater efficiency in material use, including the use of secondary raw materials, and the transition to renewable energy for these industries⁵⁹. The **construction sector**, is also a key sector in the Basque economy which due to its significant

⁵⁴ Gobierno Vasco, 2023, Programa Marco Ambiental de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.ihobe.eus/programa-marco-ambiental>

⁵⁵ *Ibidem*

⁵⁶ Gobierno Vasco, 2017, Estrategia Energética de Euskadi 2030, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/informacion/estrategia-energetica-de-euskadi-2030/web01-a2ingkli/es/>

⁵⁷ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de Prevención y Gestión de Residuos de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/documentacion/2021/plan-de-prevencion-y-gestion-de-residuos-de-euskadi-2030/>

⁵⁸ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Economía Circular en la Industria del País Vasco - Diagnostico [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: https://www.euskadi.eus/contenidos/documentacion/economia_circular/es_def/adjuntos/EstrategiaEconomiaCircular2030.pdf

⁵⁹ Gobierno Vasco, 2019, Estrategia de Economía Circular de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/documentacion/2020/estrategia-de-economia-circular-de-euskadi-2030/web01-a2ingkut/es/>

consumption of materials and generation of waste, offers great potential for circularity interventions which can enhance its use of secondary materials^{60,61,62}.

Less energy-intensive but highly relevant for the circular transition sectors, such as the **chemical, plastics, rubber, and packaging** sectors, have also been mentioned throughout different policies. In the chemical sector report for the circular economy, it is noted how the chemical industry has great potential for replicating the concept of industrial symbiosis given it generates large quantities of byproducts which can be used as raw materials for new production processes and foster the creation of chemical parks or industrial clusters where by-products and waste could be exchanged between companies⁶³. The Basque Circular Economy Strategy 2030 states that, considering that the thermoplastic processing industry is made up of more than a hundred companies and there are a few multinationals that produce plastic pellets and sheets necessary for the processing industries, the incorporation of secondary plastics material is an interesting solution, provided there is an adequate quality and a constant supply⁶⁴. Moreover, it establishes that in addition to post-consumer waste, plastic waste from industrial production should also be taken into account, as these hold great potential for high-quality mechanical recycling, and material flows must be grouped to reach critical quantities and increase profitability⁶⁵.

Bioeconomy-related sectors, such as the food industry, forestry, and wood (mainly timber), pulp and paper, wastewater and bio-waste management, have been referenced across policies. The promotion of the bioeconomy as a lever for the transformation and generation of new sources of value, with related environmental, biodiversity and economic benefits is promoted in the Industrial development and internationalization plan 2021-2024 through the development of new technologies for the transformation of materials of organic origin in sectors such as the food industry or wastewater treatment and recovery⁶⁶. In the food and beverage sector report for the circular economy, it is recommended to explore industrial symbiosis relations for the use of CO₂ surplus and for the valorisation of biowaste and bio-based by-products with a smaller carbon footprint than materials and chemical products derived from petroleum, such as bioplastics, bio composites or biosurfactants⁶⁷.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*

⁶¹ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de Economía Circular y Bioeconomía 2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/08-plan-estrategico-de-economia-circular-y-bioeconomia/>

⁶² Gobierno Vasco, 2023, Programa Marco Ambiental de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.ihobe.eus/programa-marco-ambiental>

⁶³ Gobierno Vasco, 2022, Informes de claves sectoriales en economía circular - Informe sectorial sector químico [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.ihobe.eus/publicaciones/informes-claves-sectoriales-en-economia-circular>

⁶⁴ Gobierno Vasco, 2019, Estrategia de Economía Circular de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/documentacion/2020/estrategia-de-economia-circular-de-euskadi-2030/web01-a2ingkut/es/>

⁶⁵ *Ibidem*

⁶⁶ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de desarrollo industrial e internacionalización 2021-2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/06-plan-estrategico-de-desarrollo-industrial-e-internacionalizacion/>

⁶⁷ Gobierno Vasco, 2022, Informes de claves sectoriales en economía circular - Informe sectorial sector de alimentación y bebidas [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.ihobe.eus/publicaciones/informes-claves-sectoriales-en-economia-circular>

Figure 4: Challenges of the Circular Economy in the Basque Country (Source: Gobierno Vasco, 2019, Estrategia de Economía Circular de Euskadi 2030)

More specifically, the Basque Circular Economy Strategy focuses on 7 Areas of Action and Priority Sectors: 1) metal, 2) automotive, 3) other means of transportation, 4) machinery-tools, 5) energy and other electrical equipment, 6) Agri-food and the bioeconomy and 7) the construction sector⁶⁸. As visible in Figure 4, these sectors are highly relevant for the Production Challenge 4 of reducing the consumption of raw materials and waste generation and the Challenge 9 of increasing the use of secondary raw materials.

Challenges to IS and I-US

There is no direct mention of the challenges to I-US in the region, but throughout the policies it is possible to extract what are the challenges to circular economy, industrialization or innovation that are relevant for the creation of symbiotic systems.

One of the main challenges identified by the Basque Circular Economy Strategy 2030 that could apply to symbiotic frameworks is related to the ensuring a stable and secure **supply of secondary raw materials**. In the Strategy it is argued that more research is needed in the area of identification and quantification of economically valuable raw materials in the current commercial circuit, as well as in the forecast of foreseeable changes in quantities and components⁶⁹. The quantitative requirements

⁶⁸ Gobierno Vasco, 2019, Estrategia de Economía Circular de Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/documentacion/2020/estrategia-de-economia-circular-de-euskadi-2030/web01-a2ingkut/es/>

⁶⁹ Ibidem

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applicable to post-consumer metals should be clarified and current recycling processes should be updated with the help of intelligent processes and cascade recycling, while innovations are required at the organizational level to provide a market outlet for all fractions of valuable materials obtained from recycling⁷⁰. More specifically on potential IS application, potential flows of new and unused materials will also need to be identified and technologies and measures developed to combat dissipation losses⁷¹.

The Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024 also identifies a list of challenges related to **circularity in the Basque bioeconomy**, among which those particularly relevant for IS are: 1) Lack of inventory of raw materials and waste, 2) Very atomized primary sector that complicates the logistics of raw material supply, 3) Lack of common infrastructure for scaling R&D projects, 4) Relocation of certain value chains such as the chemical industry, and 5) Lack of engineering companies that develop the transformation processes of the intermediate part of the value chain⁷². Moreover, it identifies a key threat in the economic crisis that hinders changes in consumption, R&D programs, and investments in companies⁷³.

Another set of challenges, related to the development of a **Smart Industry**, one of the driving forces of economic and social development in the Basque Country, and linked to the technological-digital and energy-climate transition, are: 1) maintaining and strengthening the competitive capabilities and expectations towards manufacturing technologies such as based on what builds value, 2) evaluate the use of data, providing intelligence and ultimately value to customers, which leads to the servicing and development of new business models, 3) increasing the value of products and services following the circular economy principles, and 4) facing an urgent cultural transformation so that organisations can exploit the maximum value of digital technologies and sustainability opportunities⁷⁴.

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving industrial symbiosis

As no analysed policy explores symbiosis more in detail, there is no direct reference to the aspired role of local authorities in the development of I-US. However, most of the policies – whether focused on circular economy, industrialization, or innovation – argue for the need of multistakeholder collaboration, as well as interdepartmental and interinstitutional coordination.

To this purpose, many policies propose the creation of interdepartmental and multidisciplinary tables or committees as channels of communication between different departments of the Basque Governments and other administrative bodies without executive or legislative functions, that will meet

⁷⁰ Ibidem

⁷¹ Ibidem

⁷² Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de Economía Circular y Bioeconomía 2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/08-plan-estrategico-de-economia-circular-y-bioeconomia/>

⁷³ Ibidem

⁷⁴ Gobierno Vasco, 2020, Plan de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/pcti-2030/web01-a2pcti30/es/>

to coordinate, generate synergies, and monitor the plan^{75,76,77}. Additionally, the Udalsarea 2030 network, the Basque Network of Municipalities towards Sustainability, and the Development Agencies stand out for the relevant role they play at the local level, due to their ability to coordinate the actions of the different local entities and extend the best practices of local application in the area of the circular economy.

At the city-level, beyond mentioning the need to collaborate with the provincial and city councils, the analysed policies do not prescribe a specific role for municipalities in the implementation of the policies. But the commitment to circularity and IS principles of the region is also possibly reinforced by some single cities policies on innovation and industrialization, such as Vitoria-Gasteiz Industry Support Plan 2021-2024 where, in coordination with the Basque Government, private companies and scientific-technological and educational entities, the Vitoria-Gasteiz City Council aims to serve as a coordinating and driving element of activities to promote the circular economy and thus guarantee that all the capacities available in the city and outside of it are used to really put them into value in projects that improve the environment⁷⁸. To this end, it launched an Industrial symbiosis initiative to incorporate the circular perspective in the management of industrial zones. Specifically, it aims to implement a circular approach in the management of industrial zones through an industrial symbiosis approach, identifying relevant information and the potential of circular flows (materials, energy, products, and services) so that they can be used and valued to improve competitiveness, industrial zones and the industries located in them. The Council will also provide financial aid for circular economy projects through a subsidy program aimed at SMEs to support the development of demonstration projects and/or the implementation of new products/services in the market framed in different areas of circular economy such as eco-design, remanufacturing, recovery of secondary materials⁷⁹.

3.3. I-US potential analysis

3.3.1. Material flows mapping

Industrial Waste Generation

The material flows analysis was conducted using the E-PRTR database. Figure 5 and Figure 6 respectively illustrate the total and disposed industrial waste flows in the Basque Country. Each year, 3.4 Mtons of waste are generated in the region, 2.9 Mtons of which is disposed. The manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys is the main emitting sector with an amount of waste of 330

⁷⁵ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de Economía Circular y Bioeconomía 2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/08-plan-estrategico-de-economia-circular-y-bioeconomia/>

⁷⁶ Gobierno Vasco, 2021, Plan de desarrollo industrial e internacionalización 2021-2024 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/gobierno-vasco/-/plan-gubernamental/06-plan-estrategico-de-desarrollo-industrial-e-internacionalizacion/>

⁷⁷ Gobierno Vasco, 2020, Plan de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Euskadi 2030 [in Spanish], Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.euskadi.eus/pcti-2030/web01-a2pcti30/es/>

⁷⁸ Ayuntamiento de Vitoria-Gasteiz, 2021, Plan de Apoyo a la Industria, Accessed: June 12, 2024, Available at: <https://www.vitoria-gasteiz.org/docs/wb021/contenidosEstaticos/adjuntos/es/93/84/79384.pdf>

⁷⁹ *Ibidem*

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ktons/year (9.7% of total waste). Without considering the waste treatment and disposal sectors, the next biggest emitting sectors are the casting of light metals, the casting of iron, and the forging, pressing, stamping, and roll-forming of metal. These five sectors represent around 14.1% of the total waste flows on the territory, and adding the waste treatment and disposal sectors, 90% of the waste flows are covered.

Regarding the disposed waste, manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys is still the most emitting sector with 160 ktons of disposed waste (10.9% of the total disposed waste), ending up either landfilled, buried, or incinerated without energy recovery. Then, 36 and 28 ktons are disposed respectively by the casting of iron and manufacture of paper and paperboard sectors. Figure 8 illustrates all the waste flows in the area and their sectorial distribution.

The following maps show that the waste flows are highly concentrated in the north of the Basque Country in the Bilbao and San Sebastian clusters. In contrast, the south of the region generates much less waste except around Vitoria-Gasteiz. As shown in Figure 7, the major waste-producing sites are located near a river. River transport has been investigated for facilitating the establishment of synergies, however rivers in Basque Country are not navigable.

Figure 5: Total waste flows in the Basque Country

Figure 6: Disposed waste flows in the Basque Country

Figure 7: Proximity between rivers and major waste-producing sites.

I-US Flow Mapping

Publicly available data provides high level aggregated waste tonnages by sector, with granularity on individual waste stream categories or volumes lacking. Although limited, the available data means that we can still provide an indicative level of analysis based on previous experience of the typical inputs and outputs for the key sectors in the Basque Country, aligning them with the major waste material flows.

As can be seen from the table below, in a number of cases a high percentage recovery rate is shown against most of the significant waste streams. As the end points are unknown it is not possible to say with certainty whether more commercially and environmentally beneficial options would exist through industrial symbiosis. The analysis that follows focusses on the materials going to disposal, which will be attracting the highest cost, and so will be the most commercially viable streams for industrial symbiosis opportunities.

For the purposes of the material flow analysis, flows associated with the waste processing sector have been removed. Although recognising the importance of the waste processing sector in realising IS and I-US opportunities, the reason for their removal is the data in its current form does not allow us to fully understand their constituent parts and therefore we cannot appraise their suitability for synergy creation at this time. That said, there is still significant flows associated with the remaining priority sectors to present significant opportunity for the Basque Country.

Table 2 Primary Waste Flow Data for Basque Country

NACE sector	Waste destined for disposal (t/y)	Waste destined for recovery (t/y)	Total of waste (t/y)
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys	161,405	178,574	339,979
Casting of iron	35,891	21,200	57,091
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	28,152	627	28,779
Raising of poultry	17,201	11,617	28,817
Manufacture of hollow glass	14,501	11	14,512
Manufacture of tubes, pipes, hollow profiles, and related fittings, of steel	8,170	8,363	16,533
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	7,470	204	7,674
Treatment and coating of metals	7,282	7,019	14,300
Casting of other non-ferrous metals	6,362	21,205	27,567
Manufacture of other inorganic basic chemicals	5,661	7,519	13,179

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Production of electricity	4,622	15,022	19,644
Manufacture of beer	3,103	11,910	15,013
Cold drawing of wire	2,337	853	3,190
Casting of light metals	2,266	59,089	61,355
Dismantling of wrecks	1,790	838	2,628
Forging, pressing, stamping, and roll-forming of metal	1,479	28,051	29,530

The high-level resource flows are dominated by metal sector-based flows and therefore likely to have associated high value due to likely metal content. There are significant volumes already going to established recovery routes, which again is likely reflective of potential metal content and intrinsic value.

The priority sectors for the Basque Country region have already been identified as:

- Casting of iron
- Manufacture of basic iron, steel, and ferro-alloys
- Casting of light metals
- Forging, pressing, stamping and roll-forming of metal
- Raising of poultry
- Manufacture of paper and paperboard

The table below details the main high-level byproduct and waste outputs expected for each of these sectors.

Table 3 Basque Country Priority Sector Flow Analysis

Sector	No. of sites	Outputs /By-products
Casting of Iron	25	Molding sand and clay
		Waste metal
		Used foundry sand
		Wastewater and process water
Manufacture of basic iron, steel, and ferro-alloys	20	Slag
		Mill scale
		Dust (Zinc rich)
		Process gases and steam
		Scrap metal
Casting of light metals	4	Metal scraps

		Slag
		Sand
		Dust
		Sludge
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	11	Waste paper / paperboard
		Ash
		Sludge
		Wood residue
		Black Liquor / other spent liquors
		Chemical waste
Forging, pressing, stamping and roll-forming of metal	3	Scrap metal
		Cutting fluids and lubricants
		Spent abrasives
		Sludge
		Dust
Raising of poultry	5	Manure
		Bedding
		Feathers
		Offal

Section 3.3.3, below, details the uses and potential sector partners for each of these material flows in turn.

3.3.2. I-US infrastructure mapping

Figure 9, Figure 10 and Figure 11 illustrate the key infrastructure for I-US in the Basque Country.

In terms of transport infrastructures, the region has 1123 km (0.15 km/km²) of motorways and around 1148 km (0.16 km/km²) of railways. For the energy infrastructures, 55 and 38% of the electricity are produced from gas and oil plants respectively while hydro (5%) and wind (2%) share the rest of the mix. Using modelling data from the HRE4project, 10.8 PJ/year and 3.8 PJ/year of excess heat from respectively industrial sites and WWTP have been identified. For the heat demands, the urban area would consume around 40.0 PJ/year. Regarding the education, 14 universities (science and technical schools) are in the region. The region also shows a good innovation appeal with 2 I-US demo cases:

- [AGGREGA CO2](#)
- [BH2C](#)

Figure 9: Transport infrastructures in the Basque Country

Figure 10: Electricity production and excess heat in the Basque Country (icons from icons8.com).

1.9 universities per 1000 km²

*Only technical and science schools are considered

2 I-US demo cases identified

Figure 11: Education and innovation in the Basque Country (icons from icons8.com).

3.3.3. Regional readiness assessment for I-US and general conclusions

The following table outlines the main industrial symbiosis opportunities for the resources identified in the resource flow analysis provided in section 3.3.1.

Table 4 Industrial Symbiosis Opportunities in Basque Country

Sector	Outputs /By-products	Uses
Casting of Iron	Molding sand and clay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land reclamation (fill material) Construction (aggregate for road bases and building foundations etc.)
	Waste metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle or remelt and re-use Feedstock for Electric Arc Furnace
	Used foundry sand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reclaim and re-use in foundry (requires chemical treatment) Construction (backfill, embankments etc.)
	Wastewater and process water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wastewater treatment for re-use
Manufacture of basic iron, steel, and ferro-alloys	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – aggregate and cement substitute Agriculture – soil amendment Marine – coral reef repair and construction
	Mill scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Iron recovery or substitute for virgin iron ore
	Dust (Zinc rich)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metal recovery and recycling
	Process gases and steam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power or steam generation Heat recovery Fuel
	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle / re-use Feedstock for furnace
Casting of light metals	Sand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – fine aggregate in concrete, asphalt, bricks Land reclamation (fill material) Agriculture – soil amendment
	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – aggregate and cement substitute Landscaping base material
	Metal scraps	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle / re-use Feedstock for furnace
	Dust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metal recovery and recycling Filler material in production of cement and bricks
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction material – bricks and tiles Metal recovery
	Waste paper / paperboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle (new paper products) Soil amendment through composting Animal bedding

Manufacture of paper and paperboard	Ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement substitute • Soil amendment
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture – soil amendment • Energy production (biomass fuel) • Cement and bricks manufacture
	Wood residue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil amendment • Energy production (biomass fuel)
	Black Liquor / other spent liquors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy recovery • Chemical recovery • Biofuel production
	Chemical waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recovery and reuse
Forging, pressing, stamping, and roll-forming of metal	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle / re-use • Feedstock for furnace
	Cutting fluids and lubricants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reconditioning for reuse • Energy recovery
	Spent abrasives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and reuse • Filler material in concrete or asphalt
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery • Cement production
	Dust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery • Concrete or brick production
Raising of poultry	Manure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fertilizer and soil amendment • Composting • Anaerobic digestion (biogas production)
	Bedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composting and mulch • Energy and biogas production
	Feathers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal feed • Fertilizer • Biodegradable materials production
	Offal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal feed • Pet food • Rendering (fats, proteins, or biodiesel) • Anaerobic digestion (biogas production)

The table above shows that the manufacturing sectors, particularly metal casting, and paper production, offer significant opportunities for recycling and reusing waste materials.

Many of the by-products in the table, such as slag from iron and light metal casting, ash from paper manufacturing, and sludge from multiple processes, can be used as substitutes for traditional construction materials. This includes their use as aggregate, cement substitutes, or in the production of bricks and tiles.

Several by-products have agricultural applications. For example, slag and wood residue can be used in soil amendment, and poultry manure can be used as fertilizer or for biogas production through anaerobic digestion.

There are also multiple opportunities for energy recovery across the different sectors, such as waste process gases and steam in iron and steel manufacturing, as well as black liquor in paper manufacturing being used for power or steam generation.

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To draw further conclusions on the Basque region's readiness for IS, the readiness assessment produced as part of the EU Circlean⁸⁰ project can be used as a framework.

Awareness of IS and Potential Benefits

Policy analysis concluded that no specific legislation or policy was driving industrial symbiosis (IS) uptake and awareness in both public and private sectors. However, there are some circular economy policies that create a suitable framework off which to hang future IS specific policy.

A search on IS activity does reveal several examples in existence:

- Smurfit Kappa invests €27 million in new sustainability initiative at Spanish paper mill : Investment at Smurfit Kappa's paper mill facility is €27M to build a lime kiln and gas treatment facility to take calcium carbonate from the paper making process and process it back into calcium oxide which can be reused in the paper manufacturing operation, or sold into new markets such as water treatment, textiles, agriculture (including sugar manufacture) and steelmaking.
- Bilbao Rai 2000⁸¹: Bilbao Rai is a not-for-profit company formed from a partnership of state administration organisations and public sector companies. Its aim is to advance the development of Bilbao in a sustainable way. Activities include capturing waste heat from iron and steel processes and feeding it into district heating systems, demolition waste captured and recycled into new building projects and development of sustainable infrastructure.

Initial Ideas of Where a Company Can Engage / Resources suiting IS / Processes Mapped & Targeted for IS

The regional analysis conducted provides some initial starting points for company engagement. Research of the region has not identified any specific IS or I-US focussed support activity, however the examples of IS identified at company level give confidence that there is an awareness at industry level on the use of secondary resources and the value that can be achieved through adopting an IS approach.

Internal Data Sources Identified for Quantification / Resources identified, quantified and characterised for IS

As with all the regions analysed, data is available at a high level, giving aggregated waste flows by sector, which allows for some analysis and understanding of opportunity to be obtained. Improvements could be made in the visibility and granularity of this data to inform commercial decision making in regard to the suitability of secondary materials to substitute for their virgin counterparts in industrial symbiosis synergies.

Check Costs, regulations and other technology specifications to be met for IS opportunities

⁸⁰ <https://circlean-symbiosis.eu/the-project/>; accessed April 2024

⁸¹ Bilbao Ria 2000, A Public Company of Reference in the Urban Transformation of Metropolitan Bilbao; Accessed June 13, 2024, available at: <https://www.bilbaoria2000.org/en/>

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As part of an EU member state the supporting regulation alongside a landfill tax regime will be creating some of the supporting framework required to drive the uptake of IS in the Basque region. As with most other regions analysed, positive benefit will be achieved through creating IS specific policy and providing some facilitated support to help industry understand the opportunities that present themselves and further strengthen the commercial case for action.

Resources Prioritised for IS with Industry Buy In / All Resources Quantified and Posted on Matching Tool

With some significant cases identified in our high-level research that involve priority sectors, then these could act as anchor industries in establishing a regional industrial symbiosis program within the Basque region. No evidence of an existing resource sharing platform was uncovered which would aid IS activity through the increased visibility of available resources.

Overall, with the significant industry and material flows in the North of the region that we know are suitable for IS activity, along with a strong academic and research infrastructure, then the basic building blocks required for a successful industrial symbiosis initiative appear to be in place. The next step would be to strengthen IS specific policy and provide support to industry in identifying and progressing the opportunities that present themselves.

4. Regional analysis: Flanders – France, Belgium, The Netherlands

4.1. Local Context

4.1.1. Geographical landscape

The geographical landscape of the Flanders region, which encompasses parts of Belgium (provinces of East Flanders and West Flanders), France (department of Nord), and the Netherlands (province of Zeeland), is diverse and characterized by its low-lying plains, extensive waterways, and fertile agricultural land.

Flanders - Belgium

The Flemish Region, comprising the provinces of Antwerp, Limburg, East Flanders, West Flanders, and Flemish Brabant, forms the northern half of Belgium. As part of the Belgian state reforms in the late 20th century, Flanders was divided into two political entities: the Flemish Region (Vlaams Gewest) and the Flemish Community (Vlaamse Gemeenschap). Despite their merger, the Flemish Community—with its wider cultural responsibilities—encompasses Brussels, unlike the Flemish Region, which does not.

Flanders is predominantly flat with low-lying plains. The northeastern area, known as Kempeland, is characterized by dunes, broom, heather, and poor pastureland, while the northwest is a fertile low-lying plain. In the west, there are Flemish polders (land reclaimed from the sea), which are crisscrossed with drainage channels and extend 10–16 km inland. The coastline, along the North Sea, features dunes, sandy beaches, and coastal nature reserves, as well as protected areas, such as the Verdrongen Land van Saeftinghe, which are important for biodiversity and environmental conservation.

The main rivers include the Scheldt, Dender, Dijle, Nete, Rupel, Yser, and Meuse, with the latter forming part of the border with the Netherlands. The Scheldt and the Meuse are vital for commerce and transportation.

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Flanders experiences a temperate maritime climate, characterized by mild winters, cool summers, and moderate rainfall throughout the year.

Flanders– The Netherlands

Zeelandic Flanders, located in the southernmost part of Zeeland province in southwestern Netherlands, is bordered to the south and east by Belgium. Covering 876 km², of which 733 km² are land and 143 km² is water, the region extends from the Zwin nature reserve in the west to the Drowned Land of Saeftinghe in the east. It comprises three municipalities: Sluis, Terneuzen, and Hulst.

- **Sluis:** Situated on the North Sea in the west, Sluis is a popular tourist destination known for its beaches.
- **Terneuzen:** Located centrally, Terneuzen borders the industrial canal from Ghent to Terneuzen and is the most significant city in Dutch Flanders, housing most central facilities.
- **Hulst:** Positioned in the east, Hulst is known as the "most Flemish city" in the Netherlands.

The fertile land supports extensive agriculture, while protected nature reserves and wetlands, such as the Hoge Kempen National Park, enhance its ecological value. Zeelandic Flanders is characterized by polders, dikes, and flat, reclaimed land south of the Western Scheldt estuary. The North Sea moderates the climate, leading to mild winters, cool summers, and frequent precipitation.

However, Dutch Flanders faces significant environmental challenges, particularly related to water management and coastal protection due to its geography⁸², characterized by having large portions of the area below sea level, with elevations ranging from approximately -1 to 2 meters. Consequently, the region relies heavily on an extensive system of dikes, polders, and drainage canals to protect against flooding from the North Sea and the Western Scheldt estuary.

Flanders - France

French Flanders is located in the northern part of France, part of the larger Hauts-de-France region and includes the departments of Nord and Pas-de-Calais, which consists of 2 sub-regions. To the north, is the French Westhoek (or Flamingo Flanders) sub-region, which corresponds largely to the Dunkirk district, with main cities Dunkirk, Cassel, Hazebrouck and Bailleul. To the south, is the Romanesque Flanders (also called Gallicant Flanders or Walloon Flanders) sub-region, corresponding to the district of Lille (nicknamed "the Capital of Flanders" in France), which includes its largest city Lille, and other main towns, such as Roubaix, Tourcoing, Armentières, and part of the district of Douai.

The flat terrain and gently rolling hills result from slow-moving watercourses shaped by the region's geology. Although large forests and wild nature disappeared early, due to extensive agriculture in these fertile plains (producing crops such as wheat, sugar beets, and vegetables), some natural or semi-natural environments, such as the Parc Naturel Régional des Caps et Marais d'Opale, remain in the mountains and in wetter depressions as reserves and protected areas, contributing to regional biodiversity and environmental conservation.

The coastline, like Belgian Flanders, features sandy beaches and dunes. The climate is similarly temperate maritime, with mild winters, cool summers, and consistent rainfall.

⁸² Zeeuwse Ankers, website. Battle against the water. Accessed. June 5, 2024 [online] Available: <https://www.zeeuwseankers.nl/erfgoedlijn/strijd-tegen-het-water>

Cross-Regional Geographical Characteristics

- **Water Management:** Across all parts of Flanders, especially in the Dutch and Belgian areas, extensive systems of dikes, polders, and canals are essential for water management and land reclamation. Given the regions' low elevations, flood control is critical, supported by sophisticated infrastructure to manage sea and river water levels.
- **Wetlands and Nature Reserves:** There are significant wetlands and nature reserves, such as the Zwin in Belgian Flanders and the Verdrongen Land van Saeftinghe in Dutch Flanders, which are vital for biodiversity.
- **Coastline:** The North Sea coastlines of Belgian and French Flanders feature natural dunes and sandy beaches, important for tourism and coastal protection.
- **Major Ports:** Ports like the Port of Antwerp in Belgian Flanders and the Port of Dunkirk in French Flanders are pivotal for international trade.
- **Agriculture:** Fertile plains across all regions support intensive agriculture, significantly contributing to the local economies.
- **Rural Landscape:** Much of the region is rural, with small towns and villages interspersed among agricultural lands.
- **Environmental Sensitivity:** The Flanders region is characterized by its flat, low-lying terrain, extensive waterways, fertile agricultural land, and significant coastal features, which underscore its economic importance and environmental sensitivity.

4.1.2. Social landscape

The Flanders region is characterized by a rich cultural heritage, influenced by its complex history, economic development, and linguistic diversity, as well as by its economic vitality and ongoing efforts to balance regional identities with broader European integration.

Flanders - Belgium

Despite covering only 45% of Belgium's territory, Flanders is home to over half of the country's population—6,821,770 residents, or 58% of the 11,763,650 inhabitants in the nation⁸³. The region is densely populated (381 inhabitants/km²), particularly in urban centers such as Antwerp, Ghent, Bruges, and Leuven. These cities are not only the largest in the Flemish Region but also cultural hubs renowned for their medieval architecture and modern art scenes. Antwerp, the largest city, has a population of 544,759, followed by Ghent with 269,597, Bruges with 119,869, and Leuven with 104,009 residents.

Flanders boasts a vibrant cultural scene with a strong tradition in arts, music, and festivals. Flanders has an extensive and well-maintained road and rail network, ensuring excellent connectivity within the region and to neighbouring countries. The region has a significant immigrant population, with diverse communities from North Africa, Turkey, Eastern Europe, and more recently, the Middle East. However, integration and social cohesion remain ongoing challenges.

⁸³ STATBEL, Structure of the population, 2024, Accessed: June 5, 2024, Available: <https://statbel.fgov.be/nl/themas/bevolking/structuur-van-de-bevolking>

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The official language is Dutch, often referred to locally as Flemish. English and French are also widely understood. According to Belgian law, education in schools located in the Flemish Region must be primarily in Dutch, while in Brussels, teaching is also conducted in French. Education is compulsory from ages 6 to 18, but most students in Flanders continue their studies until around 23. Flemish students consistently rank among the top three globally in mathematics and science. However, ethnic minority youth score consistently lower, indicating disparities in educational success.

The unemployment rate in Flanders is relatively low compared to other regions in Belgium. Nonetheless, there are disparities in job opportunities and living standards between urban and rural areas. Urban areas benefit from better infrastructure and public services, while rural areas may face depopulation and limited resources. Public transport in urban areas is highly developed, with comprehensive bus, tram, and train services, and efforts are underway to improve connectivity in rural areas.

Flanders' population includes a mix of age groups, with a significant number of young people due to the presence of numerous universities and higher education institutions. There is also a considerable elderly population, particularly in rural areas, impacting healthcare and social services. While healthcare is a federal matter, the Flemish Government is responsible for care, health education, and preventive care. Various social programs support vulnerable populations, including the elderly, low-income families, and immigrants, aiming to improve social inclusion, employability⁸⁴, and access to services. Moreover, the regional government and local organizations promote sustainability through initiatives in renewable energy, waste management, and sustainable agriculture⁸⁵.

Flanders -The Netherlands

Dutch Flanders, with a population of 105,204⁸⁶, is one of the less populated regions in the Netherlands, boasting a population density of 147 inhabitants per km², which is lower than the national average. This contributes to a more rural and tranquil environment, attracting retirees and those seeking a slower pace of life.

The official language is Dutch, but local dialects influenced by Flemish and West Flemish are also spoken. Due to its proximity to Belgium, many residents are fluent in Flemish, and French is also commonly understood. Furthermore, the rich and shared history is reflected in its architecture, traditions, and festivals. There is a strong tradition of local arts and crafts, with many artisans preserving traditional methods in pottery, weaving, and other crafts.

Zeelandic Flanders has an ageing population, as younger generations often move to larger cities in the Netherlands or Belgium for education and employment opportunities. The limited higher education institutions within the region impact local demographics and community life. The higher proportion of elderly residents increases the demand for specialized social and healthcare services, including

⁸⁴ SERV, Accessed: June 5, 2024, Available: <https://www.serv.be/serv/thema/arbeidsmarkt>

⁸⁵ VLAANDEREN, Accessed: June 5, 2024, Available: <https://www.vlaanderen.be/en/environment>

⁸⁶ Statistics Netherlands, Population dashboard, Accessed: June 7, 2024, Available: <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/visualisations/dashboard-population>

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geriatric care and support for chronic conditions⁸⁷. Efforts are ongoing to improve healthcare infrastructure to meet these needs, including the expansion of medical facilities and home care services.

The region is known for its strong sense of community. Social cohesion is high, with residents actively participating in local clubs, associations, and volunteer activities. Local governments and organizations support these dynamics through programs for the elderly, low-income families, and other vulnerable groups. They also work to preserve and promote local cultural heritage through museums, cultural centers, and educational programs. Various initiatives aimed at promoting sustainability are in place, including projects on renewable energy, green roofs, and circular economy practices⁸⁸.

The infrastructure in Dutch Flanders is well-developed, with good road connections to the rest of the Netherlands and Belgium. The opening of the Western Scheldt tunnel in 2003 significantly improved connectivity with the rest of Zeeland. Public transport consists of a network of bus lines, though the system operates less frequently than in more urbanized areas. Efforts are ongoing to improve connectivity and accessibility.

Flanders - France

French Flanders is densely populated, with over 2.6 million residents in the Nord department alone⁸⁹. Urban areas like Lille, one of France's major cities, are especially populous.

French is the official and dominant language in the region. However, two other languages, Picard (called "chti" locally) in Roman Flanders and most of Flemish Artois, and Flemish (a Low Franconian dialect of Dutch) in French Westhoek and the Saint-Omer district, are still spoken, though their use has declined significantly.

Flemish culture in the region extends beyond language, encompassing traditional festivals, cuisine, art, industry, and architecture, contributing to a distinct cultural identity influenced by both French and Flemish heritage.

The population of French Flanders includes a mix of age groups. Cities like Lille have a significant number of young people due to the presence of several universities and higher education institutions. However, rural areas face challenges related to an aging population—24% of the population in Hauts-de-France was aged 60 or over in 2020, and this is expected to increase to 33% by 2070 if current demographic trends continue⁹⁰.

There are notable differences in living standards, education, infrastructure, and access to public services between urban and rural areas. Urban areas like Lille feature high educational attainment and diverse job opportunities and benefit from extensive public transport networks (including buses, trams, and metro services). On the other hand, rural areas experience social issues such as limited

⁸⁷ ZorgSaam, Accessed: June 7, 2024, Available: <https://www.zorgsaam.org/>

⁸⁸ Sustainable Zeeland Flanders, ENERGY-NEUTRAL SOCIETY IN 2030, Accessed: June 7, 2024, Available: <https://duurzaamzeeuwsvlaanderen.nl/projecten/energieneutrale-samenleving-in-2030/>

⁸⁹ Insee, INSEE Hauts-de-France, 2023, Accessed: 10 June, 2024, Available: <https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2018861>

⁹⁰ Plateforme sanitaire et sociale HAUTS-DE-FRANCE, 2024, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: <https://www.pf2s.fr/15-dernieres-publications/873-le-numero-de-mars-2024-de-la-revue-de-la-plateforme-est-paru>

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access to quality education, higher unemployment rates, depopulation, scarce resources and less well-served public transport, but efforts are underway to improve connectivity. For example, the railway line connecting Picardy to Roissy is planned for completion in July 2026, marking a significant step towards enhanced regional connectivity and development⁹¹.

Economic disparities in the region have led to various social programs supporting vulnerable populations, including the elderly, low-income families, and immigrants. These programs aim to improve social inclusion and access to services. Additionally, local governments and organizations are promoting sustainability through initiatives in energy management, waste management, and broader climate and ecological transitions⁹².

Cross-Regional Social Characteristics

- **Linguistic and Cultural Exchange:** The region's history as a crossroads of Europe has created a rich tapestry of linguistic and cultural exchange. Multilingualism is common, and cultural events frequently celebrate this diversity.
- **Economic Integration:** Significant economic ties exist across the regions, particularly in trade, transport, and labor markets. Cross-border cooperation programs aim to enhance economic and social integration.
- **Political and Social Cooperation:** Various European Union initiatives foster collaboration across national borders, addressing issues such as regional development, infrastructure, and environmental protection. For example, the Borderless Canal Zone project seeks to improve the living and working environment of the entire Ghent-Terneuzen Canal Zone⁹³.

4.1.3. Economic and Industrial landscape

The industrial landscape and industrial sectors distribution of the Flanders region is detailed in Figure 12 and Figure 13. Industrial sites are mainly concentrated in the clusters identified in T2.1:

- Lille/Coutrai/Roulers cross border cluster in France and Belgium.
- Dunkerque, Lens and Valenciennes clusters in France
- Antwerpen and Gentt clusters in Belgium
- Rotterdam cluster in Netherlands

As shown in Figure 13, the sector distribution is quite homogenous. 4 major industrial sectors are identified along with their number of sites as a percentage of the total number of sites:

- Manufacture of chemical, pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic products (17%)
- Waste collection, treatment, and disposal activities; materials recovery (17%)
- Manufacture of food products, beverage, and tobacco products (12%)
- Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment (11%)

⁹¹ Region Hauts-de-France, New Roissy-Picardie rail line: a major asset for the Region!, 2024, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: <https://www.hautsdefrance.fr/nouvelle-ligne-ferroviaire-roissy-picardie-un-atout-majeur-pour-la-region/>

⁹² ADEME, ADEME Hauts-de-France, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: <https://www.ademe.fr/direction-regionale/hauts-de-france/>

⁹³ Interreg, Boundless Canal Zone, Accessed: June 10, 2024, Available: <https://interregvlandeu/grenzeloze-kanaalzone/over-ons>

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The next sub-sections describe the economical and industrial landscapes of the Flanders for each country separately (France, Belgium and Netherlands) to take into account the national disparities.

Flanders - Belgium

In the past, Flanders was a major trade hub and the focal point of Europe's textile industry, which has been losing its economical relevance. Nowadays, Flanders presents a diverse industry landscape and a perfect European hub for commerce with its central location and easy access to some of the most important economies in Europe, being home to more than 650 European distribution centres, which represents the highest density in Europe⁹⁴. These conditions allow for the Flemish industry to have an economy strongly export-oriented: Flanders' exports represented 82.0% of Belgium's total export volume, in 2021⁹⁵. The region's main export sectors are:

- chemicals and pharmaceuticals
- transport equipment
- machines, devices and electronics
- minerals
- plastics
- food and beverages
- pearls, gems, and diamonds
- textiles
- optics and precision equipment⁹⁶

Regarding Flanders technology and innovation, is expected for the government, companies, knowledge centres and citizens to focus on six domains: energy transition, health care, lifelong learning, data mobility and media and entertainment. Six large-scale clusters drive the progress in critical areas: Catalisti (sustainable chemistry), Flanders' Food (agro-food), Flanders Logistics Cluster (Specialised logistics), Flux50 (energy), the Blue Cluster (sea-related activities) and Medvia Flanders (personalised medicine)⁹⁷.

In 2021, the Flanders GDP per capita was 35.900€, above the European union average of sensibly 30 000€, and the unemployment rate was 3,9%, being among the lowest of the European union and even lower than Belgium⁹⁵.

The chemical industry has a vital role in the Flanders economy. In 2021, EUR 73.8 billion income of sales of plastic and chemicals per capita were generated in Flanders, more than two-thirds of Belgium related income⁹⁸.

The region location and a large and evolved infrastructure contributed to the development of the sector. Flanders is situated at the heart of the Antwerp-Rotterdam-Rhine-Ruhr Area (ARRRA), being centrally located within the Western European pipeline network. The world's second largest, second

⁹⁴ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Why Flanders is a strategic location in Europe, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/business-environment/strategic-location>

⁹⁵ Department of Finance and Budget, Flanders, 2022 - Investor presentation Flanders in a Nutshell. Accessed: July 3, 2024.

⁹⁶ OECD, 2022, The Culture Fix: Creative People, Places and Industries. <https://doi.org/10.1787/991bb520-en>. Accessed: July 2, 2024.

⁹⁷ EWI Vlaanderen, 2024, STI (Science, Technology & Innovation) in Flanders: Policy & key figures 2024. Accessed: July 3, 2024.

⁹⁸ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Chemical industry in Flanders, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/chemicals>

only to Houston, and Europe's largest integrated petrochemical cluster is based in Flanders. Eight of the world's top ten chemical companies operate from there, alongside key activities of the world's top ten biopharma companies⁹⁸.

With 500 chemical companies spread across more than 2,500 hectares of industrial land, two refineries, three steam crackers, and a high degree of integration and diversity across the chemical value chain, the Port of Antwerp-Bruges (Flanders) petrochemical cluster is home to production and storage facilities for over 300 different chemicals. Additionally, the Zeebrugge area of the port acts as one of the main entry points for the supply of Liquefied natural gas (LNG) in Northwestern Europe⁹⁸.

The chemical sector is essential to solving climate-related issues, advancing the circular economy, and building a carbon-smart society. To tackle a vast array of initiatives centred on sustainability, Catalisti, one of the most significant Flanders' clusters for chemistry and plastics, aims to promote innovation and multidisciplinary cooperation in these high-impact sectors⁹⁸.

Although Flanders covers 13,625 km², it is home to 23,218 agricultural businesses. Among these, 621 pioneers are dedicated to biopharming, promoting agricultural innovation. This compact powerhouse driving agricultural advancements, has fresh meat, dairy, and cocoa products in the centre stage, harmonizing with fertilizers, agricultural equipment, and chemicals in a grand production of agricultural commerce. Flanders' annual agricultural exports account for €43.1 billion, supporting a workforce of 45,938 individuals within this sector⁹⁹.

Flanders' institutes, such as Inagro and Flanders' FOOD, play pivotal roles in research and development, offering expert guidance on sustainable farming techniques. These institutions provide the workforce with a versatile skill set crucial for the agribusiness sector to prosper⁹⁹.

Flanders mobility sector also plays an essential role in the region economy, with the automotive and aerospace industry being responsible for the creation of jobs and boost the region's economy. The automotive industry also plays a relevant role in the economy of Flanders with 326 companies, 45,608 direct jobs, 14.4 billion € in annual turnover, and an annual investment value of 370 million €. This sector represents 3.1 billion € in added value per year and over 85% of Belgium's entire turnover in the automotive industry. Flanders' aerospace industry – aeronautics and space combined – generated a total turnover of EUR 1.2 billion in 2016, employing more than 3,900 people in the region. Flanders aerospace industry is not limited to transportation. Its diverse applications have become indispensable to our daily lives, from precision agriculture to construction, traffic and logistics, life sciences and smart health, telecommunications, finance, and insurance^{100 101}.

Other areas that have a remarkable influence in the economic activity of Flanders are life sciences, energy, environmental, machinery and smart logistics. Life science innovation in Flanders is very

⁹⁹ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Agribusiness in Flanders, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/agribusiness>

¹⁰⁰ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Automotive industry, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/automotive-industry>

¹⁰¹ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Aerospace, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/aerospace>

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strongly present alongside with the local community of biopharma companies, biotechnological firms, and agribusinesses present both, large enterprises, and SMEs.^{102 103 104 105}

Flanders' energy sector aspires to make progress in the areas of alternative energy sources and intelligent energy management, being a pioneer, for example, in the development of wind turbine tech, with one of the world's first large-scale wind energy parks built, in 1986, in Zeebrugge, West Flanders. Projects related to the production of green hydrogen are also being developed with the construction of a hydrogen plant called HYPOR¹⁰³.

Two of the most relevant clusters for smart energy that unite the private, public, and academic sectors in multidisciplinary and collaborative projects are the Flux50 and the Blue Clusters¹⁰³.

Flanders also shines in machinery, robotics, and advanced technology sectors. Its manufacturing industry is at the forefront of innovation, focusing on automation, flexibility, and customization. The region boasts a strong collaboration between academic institutions and private companies, all supported by favourable government policies. With significant expertise in specialized areas like additive manufacturing, Flanders is also in the front row in regard to the Industry 5.0, which blends human creativity and craftsmanship with cutting-edge digital technologies^{105 106}.

Flanders- The Netherlands

In the Dutch Flanders, the analysis included two regions, Zeeland, and South Holland.

South Holland is a region where Rotterdam and The Hague Leiden can be highlighted as the major cities, with strong economic activity in the food and agriculture sectors, with its agricultural exploitation being very marked using greenhouses. Also, economic clusters, such as petrochemicals, medical technology, aerospace, and marine industries are a central part of the region's economy. These factors contribute to this region being one of the richest in the Netherlands, with a GDP per capita of 48,548€, and 21% of the country's GDP in 2021¹⁰⁷.

Through programs such as 'Strategy Circular Zuid-Holland: Accelerating Together', launched in 2020, the region is trying to achieve certain objectives aimed at minimizing environmental impact. These objectives follow the 'A Circular Economy in the Netherlands by 2050' programme, launched in 2016, and the 2017 Raw Material Agreement. In short, the main goal is to reduce the use of raw materials such as minerals, metals, and fossil fuels by 50% by 2030, compared to 2016 levels, and achieve full

¹⁰² Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Life sciences & health, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/life-sciences-health>

¹⁰³ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Energy, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/energy>

¹⁰⁴ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Environmental tech & sustainability, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/environmental-tech-sustainability>

¹⁰⁵ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Machinery & robotics, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/machinery-robotics>

¹⁰⁶ Flanders investment & Trade, Invest in Flanders, Micro & nanoelectronics, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://invest.flandersinvestmentandtrade.com/en/sectors/micro-nanoelectronics>

¹⁰⁷ OECD, 2024, The Circular Economy in Zuid-Holland, Netherlands. The Circular Economy in Zuid-Holland, Netherlands | OECD. Accessed: July 2, 2024

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circularity by 2050. Four main 'transition themes' support this objective: Circular Built Industry, Circular Plastics, Circular Green, Resources and Food, and Circular Manufacturing Industry¹⁰⁷.

The 2023 OECD Circular Cities and Regions Survey highlights several key drivers for the circular economy in South Holland: boosting innovation, creating added value, and addressing climate change. The provincial strategy underscores the importance of the circular economy in job creation and enhancing the province's competitiveness¹⁰⁷.

Because of its advantageous location between the two biggest ports in Europe, Antwerp and Rotterdam, Zeeland also functions as a significant logistical hub. The North Sea Port, a combination of the ports of Vlissingen, Gent, and Terneuzen, is among the top 10 largest ports in Europe. This prime location attracts a diverse range of companies, boosting Zeeland's international connectivity¹⁰⁸.

Zeeland is also a significant energy hub in the Netherlands, with substantial investments in offshore wind and solar energy. The Energy Port Zeeland, a partnership focusing on education, the labour market, and research, drives advancements in the energy sector. The region is set to become a leading hydrogen hub in Europe, as part of the Smart Delta Resources initiative¹⁰⁸.

Agriculture and tourism are other important sectors in Zeeland. The province attracts numerous international agricultural companies that continuously seek talent to develop new technologies and solutions. Over 10% of all jobs in Zeeland are attributed to the tourism and leisure sectors, further diversifying the regional economy¹⁰⁸.

Zeeland is dedicated to sustainable innovation across all sectors, including chemical, energy, food, and logistics. The use of residual heat as an energy source and the recycling of plastics and other materials highlight the region's commitment to the circular economy. Smart Delta Resources, a collaboration of governments, ports, and major energy and raw material-intensive industrial companies in the Delta region (Zeeland, West Brabant, and Flanders), aims to establish a competitive and climate-neutral industry by 2050 through various sustainability programs¹⁰⁸.

¹⁰⁸ NL Netherlands, Zeeland, No date. Accessed: June 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.welcome-to-nl.nl/about-nl/zeeland>

Figure 12: Mapping of industrial sites in the Flanders region (icons from icons8.com).

Figure 13: Industrial sectors distribution and zoom into the Lille/Courtrai/Roulers cluster (icons from icons8.com).

Flanders-France

In the French Flanders, the analysis was centred on two main cities, both with a past of great economic and industrial development: Lille and Dunkirk.

The steel and textile industry were two very important sectors in Lille's industry, being one of France largest producing region. Despite the relevance of these two sectors, the coal sector was clearly, the sector with the highest share in the local economy and it was the most important coal mining region in France^{109 110 111}.

However, from the 1960s onwards, Lille faced a severe deindustrialization caused by the international steel and oil crisis and the preference for industries in other countries with cheaper labour. This crisis led to the bankruptcy of many factories and staff cuts. By the 1980s, coal mining had essentially ceased, plunging the region into economic decline. By the 1990s, Lille had some of the highest levels of unemployment and population decline in France.¹³⁻¹⁵ Despite these challenges, significant economic progress has been made over the past three decades. This transformation has been driven by strategic initiatives such as the central government-funded competition poles program and the locally driven sites of excellence program. These initiatives combined with the city's strategic location have spurred innovation in advanced textiles, e-commerce, R&D, tech startups and boosted exports of foodstuffs, biotech, nutrition and vehicles^{109 110 111}.

The Flanders-Dunkirk region boasts a thousand-year-old maritime tradition and a rich history in the industrial and energy sectors for over a century. The chemical industry had a significant evolution over the last decades, becoming more diversified over the years with a growing environmental awareness. The region has a strong legacy in oil refining, steel production, and chemical industry. Today, it is recognized as Europe's largest energy platform, housing a diverse array of energy facilities. These include a nuclear power plant, an LNG terminal, and a combined cycle power plant. To add to the energy sector, green hydrogen production and offshore wind energy production are also being developed^{112 113 114}.

¹⁰⁹ Frick, S. Lessons from successful 'turnaround' cities for the UK, 2023. Accessed: July 3, 2024.

¹¹⁰ Why entrepreneurs are choosing Lille for European business, No date. Accessed: July 3, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eurostartentreprises.com/en/business-advice/why-entrepreneurs-are-choosing-lille-for-european-business>.

¹¹¹ Frick, S. Turnaround Cities: French Case Study Insights from Lille, 2023. Accessed: July 3, 2024.

¹¹² Hydrogen in Dunkirk area Energy - Dunkerque Promotion, No date. Accessed: July 2, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dunkerquepromotion.org/en/energies/hydrogen-energy-dunkerque-promotion/>.

¹¹³ Power plant profile: Dunkirk Offshore Wind Farm, France, 2024. Accessed: July 2, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.power-technology.com/data-insights/power-plant-profile-dunkirk-offshore-wind-farm-france/>.

¹¹⁴ Major energy producers - Dunkerque Promotion, No date. Accessed: July 2, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dunkerquepromotion.org/en/energies/major-energy-producers/>.

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4.2. Local policy analysis

The Flanders region encompasses three countries; therefore, this section is divided into three, repeating the analysis for each country.

Flanders-Belgium

Overview

Belgium is a highly decentralised federal country. Its three regions (Brussels, Flanders, and Wallonia) have almost full competence on matters related to circular economy. Few exceptions exist, and those include energy (security and taxation), nuclear energy and nuclear waste, waste shipments and product policy. Some of these federal competences are important for the discussion on the policies related to industrial symbiosis. Further, the federal government has an important coordination role across the regions as well as the position of Belgium vis-a-vis other countries and the EU.

Policies promoting circular economy in general have been described extensively in many previous publications¹¹⁵, in this section we only focus on policies specifically targeting industrial symbiosis and if possible, industrial-urban symbiosis.

Policies specifically targeting IS and/or I-US and their origins

There is not a policy exclusively dedicated to industrial symbiosis. However, IS and I-US is encouraged through a number of relevant initiatives, albeit not always mentioned as an end goal. They stem mainly from the regional level. Due to the distribution of competences, federal level documents usually refer to what is being done at regional level, which is then completed with federal level initiatives, if relevant and falls within their competence. These initiatives range from action plans to political agreement of the coalition governments. A complete list is provided in Annex 2: List of the documents screened for policy analysis section.

For Flanders (BE), the longer list contains 22 relevant policy documents. Only two documents refer to national/federal level, while the rest stem from the regional competence.

The following documents were selected for in-depth analysis because they contained several of the keywords used for screening, and at least the word industry. They can be divided into broad groups of overarching strategies and sector specific initiatives. They include:

- Federal/national: Belgian National Plan for Energy and Climate 2021-2030 and National CEAP (2021-2024)
- Overarching strategies/vision building documents:
 - The Flemish energy and climate plan 2013-2020 and 2021-2030
 - Flemish Coalition Agreement 2019-2024
 - Flanders Vision 2030
 - Flanders Vision 2050
 - Flanders Strategy for Smart Specialisation (including its update in 2023)
 - Images of Future: Flemish Circular Economy Strategy 2050
 - Flanders in Action with the New Industrial Policy (2013)
- Sector and value chain-specific documents:
 - Chemical and Plastics Work Agenda (and related documents)
 - Manufacturing Industry Work Agenda

¹¹⁵ See for instance: EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for Belgium, Available : https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/belgium-ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

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- Action Plan Circular Food Loss and Biomass (Residual)
- Relevant frameworks specific to certain policy fields:
 - Spatial Policy Plan for Flanders
 - Natural Resources and Waste Plan

Main Actors with work relevant for Industrial Urban Symbiosis

Based on the policy documents listed above, it can be concluded that all relevant ministries are working on issues related to industrial symbiosis. These include the Ministry for Justice and Enforcement, Environment and Spatial Development, Energy and Tourism (environmental policy, spatial planning, energy, and natural resources), Flemish Ministry for Economy, Innovation, Work, Social Economy and Agriculture.

The policies are implemented through a multitude of mechanisms and institutions that support these. **Circular Flanders** is the most important entity in terms of delivering circular economy related initiatives, in line with the national and regional policy objectives since 2017. Operationally a part of OVAM (the Flemish Waste Management Agency), Circular Flanders acts as the focal point for anything related to circular economy in the region. It works in close partnership with private stakeholders (industry), academia, research institutions and civil organisations. Among its six thematic areas, chemicals and plastics, water cycles, bioeconomy, food chain and manufacturing are directly or potentially relevant for industrial-urban symbiosis. The work agendas and initiatives discussed in the section below are resulting from the work done in these sub-groups and are connected to other relevant policy initiatives either led or supported by Circular Flanders.

OVAM, the Flemish Waste Agency¹¹⁶ is another important organisation. As a regulatory body, it designs and supports the implementation of various instruments, including waste and material plans. It also engaged in the financing and monitoring of circular economy initiatives through different mechanisms, including Circular Flanders and the Circular Economy Centre.

On the side of the innovation and engaging with businesses, **Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship (VLAIO)** is worth mentioning. It aims at supporting and stimulating sustainable innovative entrepreneurship in Flanders. It works closely with OVAM and Circular Flanders on some of the strategic agendas and levers. As such, it is an important instrument for the overarching vision of the green revival of the industry. It provides support under many forms including training and advice but also funding to projects. Another important work led by work led by VLAIO is the Flemish cluster policy. Both are explained in sections below.

Funding Mechanisms and other support instruments for I-US

There are many funding instruments which are potentially relevant for IS and I-US which can be grouped in two main categories.

Funding instruments that support green transition in general: these stem from a variety of over-arching policy objectives including climate neutrality and sustainable energy transition and achieving a circular economy. They originate both from federal and regional level.

Since industrial symbiosis can contribute to many green transition objectives, all funding instruments that fall in the first group are potentially relevant and can be used to encourage industrial symbiosis.

¹¹⁶ OVAM website. Accessed: May 17, 2024, Available: <https://ovam-english.vlaanderen.be/>

For instance, The Belgian Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRF) with a total budget of **6.9B€** is a potentially powerful instrument since at least two of its principal objectives can be mobilise for investments in I-US: ‘climate and sustainability’ and ‘economy, productive and innovation’. Together these two pillars make up 51% of the total budget. Several initiatives and projects stemming from RRF have already started. One of them is the federal initiative called ‘Belgium Builds Back Circular (BBBC) with a total budget of 8M€ annually targeting SMEs and research centres, among others. It launches different calls aiming at supporting eco-design and substitution of hazardous substances. These general objectives are translated into more specific topics (wind-energy, bikes, health care and biomimicry for year 2022). Selected projects can receive between 250K€ to 1 M€¹¹⁷.

Funding instruments focusing on innovation and process improvement targeting companies: the second group is somewhat more targeted towards ‘innovation’ while the ultimate objective remains the strategic priorities mentioned in the first group. They target companies (both large and SMEs) operating in Flanders. Important examples include subsidies from VLAIO, namely the *Ecology Premium Plus* and *Strategic Ecology Support*. Both are investment grants and complementary: the former allows companies to benefit from the financial support if they invest in one of the technologies¹¹⁸ included in the ‘limitative technology list’¹¹⁹ and the latter is more adopted to investments that cannot be standardised in this way, due to being more cutting edge and strategic¹²⁰. Both instruments provide up to 1M€ (to cover up to 55% percent of investment) over a period of three years. Examples of the eligible technologies demonstrates that these instruments can potentially be used to put in place processes related to I-US: *production of process heat through fermentation of biomass or wastewater*¹²¹, *heat pipe between two companies*¹²² and *water reuse through electrocoagulation*¹²³.

Further, through the [Moonshot program](#), the Flemish Government will invest 20M€ in industry innovation between 2020-2040 through financing to both early and late-stage innovation projects. In its long-term vision, this industrial innovation program aims at developing cutting-edge technology by 2040 which would then deliver low emission and carbon circularity targets set for 2050. With extensive cooperation between research centres, industries and universities, Moonshot program has four main focus areas (dubbed trajectories): biobased chemistry, circularity of carbon in materials, electrification,

¹¹⁷ Belgian Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment Service, 2023, BBBC 2023 call for circular economy projects, Accessed: May 17, 2024, Available: <https://www.health.belgium.be/en/second-bbbc-call-projects>

¹¹⁸ Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, No date, 49 Limitative Technologies, [In Dutch]. Accessed: May 17, 2024, Available: <https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/limitatieve-technologieen?page=2>

¹¹⁹ Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, No date, What does the Ecology Premium Plus Entail?, Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.vlaio.be/en/subsidies/ecology-premium-plus/what-does-ecology-premium-plus-entail>

¹²⁰ Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, No date, What does the Ecology Premium Plus Entail?, Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.vlaio.be/en/subsidies/ecology-premium-plus/what-does-ecology-premium-plus-entail>

¹²¹ Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, No Date, Limitative Technologies: Production of process heat through fermentation of biomass or waste water, [In Dutch], Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: Productie van proceswarmte door vergisting van biomassa of afvalwater | VLAIO

¹²² Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, No Date, Limitative Technologies: Heat pipeline between two companies, [In Dutch], Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/limitatieve-technologieen/warmteleiding-tussen-twee-bedrijven>

¹²³ Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, No Date, Limitative Technologies: Water reuse by electrocoagulation, [In Dutch], Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/limitatieve-technologieen/waterhergebruik-door-elektrocoagulatie>

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and radical process transformation as well as energy innovation¹²⁴. The program mainly targets refining, chemical, iron and steel industries as they are central in the Flemish landscape. That being said, the importance of cross-sectoral synergies and creating new value chains is acknowledged and following downstream sectors are mentioned: textiles, paper, food, logistics, non-metallic minerals¹²⁵. Six projects have been selected to start in 2024 will receive a total of 14M€ from Flanders. One of them is relevant for the topic of IS: HYBRID: *Harnessing Pyrolysis & Biotechnology to Recycle mixed plastic waste to Dicarboxylic acids*¹²⁶.

The Moonshot initiative is linked to Flemish cluster policy explained below.

Other support instruments: Flemish Cluster Policy

Besides financial support, an important pillar for encouraging industrial symbiosis is facilitation of networks and linkages between the companies. The overall approach is dubbed 'cluster policy' launched in 2016 by the Flemish government. Cluster policy acknowledges the crucial importance of collaboration and ecosystem building to unlock untapped economic potential¹²⁷. Following from this, seven 'spearhead' clusters are selected to work on a long-term transformation of their respective value chains and industries, in collaboration with the government and knowledge centres. Because of their cross-sectoral and innovative character, almost all of them are potentially relevant for industrial symbiosis:

- [Catalisti](#), spearhead cluster for sustainable chemistry and plastics
- SIM, spearhead cluster for materials
- [FLUX50](#), spearhead cluster for energy
- [VIL](#), spearhead cluster for logistics and transport
- [Blue Cluster](#), spearhead cluster for blue growth

These clusters are supported by VLAIO and bring together all relevant stakeholders, though they seem to have different levels of progress and engagement. They each are developing projects under their topic.

¹²⁴ Moonshot Program Website, Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: Moonshot Research Trajectories (MOTs) – moonshotflanders.be

¹²⁵ Moonshot Program Website, Three Target Sectors – moonshotflanders.be

¹²⁶ Moonshot Program Website, Six pioneering Moonshot projects ready for lift-off – moonshotflanders.be

¹²⁷ Flanders Innovation & Entrepreneurship Agency, Cluster Policy in Flanders, Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.vlaio.be/en/clusterorganisaties/het-clusterbeleid/het-vlaamse-clusterbeleid>

A critical reading of the policy: the vision of a competitive Flanders and the role of circular economy in industrial policies

General context

Flanders has a dynamic and innovative industrial landscape. It is well connected, hosts the second largest port in Europe¹²⁸, with a highly educated work force. However, the region is also facing unique challenges. As a very small and densely populated region, there is a real and pressing need to juggle competing land use with a very smart use of space and progressively cutting back on land artificialisation¹²⁹. Second, there is high pollution levels stemming from some of these heavy industries located in the high-potential regions. Further, Belgium is highly dependent on raw material imports. These factors necessitate a multi-focal approach, reconciling the need to stay ahead (competitiveness), encouraging innovating and prosperity as well as moving away from polluting industrial practices.

Industrial symbiosis as a pathway to the revival of the Flemish industry

The concept of industrial symbiosis is not new in this region, at least relatively speaking: the Industrial Policy Plan, dating 2013, the oldest document we scanned, already refers to the ‘Symbiosis Platform’ which was being built around the same time. The symbiosis platform is systematically mentioned throughout the relevant documents including both the National and Flemish Energy and Climate Plans, The Flemish Material Resources Plan as well as sector-specific documents such as the Action Plan Circular Food loss and Biomass and The Chemistry/Plastics Strategic Agenda. It should be noted that these documents only briefly mention the Platform without elaborating on it.

Smart Symbiosis Platform aims at connecting companies to share information about their residual flows and finding higher-value applications for by-products and seems to be the main tool to facilitate IS. It is referred to in multiple documents attesting to its relative importance within the IS initiatives led by public authorities in Flanders.

On the other hand, apart from the Symbiosis Platform, few documents explicitly mention industrial symbiosis as a concept or as an ambition in itself. The documents with highest relevance for industrial symbiosis are the sector-specific sectoral agendas.

In the **Chemicals/Plastics agenda, published in 2022**, the main ambition is to make Flemish chemicals/plastic sector circular by 2050, where ‘*only minimum raw materials are used*’¹³⁰. It targets the entire value chains such as polymer producers, formulators (e.g. paints, industrial lubricants), processors (e.g. plastic objects) and recyclers/processors of these. The complementary with the energy/climate goals also known as the ‘Flemish Climate Leap’ is

¹²⁸ United States Department of Commerce, 2024, Belgian Country Guide, Accessed: May 17, 2024, Available: <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/belgium-market-overview>

¹²⁹ Department of Environment, Policy and Planning, 2018, Flanders Spatial Policy, Available: Flanders Spatial Policy Plan. Strategic vision. Illustrated version | Vlaanderen.be

¹³⁰ Circular Flanders, No date, Work Agenda for Chemistry and Plastics Sector, [In Dutch], Available: Werkagenda ChemieKunstoffen_startcharter_25-04-2022.pdf (vlaanderen-circulair.be)

emphasised particularly because of the heavy carbon footprint of these industries¹³¹. To achieve its goals, the policy identified work paths' one of which is industrial symbiosis (work path 6). Acknowledging the importance of the latter, the document signals a current lack of in-depth understanding as to why industrial symbiosis is not happening across the companies and what are the elements that would bring success. Further, the Gap Analysis report accompanying the strategic agenda has a dedicated section on industrial symbiosis, exploring the barriers and current initiatives to remove them¹³². The document clearly acknowledges that in its current state, IS remains limited to use/reuse of flows at the same company site or exchange of products between companies closely located, but not residual flows. Document also mentions ways of unlocking the potential, such as the Platform and the possibility of screening future investors for openness to symbiosis¹³³. Another important point is that the document makes explicit reference to water and use, as it is a major by-product in the chemical sector¹³⁴.

In the same vein, over-arching policy initiatives such as the Climate and Energy Plan consider industrial symbiosis as a pathway to the ultimate objective at hand, depending on the policy field. Sometimes very close or interchangeable concepts are mentioned, such as side stream valorisation in the chemicals industry, or encouraging 'more circularity in the production processes' (National Circular Action Plan for a Circular Economy 2021-2024).

Other documents hint at the concept, without mentioning it, especially when it underscores wider or similar ambitions such as 'stable demand and use of circular raw materials' or 'a *local processing market for locally generated waste*' (*Manufacturing Industry Strategic Agenda*), 'side-stream valorisation' (*Smart Specialisation Strategy*) or 'smart and efficient use of materials and close material cycles' (*Vision 2050*). In other documents, such as the Flemish Coalition Agreement (2019-2024), both circular economy and energy/industry intersection are important components of policy plan. Stemming from that, ambitions such as 'zero waste incineration' are set out, implying a fundamentally different approach to the current industrial processes¹³⁵. Although nothing is mentioned about industrial symbiosis as such, nor exchange of energy or waste streams between the industries, one can assume that IS can potentially contribute achieving these ambitions.

Ultimately, these are connected to the strategic long-term vision of strengthening the innovative character, prosperity, and the competitiveness of Flemish industry at the global stage. The double objectives of sustainability and industrial productivity are seen as the gateway to the revival of the Flemish industry. Innovation and high-added value come to fore as the forces spearheading this revival. Thus, the concepts of IS and U-IS are interesting for the policy makers to explore, as they can be considered innovative by definition. They are one of the elements binding industrial policy and

¹³¹ Circular Flanders, No date, Work Agenda for Chemistry and Plastics Sector, [In Dutch], Available: [Werkagenda ChemieKunststoffen_startcharter_25-04-2022.pdf](#) (vlaanderen-circulair.be)

¹³² Circular Flanders, No date, Chemicals and Plastics Work Agenda Background Report: Gap Analysis, Available: [Rapport GAP-analyse_v1_1.pdf](#) (vlaanderen-circulair.be)

¹³³ Circular Flanders, No date, Chemicals and Plastics Work Agenda Background Report: Gap Analysis, Available: [Rapport GAP-analyse_v1_1.pdf](#) (vlaanderen-circulair.be)

¹³⁴ Circular Flanders, No date, Chemicals and Plastics Work Agenda Background Report: Gap Analysis, Available: [Rapport GAP-analyse_v1_1.pdf](#) (vlaanderen-circulair.be)

¹³⁵ Flemish Department of Chancellery, 2019, The Flemish Coalition Agreement 2019-2024, [In Dutch]. Available: 31741 (vlaanderen.be)

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innovation and R&D together. Therefore, even though IS and I-US are not mentioned systematically throughout the documents, they are hinted at as powerful levers to arrive a strategic objective.

Sectors targeted by the policy documents relevant for IS and U-IS

Not surprisingly, the sectors that are important the Flemish industry are frequently mentioned in many of the documents. It is important to mention that the latest overarching industrial policy strategy dates to 2013, however other initiatives have seen the day since then, without an updated framework strategy.

In the circular economy policy, the following sectors are identified as priority and addressed through ‘strategic agendas’: circular construction; chemistry and plastics; water cycles; bioeconomy; food chain and manufacturing. Among those, chemistry and plastics, bioeconomy and manufacturing agendas were analysed more closely as they are more relevant for the scope of this study. The emphasis on the same sectors is echoed in other documents which seem to form a coherent policy in the absence of the over-arching strategy.

Challenges to IS and I-US

Only the sector-specific documents mention challenges related to industrial symbiosis. Currently only large companies are taking part in what can be considered as industrial symbiosis as they can afford to face the ‘Death Valley’ curve. The latter refers to the situation where cost of becoming circular/changing long-established practices undermine the financial viability of a company, therefore its very existence. Chemical/plastics work agenda states that exchanging residual flows might be too costly because of the distances between the locations and the limited quantities exchanged. A number of other barriers are mentioned:

- A general lack of interest among the companies
- Silos thinking and linear paradigm with legislation lagging behind
- Lack of framework in which they can operate
- The end-of-waste criteria due to lack of clarity around it and the very late point in which it gets triggered along the chain
- Lack of harmonised rules within the EU to transport such materials
- Sometimes the receiving end of the symbiosis might not be fully aware of the content of the material, leading to reluctance
- No strategic planning/permit granting when building industrial sites (for instance to encourage those willing to exchange residual flows¹³⁶)

Another sectoral policy document focusing on biomass underlines the ‘fragmented landscape, ownership structure rules and regulations’ of Flanders, making exchange of flows difficult. Logistic issues such as collection, transport and storage are seen as important challenges. Biomass hubs are considered part of the solution, but they are not easy to start and operate. Further, new fields of application might fail because a continuous supply and/or demand cannot be guaranteed due to many reasons, including regulatory uncertainty.

The Plastics Implementation Plan further states that there is lack of transparency on the use of recyclates since the converters fear that the latter will be considered inferior (less good) to the virgin

¹³⁶ Circular Flanders, No date, Work Agenda for Chemistry and Plastics Sector, [In Dutch], Available: Werkagenda ChemieKunststoffen_startcharter_25-04-2022.pdf (vlaanderen-circulair.be)

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materials. This leads to a lack of interest¹³⁷. Although this is not directly related to IS, it is very relevant in terms of understanding the barriers.

Other barriers are mentioned in some of the documents, but these are not specific to IS and can apply to circular economy in general. These include lack of data on flows/resource use¹³⁸, lack of understanding of circular projects within the finance sector and methodologies to evaluate these¹³⁹.

Finally, the ERDF program (2021-2027) refers back to the death-valley phenomenon for the broader concept of 'innovation'. It states that the phase between establishing proven results and scaling up is capital intensive while still being uncertain about the return on investment. This is considered a major barrier and the importance of efforts to 'valorise innovative applications' is emphasised¹⁴⁰. This is relevant since U-IS related processes can be considered innovative.

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving industrial symbiosis

Among the multitude of actors needed to accelerate the transition to industrial symbiosis, the policy puts emphasis on private actors and more specifically the sectors with relatively big importance in the economic landscape of Flanders. Since some of these sectors are also considerably polluting or carbon-heavy, the angle of sustainability/innovation seems to be a good entry point. The role of the Flemish government seems to be creating an enabling environment for the private actors to lead the way. In other words, public authorities provide a common framework and a hub (such as Circular Flanders) with a facilitating role. This is complemented by practical tools, also provided by the public authorities such as the Smart Symbiosis Platform, support services and/or funding. These initiatives partially respond to the challenges identified, specifically to the 'fragmented landscape' by offering an eco-system development service and connecting diverse actors. As such, the Flemish policy acknowledges the importance of good governance and necessity to encourage collaboration between all relevant stakeholders. For instance, Circular Flanders has a governance model that reflects the multi-actor nature of circular economy and the need to collaborate in order to 'scale up and mainstream' the innovative character of circular economy projects. This results in six thematic agendas, each led by one private and one public entity: circular construction, chemicals and plastics, water cycles, bioeconomy, food chain and manufacturing. Each of these thematic agendas have their own priorities, working groups and initiatives. They are all supported by seven levers namely, policy, procurement, communication, research, innovation and entrepreneurship, financing and jobs & skills¹⁴¹. In turn, leaders for six agendas work under the strategic leadership of the Transition Manager, creating the link to the relevant ministries and various stakeholders. This approach also helps to accommodate the different needs and priorities of different sectors while steering the entire economy in the same strategic dimension.

¹³⁷ OVAM, 2020, Plastics Implementation Plan, Available: 55065 (vlaanderen.be)

¹³⁸ Government of Flanders, 2016, Vision 2050: A longterm Strategy for Flanders, [In Dutch], Available: 28831 (vlaanderen.be)

¹³⁹ Belgian Federal Ministry of Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, No Date, Federal Action Plan for a Circular Economy 2021-2024, [In French], Available; Plan-d-action-federale-economie-circulaire-2021-2024.pdf (fgov.be)

¹⁴⁰ The European Commission, ERDF 2021-2027 Flanders, [Online], Accessed: May 17, 2024, Available: Inforegio - ERDF 2021-2027 Flanders (europa.eu)

¹⁴¹ Circular Flanders, Our Approach, [Online], Accessed: May 17, 2024, Available: <https://vlaanderen-circulair.be/en/approach>

Figure 14: Governance Structure of Circular Flanders, Source: Circular Flanders

Further, there are funding mechanisms made available which is an important lever for accelerating the transition. Although these funding instruments do not target industrial symbiosis directly, they can be instrumentalised for the latter. Once all the support structures are in place, the industrial stakeholders are invited to take lead and advance forward, using the help provided by the public authorities.

Flanders-The Netherlands Overview

South Holland Region in The Netherlands is the second territory within the Flanders identified cluster. The Netherlands is a decentralised unitary state with both sub-national levels (provinces and municipalities) holding considerable powers. Whereas the central government has legislative powers on all policy fields, the latter can issue provincial and local regulations as long as they are in line with the national ones. Policy fields relevant for this study including energy, spatial planning, circular economy policies are therefore planned at both levels and implemented at regional and local level.

Policies specifically targeting IS and/or I-US and their origins

The longer list of 16 document for the Netherlands includes, where relevant, supporting studies for the policy making and overview documents which provide important information on the topic or websites. Except two, none of the policy documents explicitly mentions the concept of industrial symbiosis. However, they contain other concepts that are directly connected to industrial symbiosis¹⁴². Therefore, we made the selection larger to cover those as well:

- Circular Vision for the Netherlands 2050 (National)

¹⁴² For the list of keywords used in screening see Annex 3: List of keywords used for screening/selecting the documents for in-depth analysis in the policy section

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- National Circular Economy Program 2023-2030 (National)
- Circular Economy Implementation Programme (National)
- Transition Agenda for Manufacturing Industry and its relevant documents (National)
- Transition Agenda for Plastics Industry (National)
- Raw Materials Agreement (National)
- The Dutch Climate Agreement 2050 (National)
- Spatial Strategy of South Holland (Regional)
- Circular Strategy for South Holland and its update in 2023 (Regional)
- Final report on Circular Trading Platforms (National and regional)

The country has a climate neutrality and fully circular economy target by 2050. South Holland region follows this ambition, as well as an intermediate target of halving the use of fossil-based raw materials, minerals, and metals by 2030¹⁴³.

All these documents are relevant for IS and I-US although at varying degrees. They all integrate the overarching vision of carbon neutrality and zero-waste with an increasing awareness of raw material security, coupled with sustainability and the innovative character of the region. They are supported via measures using the full spectrum of policy toolbox available to the policy makers (from taxes to spatial land planning, from facilitation to redefining end-of-waste criteria).

The main potential entry points are the National and Regional Circular Economy Plans, the Raw Materials Agreement, Spatial Policies, Climate Policy and the National Transition Agendas which constitute the backbone of the policy approach to industrial strategies in the country. Together they cascade into several different programs supporting the policy objectives, such as innovation missions.

At regional level, an industrial strategy is not available, however it is reported that the region will publish its integrated energy and industrial strategy in 2024¹⁴⁴. The regional circular economy plan is also relevant. They are discussed further below.

Main Actors with work relevant for industrial-urban symbiosis

At national level, the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management plays a very important role in design, implementation, coordination, and monitoring of several policies relevant for circular economy (hence industrial symbiosis, potentially). It is particularly important for fields such as plastics and consumer goods and construction. The other ministries relevant for sectoral focus on circular economy (transition agendas) are the following:

- Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations for construction (housing and non-residential).
- Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy for manufacturing industry.
- Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality for biomass and food.

Further, the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science is important since innovation constitutes an important entry point for IS and I-US as well an asset of the sustainable Dutch economy.

¹⁴³ The Province of South Holland, 2023, Updated Circular Economy Strategy 2023-2023 [In Dutch], Available: [Strategie+'Samen+bouwen+aan+een+Circulair+Zuid-Holland'](#) (notubiz.nl)

¹⁴⁴ OECD, 2024, The Circular Economy in Zuid-Holland, Netherlands, OECD Regional Development Papers, n° 70. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1787/d568d66e-en>

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Another important entity for governance and cooperation is the Association of Dutch Provinces (IPO)¹⁴⁵, acknowledging the important role of regional entities in the transition. It provides a ‘helicopter view’ of the initiatives in different provinces and enables synergies and collaboration. It also presents a unified front vis-a-vis the national government, voicing the needs of provinces to support the transition through initiatives such as Power Map (KrachtenKaart)¹⁴⁶.

At regional level, important actors include all the relevant provincial ministries stemming from the national ministries (the province of South Holland has responsibilities in spatial planning, environment, water, landscape, regional economy, and transport infrastructure), The Economic Affairs Bureau of the Department of Society and Economy and the South Holland Economic Board. There are other structures for coordination and support of diverse initiatives such as innovation agencies, business stakeholders’ networks and academic institutions for innovation which are explained further below.

Funding mechanisms and other support instruments

EU, National and Regional funds are used in tandem to support circular economy related projects. The European Regional Development Fund is one of the most important instruments, co-funded by each region, including South Holland. For the period 2014-2020, provinces jointly invested 229M€ per year for such regional programs, though it is not known how much of this amount went to CE projects specifically, let alone IS¹⁴⁷.

Innovation Incentives Scheme for Regional and Top Sectors, partially financed by the provinces, provides additional financing, amounting to 118M€ for 2015-2020 (all combined)¹⁴⁸. It is reported that 10% of this budget was allocated to CE-related projects¹⁴⁹.

In the national policy for circular economy, financial support is part of the ‘stimulus’ pillar. These can target specific sectors. For instance, the National Growth Fund will invest 500M€ in circular plastics over an eight-year period (2022-2030), of which 220M€ will come from public budget¹⁵⁰. A specific example for the use of this fund is the Circular Plastics Programme (CPNL), by Dutch Research Council, that will run for eight years and provide funding for research to overcome the bottlenecks to circularity in the plastics sector¹⁵¹.

¹⁴⁵ IPO (Association of Dutch Provinces), Website [In Dutch], Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: <https://www.ipo.nl/>

¹⁴⁶ IPO (Association of Dutch Provinces), Power Map, Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: [a0-formaat-krachtenkaart-ipo-engels.pdf](#)

¹⁴⁷ EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for the Netherlands, Available: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/netherlands_ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

¹⁴⁸ EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for the Netherlands, Available: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/netherlands_ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

¹⁴⁹ EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for the Netherlands, Available: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/netherlands_ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

¹⁵⁰ Government of Netherlands, 2023, National Circular Economy Program, Available at: [National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 | Policy paper | Rijksoverheid.nl](#)

¹⁵¹ NWO, Announcement: research on technical innovations to make plastics circular | NWO.

At regional level, all the above can be mobilised to accelerate transition¹⁵². The Circular Strategy mentions that ‘South Holland is the only province where universities, businesses and government have set up a knowledge program with more than 7 M€ to accelerate the transition to a circular economy’¹⁵³. Provincial budget is also important: OECD reports that CE-related funding tripled between 2020 and 2023 from 750K€ to 2.5M€, at least partially financed with provincial tax on motor vehicles¹⁵⁴. Further, the circular economy strategy of the province states that ‘providing sufficient funding for circular business and start-ups by 2030 is one of the objectives as well as linking circularity to certain subsidies as a condition’¹⁵⁵. Financial support to start-ups and innovative companies/projects constitutes the main entry point. An example is the Innovation Quarter, led by the Regional Development Agency of South Holland supporting high-risk and disruptive projects needing longer term investment streams. It uses equities and loans ranging from 250K€ to 5M€ to support ‘deep tech’ and ‘high-tech’ innovations¹⁵⁶.

Another way of supporting circular business is circular procurement and the public authorities leading ‘by example’, by ‘being the client’. These however stay at circular economy level – without going into further detail.

Other support instruments

The research identified two support instruments specifically targeting IS and I-US. First can be considered as a portal dedicated to IS and I-US named Circular.Biz. It is a joint initiative between the provinces of South Holland, Groningen, Limburg, their environmental services, and associated initiatives in each province¹⁵⁷. It helps both public authorities and businesses to become circular by providing information on circular opportunities, data flows and community building. It has specific sections targeting the provinces, including South Holland and its four distinct geographical regions (Metropolitan Rotterdam and Ten Haag, Central, West, and South Islands)¹⁵⁸. The provinces and businesses can see their mapped potential (currently available for a limited number of regions with more to come) and consult the circular opportunities database. If available, there is more specific information on delimited spaces (industrial estates or business parks) with information on their circularity level, e.g. quantities of waste reused and incinerated. Further, the companies are invited to list their resources or look for specific materials to further expand the knowledge base. The website seems to be still incomplete with more information to come however seems very promising¹⁵⁹.

¹⁵² The Province of South Holland, 2023, Updated Circular Economy Strategy 2023-2023 [In Dutch], Available: [Strategie+Samen+bouwen+aan+een+Circulair+Zuid-Holland'](#) (notubiz.nl)

¹⁵³ The Province of South Holland, 2020, Circular Strategy for South Holland [In Dutch], Available: [circulairzuid-holland-samenversnellen-5.pdf](#)

¹⁵⁴ OECD, 2024, The Circular Economy in Zuid-Holland, Netherlands, OECD Regional Development Papers, n° 70. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1787/d568d66e-en>

¹⁵⁵ The Province of South Holland, 2023, Updated Circular Economy Strategy 2023-2023 [In Dutch], Available: [Strategie+Samen+bouwen+aan+een+Circulair+Zuid-Holland'](#) (notubiz.nl)

¹⁵⁶ Innovation Quarter, Website. Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: [InnovationQuarter long-term investor for startups & scale-ups](#)

¹⁵⁷ Circulair.biz, Website [In Dutch], Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: <https://circulair.biz/over-circulair-biz/achtergrondinformatie/>.

¹⁵⁸ Circulair.biz, South Holland [In Dutch], Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: <https://circulair.biz/zuid-holland/>

¹⁵⁹ Circulair.biz, Overview for Maasoever District [In Dutch], Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: <https://circulair.biz/rechter-maasoever/>

Figure 15: A snapshot from the website, Circular.Biz – providing information on circularity potential and materials flows for different business parks in each district – example of Metropolitan Rotterdam and Ten Haag¹⁶⁰.

¹⁶⁰ Circulair.biz, Factsheet for MRDH sub-region, [In Dutch], Accessed: June 04, 2024. Available: https://circulair.biz/zuid-holland/mrdh/factsheets-mrdh/?_factsheets=mrdh

The other one is the 'Multi-annual Mission Driven Innovation Programs (MMIPs), stemming from the climate goals for 2050¹⁶¹, which mentions industrial symbiosis as a potential pathway to sustainability¹⁶². However, it seems to be mostly steered by industrial stakeholders involving the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate (EKZ) and the Netherlands Enterprise Agency as participants¹⁶³. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning since it has sub-topics that are potential entry points for IS and I-US. For instance, the MMIP 6 – Closing industrial chains program support the ambition of 80% circular Dutch industry by 2050, with three relevant sub-programmes: circular plastics, CCU (Carbon Capture and Usage – the use of CO₂ as a raw material) and circular non-ferrous metals¹⁶⁴.

Other more generic support instruments target circular businesses through a variety of different structures and are all potentially relevant for IS and I-US. The main two focus areas seem to be facilitation and network-building targeting business ecosystem and in parallel, supporting innovation and research. The connection between the two is considered vital for the innovative character of the Dutch business landscape. Many of the funding structures mentioned above also provide 'softer' support such as networking, inter-sectoral and inter-disciplinary connections, knowledge sharing and training to companies. The Dutch Research Council (NWO) provides networking and knowledge building space coupled with funding mentioned above¹⁶⁵. The Innovation Quarter is providing similar support via connecting innovation start-ups in South Holland to regional and international networks¹⁶⁶. Connected to the Innovation Quarter, another regional entity worth mentioning is the EBZ (Economic Board of South Holland). It gathers leading companies in the focus industries, public authorities, and research sector to mobilise the collective expertise in the region to realise the South Holland Growth Agenda¹⁶⁷. One of its task forces focuses on circular economy and more specifically, chemical industry in the region¹⁶⁸. Specific tools such as the 'Stakeholder Scan' are also important: the latter provides information on companies' circular strategies and activities to each other as well similarities, facilitating network building¹⁶⁹. Also important to mention is the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO)¹⁷⁰ actively taking part in initiatives such as the MMIP mentioned above. It is a government-led

¹⁶¹ Institute for Sustainable Process Technology, Multiannual Mission Driven Innovation Programs (MMIP's), [In Dutch] Accessed: June 04, Available at: <https://ispt.eu/mmip/>

¹⁶² Van der Brink, O et al, (No Date), Final Proposal for MMIP6: Closure of industrial, [In Dutch], Available: <https://www.klimaataakkoord.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/11/07/mmip6-sluiting-van-industriële-ketens>

¹⁶³ Van der Brink, O et al, (No Date), Final Proposal for MMIP6: Closure of industrial, [In Dutch], Available: <https://www.klimaataakkoord.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/11/07/mmip6-sluiting-van-industriële-ketens>

¹⁶⁴ Van der Brink, O et al, (No Date), Final Proposal for MMIP6: Closure of industrial, [In Dutch], Available: <https://www.klimaataakkoord.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/11/07/mmip6-sluiting-van-industriële-ketens>

¹⁶⁵ Dutch Research Council, Website, Accessed: June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.nwo.nl/en>

¹⁶⁶ Innovation Quarter, Working Towards a Health South Holland, Website. Accessed: June 04, 2024, Available: Life Sciences & Health – Innovation Quarter

¹⁶⁷ The Economic Board of South-Holland, What is the Economic Board of Zuid-Holland? Website. [In Dutch] Accessed: June 04, 2024, Available: What is the Economic Board Zuid-Holland? - EBZ | Economic Board Zuid-Holland (economicboardzuidholland.nl)

¹⁶⁸ The Economic Board of South-Holland, What is the Economic Board of Zuid-Holland? Website. [In Dutch] Accessed: June 04, 2024, Available: What is the Economic Board Zuid-Holland? - EBZ | Economic Board Zuid-Holland (economicboardzuidholland.nl)

¹⁶⁹ Circular Manufacturing Industry Management Team, 2022, Advisory Roadmap for Manufacturing Industry Transition Agenda, [In Dutch], Available: Adviesroutekaart Transitieagenda Maakindustrie (2022) - Circulaire Maakindustrie

¹⁷⁰ Netherlands Enterprise Agency, About RVO, Available: <https://english.rvo.nl/topics/about-us>

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agency with the main mission of supporting Dutch businesses on many topics, including sustainability and innovation.

Further, since 2012, The Green Brain (Het Groen Brein) gathers academics and researchers from diverse disciplines to support companies on specific questions related to sustainability, including circular economy¹⁷¹. They are connected to other support programs such as The Acceleration House (Versnellingshuis) which provides tailored support to businesses. Without providing funding, it helps businesses to become more circular by helping to connect with others to share knowledge about existing circular solutions as well navigating legal and financial support structures¹⁷². The latter is a joint initiative between the public authorities, trade associations, SMEs and research institutes¹⁷³. The work pillars of the Acceleration House mirror the policy ambitions, as mentioned above. For instance, every year, its Moonshot programmes selects five Moonshot projects, gathering multiple stakeholders across ‘complex’ chains. At the time of writing, there are 21 Moonshots each connected to one or more transition agendas. A specific example, directly relevant is Moonshot 15: Industrial Symbiosis: Collecting and Scaling. This ‘meta’ level project studied the digital platforms, their added value and how they be sustained and scaled-up in the future¹⁷⁴.

Another important initiative is CIRCO, which focuses on circular design with agencies on each regional hub, including South Holland. It provides networking, tools for various purposes (e.g. impact assessment tools, webinars, guides, case stories and templates for business models) targeting businesses. It has targeted ‘tracks’, series of online and in-person workshops for companies¹⁷⁵. One example is ‘Plastic residual flow reflections’ where companies can join in person to learn about business opportunities and upcoming regulations, focusing on circularity in the plastic production chain¹⁷⁶.

A critical reading of the policy: the vision of a competitive Flanders and the role of circular economy in industrial policies

General context

South Holland shares similar characteristics to its neighbour across the border: both densely populated regions with innovative character, heavy industries concentrated on the territory and a highly skilled workforce. Since most of the manufacturing is processing industry, there is awareness about the dependency on imported raw materials and the risks this entails¹⁷⁷. At the same time, due to its geographical context, addressing climate change is considered very high priority, hence working

¹⁷¹ Het Groene Brein, About Us, Website [In Dutch], Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://hetgroenebrein.nl/over-ons/>

¹⁷² Accelerator House, Website, [In Dutch], Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: [Versnellingshuis Nederland Circulair! | Hulp bij circulair ondernemen \(versnellingshuisce.nl\)](https://versnellingshuisce.nl/)

¹⁷³ Accelerator House, Website, [In Dutch], Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: [What is the Acceleration House Netherlands Circulair! | About us \(versnellingshuisce.nl\)](https://versnellingshuisce.nl/), Accessed June 04, 2024

¹⁷⁴ Accelerator House, Moonshot 15: Industrial Symbiosis: Connection and Scale Up, [In Dutch]. Accessed: June 04 2024, Available: <https://versnellingshuisce.nl/circulaire-ketens/moonshotprojecten/moonshot-15-industriële-symbiose-of-verbinding-en-opschaling>

¹⁷⁵ Circo, Website, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: [CIRCO | Circular business models & sustainable design strategies \(circonl.nl\)](https://circonl.nl/)

¹⁷⁶ Circo Track on Plastics, Event Page, [In Dutch]. Accessed: June 04 2024, Available: [Track- Plastic residual flow reflections - CIRCO \(circonl.nl\)](https://circonl.nl/)

¹⁷⁷ Government of Netherlands, 2016, Government-wide Circular Economy programme, Circular Netherlands 2050 [In Dutch], Available: [pdf \(overheid.nl\)](https://overheid.nl/)

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towards climate neutrality. Therefore, the policy ambitions emphasise these challenges and try to provide solutions that will deliver multiple benefits at once. Against this background sustainability, carbon-neutrality and zero-waste are all intimately linked to the idea of raw material security and territorial resilience.

Furthermore, the Netherlands has currently the highest resource productivity in the EU¹⁷⁸. South Holland is particularly important since it has the biggest contribution to GDP and is the country's most populous region¹⁷⁹. Further, it is home to the largest port in the EU, Rotterdam with important economic activity ranging from chemicals to refineries with considerable contribution to GHG emissions¹⁸⁰.

Industrial symbiosis: an un-named pathway to achieve multiple objectives

As mentioned above, IS or I-US are not explicitly mentioned in most of the documents, except two lower-level support documents to main policy¹⁸¹. Despite this, there is an awareness about the concept although it is not fully explored, at least in terms of operationalising the policy ambitions. For instance, The National Circular Economy Program (NCEP hereafter) sets the overarching priorities and the direction around which other policies will be built. NCEP is structured around 4 main pillars, three of which are potentially relevant for IS and I-US: reducing the use of raw materials (narrowing the loop), substituting raw materials with more sustainable alternatives and high-grade processing (close the loop)¹⁸². This is particularly important for fossil-based raw materials that need to be substituted by either recycle or bio-based materials.

Similarly, the Circular Strategy for South Holland (and its update published in 2023) has the same priority sectors (plastics, built-environment, biomass and food, manufacturing industry). The document itself does not mention IS and I-US but the concept is very much present throughout the approach. For instance, the older version presents the use of waste from one company by another as a promising venue and mentions concrete examples of IS projects¹⁸³. Rotterdam port is mentioned in relation to residual flows and the opportunities that it presents. Further, the policy is aware of many promising though experimental initiatives within the plastics and bio-mass sectors (reuse of plastics and high-grade input materials such as peat, rock wool) as well as the link between the port and the urban areas, all of which are essential for I-US.

Perhaps most importantly, the policy gives a clear message to the industry as an important financial partner: it states that initiatives that do not incorporate other partners in the value chains within the region will not be considered for support (finance or otherwise). To complement this, the updated version also mentioned the importance of spatial planning to encourage circular initiatives. There are

¹⁷⁸ EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for the Netherlands, Available: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/netherlands_ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

¹⁷⁹ The Province of South Holland, 2020, Circular Strategy for South Holland [In Dutch], Available: [circulairzuid-holland-samenversnellen-5.pdf](https://www.circulairzuid-holland-samenversnellen-5.pdf)

¹⁸⁰ The Port of Rotterdam, Website. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en/why-rotterdam/port-will-take-you-ahead>

¹⁸¹ These are the documents referenced in 162 and 191.

¹⁸² Government of Netherlands, Website: Circular Dutch economy by 2050. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: [Circular Dutch economy by 2050 | Circular economy | Government.nl](https://www.circulardutch.nl/en/circular-dutch-economy-by-2050)

¹⁸³ For instance see the Asbeter Project, Available: <https://www.asbeter.com/en>

many activities on-going under each of themes for instance the work of Circular Task Force (Economic Board Zuid-Holland Taskforce Circulair)¹⁸⁴ to explore possibilities in the port area for a plastic valorisation hub¹⁸⁵.

Policies pertaining to land use are another important entry point. Generally speaking, they have the ambition to make space for circular businesses at the expense of linear ones. This is considered necessary in the face of space limitations and competition within the dense country. Further, the South Holland Spatial Strategy has three building blocks, one of which is '*Building and strengthening a circular spatial framework*', which aims at creating the physical conditions for circular economy within specific territories, based on their unique characteristics. Directly relevant for I-US are the following sub-themes: connections into a sustainable energy system; '*a logistical system for circular material flows*'; and '*transforming the waste management system into a raw materials and residual streams system*'¹⁸⁶.

When it comes to sectoral policies, transition agendas build the backbone of policy intervention, and directly follow from the 'supply chain/sector approach'. They target sectors with high-impact potential to deliver lasting change. In South Holland these are construction, biomass and food, manufacturing and plastics¹⁸⁷. For the purposes of this study, we have looked into Plastics and Manufacturing Transition agendas. For the Manufacturing Agenda, several sub-topics are chosen as priority: photovoltaic panels, air-conditioning machinery, and wind-turbines. These are important at the junction of climate policy with raw material use as they present important opportunities but necessitate a holistic approach. Relevant points worth mentioning are the strategic ambition aligned with the wider circular economy plan (e.g. closing the loop and reducing the use of raw materials). More specifically, the industry is expected to reduce material use by adopting new process technologies (to produce these products). The region aims to support that by many initiatives including creating regional networks gathering diverse stakeholders. A specific example mentioned in the section dedicated to wind-turbines reflects elements of industrial symbiosis: use of co-processing in cement for turbine blades production and creating of value-chains for recycling composites from diverse sectors. The document acknowledges the wide spectrum of this area and calls for further exploration of possibilities. The Plastics Agenda¹⁸⁸ also includes similar element but goes into further detail about the issues of 'residual flows' whereas the Manufacturing Agenda seems to focus on the recycling of parts at the end of their life cycle.

Policy makers employ a wide range of tools they have at hand to operationalise these ambitions. These include taxation more polluting primary raw materials, eco-modulation, extending polluter pays principle or minimum recycle requirements. Softer measures are also deployed such as creating 'hubs' to enable cooperation between stakeholders. Innovation remains a very important enabler and

¹⁸⁴ Province of South Holland, Website. Activities: Economic Board of South Holland: Circular Taskforce, [In Dutch], Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://circulair.zuid-holland.nl/activiteit/economic-board-zuid-holland-taskforce-circulair/>

¹⁸⁵ Province of South Holland, Website. Activities: Plastic valorisation hub Zuid-Holland [In Dutch], Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://circulair.zuid-holland.nl/activiteit/plastic-vervaardingshub-zuid-holland/>

¹⁸⁶ BVR and Ecorys for the Province of Zuid-Holland, 2022, Spatial Strategy for Zuid Holland: Main messages.

¹⁸⁷ Province of South Holland, Circular Economy Themes, Website. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://circulair.zuid-holland.nl/themas/>

¹⁸⁸ Transition Agenda for Plastics Industry, 2018, [In Dutch], Available: pdf (overheid.nl)

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is encourage financially but also by creating ‘regulatory sandboxes’ where experimentation can be allowed without regulatory barriers.

On the other hand, as mentioned above, when it comes to achieving industrial symbiosis, the policy remains vague. This might be related to the governance approach which would entail providing the direction in the form of outcomes for the industry without being prescriptive. Further, for some of the priorities, the focus seems to be on recycling at the end-of-life cycle of a product (e.g. wind turbines) or substitution of fossil-based raw materials rather than the actual production process. This might present limitations, at least conceptually, in terms of supporting IS and I-US.

Sectors targeted by the policy documents relevant for IS and I-US

As a good practice example of evidence-base policy making, both national and regional level build their interventions on studies and or analyses of the territorial context and conditions. Therefore, all sectors important for the region are identified in terms of material flows and potential impact. These are aligned with the priority sectors mentioned above (for South Holland these are bioeconomy and food, manufacturing, plastics and built environment).

Challenges to IS and I-US

There is little information specific to implementation of IS-related initiatives. Context dependant challenges are relevant including the density and space limitation, high dependence on imported materials used by the processing industries, the economic model with lower prices for virgin materials, cost of labour and legal barriers. The following are more directly relevant for IS and I-US, compiled from a variety of sources scanned:

- Lack of market for circular products and services¹⁸⁹
- Difficulties in trading in secondary materials¹⁹⁰ more specifically, administrative burden associated with using these materials that were classified as ‘waste’ and labour intensiveness of finding, assessing, and purchasing these materials¹⁹¹
- Legal uncertainty about secondary raw materials and shared infrastructure¹⁹²
- Legal issues regarding liability (who bears responsibility if the product is defective?)¹⁹³
- Companies’ fear that they will be locked-in to certain operations or service delivery (for instance delivering residual heat to urban areas) which will result in loss of freedom of action¹⁹⁴

¹⁸⁹ EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for the Netherlands, Available: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/netherlands_ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

¹⁹⁰ EEA, 2022, Circular Economy Profile for the Netherlands, Available: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-ce/products/etc-ce-products/etc-ce-report-5-2022-country-profiles-on-circular-economy/netherlands_ce-country-profile-2022_for-publication.pdf

¹⁹¹ Huisman, C. et al, Royal HaskoningDHV Report for Province of South Holland, 2021, Final report on Circular Trading Platforms, [In Dutch], Available at: <Eindrapportage-Circulaire-Handelsplatformen-Royal-HaskoningDHV.pdf> (zuid-holland.nl)

¹⁹² Van der Brink, O et al, (No Date), Final Proposal for MMIP6: Closure of industrial, [In Dutch], Available: <https://www.klimaataakkoord.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/11/07/mmip6-sluiting-van-industriële-ketens>

¹⁹³ Huisman, C. et al, Royal HaskoningDHV Report for Province of South Holland, 2021, Final report on Circular Trading Platforms, [In Dutch], Available at: <Eindrapportage-Circulaire-Handelsplatformen-Royal-HaskoningDHV.pdf> (zuid-holland.nl)

¹⁹⁴ Van der Brink, O et al, (No Date), Final Proposal for MMIP6: Closure of industrial, [In Dutch], Available: <https://www.klimaataakkoord.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/11/07/mmip6-sluiting-van-industriële-ketens>

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- Material use at higher scales of R hierarchy is currently less accessible for the businesses¹⁹⁵
- Circular businesses (e.g. start-ups, innovation projects) remain limited and lack necessary acceleration and up-scaling¹⁹⁶
- Lack of information on the material flows and materials¹⁹⁷ and related to that, difficulties in anticipating which material will be available and when (supply issues)¹⁹⁸
- Main focus being on OEMs (original equipment manufacturers) rather than those who supply to the latter, which is a far larger group. For the manufacturing industry, this implies that the policy will have a limited effect¹⁹⁹
- Putting the materials back into circular means paying TVA once again, for instance for the products purchased through platforms²⁰⁰
- For plastics, the legal issues related to the end-of waste criteria²⁰¹, but the same is mentioned for other sectors as well
- Logistical barriers such as the distance between the buyer and the seller and/or storage space for secondary materials²⁰²

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving IS and I-US

There are multiple ways in which the public authorities interact with a variety of stakeholders to support the transition to circular economy in the Netherlands. The NCEP differentiates among three types: pricing measures such as taxes, standard setting measures such as waste regulations, land use permit and stimulus measures, such as funding, public procurement, and support to eco-system building²⁰³. Policy makers use all three for a wide range of fields and stimulus measures complement harder regulations. For all three, the emphasis is on the essential duty of the government to provide necessary conditions for the stakeholders to thrive in their circular journey, with support targeted to their needs and specific conditions.

This approach is mirrored at regional level. Circular Strategy for South Holland states that the province ‘*opens the doors, provide financing when needed and helps scale up the projects*’. Further, due to geographic proximity to the local actors, the role of the public authorities as facilitator, knowledge

¹⁹⁵ Government of Netherlands, 2023, National Circular Economy Program, Available at: National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 | Policy paper | Rijksoverheid.nl

¹⁹⁶ The Province of South Holland, 2023, Updated Circular Economy Strategy 2023-2023 [In Dutch], Available: Strategie+‘Samen+bouwen+aan+een+Circulair+Zuid-Holland’ (notubiz.nl)

¹⁹⁷ Circular Manufacturing Industry Management Team, 2022, Advisory Roadmap for Manufacturing Industry Transition Agenda, [In Dutch], Available: Adviesroutekaart Transitieagenda Maakindustrie (2022) - Circulaire Maakindustrie

¹⁹⁸ Huisman, C. et al, Royal HaskoningDHV Report for Province of South Holland, 2021, Final report on Circular Trading Platforms, [In Dutch], Available at: Eindrapportage-Circulaire-Handelsplatformen-Royal-HaskoningDHV.pdf (zuid-holland.nl)

¹⁹⁹ ¹⁹⁹ Circular Manufacturing Industry Management Team, 2022, Advisory Roadmap for Manufacturing Industry Transition Agenda, [In Dutch], Available: Adviesroutekaart Transitieagenda Maakindustrie (2022) - Circulaire Maakindustrie

²⁰⁰ Huisman, C. et al, Royal HaskoningDHV Report for Province of South Holland, 2021, Final report on Circular Trading Platforms, [In Dutch] Available at: Eindrapportage-Circulaire-Handelsplatformen-Royal-HaskoningDHV.pdf (zuid-holland.nl)

²⁰¹ Transition Agenda for Plastics Industry, 2018, [In Dutch], Available: pdf (overheid.nl)

²⁰² Huisman, C. et al, Royal HaskoningDHV Report for Province of South Holland, 2021, Final report on Circular Trading Platforms, [In Dutch], Available at: Eindrapportage-Circulaire-Handelsplatformen-Royal-HaskoningDHV.pdf (zuid-holland.nl)

²⁰³ Government of Netherlands, 2023, National Circular Economy Program, Available at: National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 | Policy paper | Rijksoverheid.nl

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sharer and network builder is put forward²⁰⁴. This facilitator role is important in the privileged approach that focuses on clusters, value chains and network collaboration. The regional public authorities are considered as a ‘conversation starter’, in which the companies are then expected to continue to activities on their own terms.

Further, the local and regional authorities are also considered on their own right, besides their role to support businesses. For instance, the NCEP refers to an explorative process whereby many government levels will decide whether there is a need for a support mechanism similar to the Acceleration House but working with LRAs instead of businesses²⁰⁵. Similarly, a ‘Community of Practice’ is envisaged to be set up by the provincial government engaging with municipalities which would facilitate to exchange knowledge and practices among the provinces and municipal level²⁰⁶.

Flanders-France Overview

Haut-de-France is the third territory within the Flanders region hosting the clusters identified in the analysis. It is one of the thirteen administrative regions of France sharing a border with Belgium. France is a decentralised unitary state with three sub-national levels: regions, departments, and municipalities. While only the national level has the power to make regulations, regions have competence on many policy fields including regional land planning, sustainable development, economic development, and environment (air quality, waste management, rural and urban development)²⁰⁷ as to translate the national legislation into regional implementation.

We focused our research on the region, with complementary information from the relevant sources on the two main cities within the cluster: Dunkirk and Lille.

Policies specifically targeting IS and/or I-US and their origin

The policy at national level is translated into different regional plans and strategies. Different policy fields such as environment, industrial development and employment integrate a common vision of sustainability. Circular economy is considered an important pathway to address multiple challenges and is mentioned in many different policy documents. Further, industrial symbiosis is mentioned in the following documents under the concept of ‘industrial [and territorial] ecology:

- Circular Economy Action Plan (2019, National)
- Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Hauts-de-France 2024-2027 (Regional)
- Waste Management and Prevention Plan for Haut-de-France (2019, Regional)
- Strategy for economic development, innovation, and cross-border relations 2022-2028 (Regional)
- Regional Scheme Planning, Sustainable Development and Territorial Equality 2020-2030 (Regional)

²⁰⁴ Province of South Holland, On the way to a circular South Holland, Website. [In Dutch], Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: Home - Construction - South Holland (zuid-holland.nl)

²⁰⁵ Government of Netherlands, 2023, National Circular Economy Program, Available at: National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 | Policy paper | Rijksoverheid.nl

²⁰⁶ The Province of South Holland, 2023, Updated Circular Economy Strategy 2023-2023 [In Dutch], Available: Strategie+'Samen+bouwen+aan+een+Circulair+Zuid-Holland' (notubiz.nl)

²⁰⁷ 'Division of Powers Portal | Committee of the Regions, [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: CoR - France Introduction (europa.eu)

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- Climate Strategy for Haut-de-France 2023-2040 (Regional)
- Lille Circular Economy Strategy (2022-2026) (Local)

Industrial symbiosis is therefore within the policy landscape and according to the government, supported in a *'structural way'*²⁰⁸. Further, the policy is supported through a variety of initiatives in the implementation process. These are explained further below.

Main Actors with work relevant for industrial-urban symbiosis

The following ministries are the most relevant for initiatives related to IS and I-US at national level:

- Ministry for an Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion (on energy, territorial cohesion, sustainability, transport and related infrastructure, environment)
- Ministry of Economy, Finance and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty (on industrial policy, competitiveness and innovation)
- Ministry for Higher Education and Research (on education and skills, research and innovation for sustainable development, energy transition and other strategic priorities)
- Transversal governance entities working with all relevant ministries such as the National Circular Economy Council²⁰⁹, National Council on Ecological Transition²¹⁰ and the General Commissioner for Sustainable Development²¹¹, among other things they coordinate the work between diverse stakeholders, including public authorities, civil society, and businesses.

ADEME (The French Agency for Ecological Transition) is a central actor worth mentioning. The public agency plays an important role in creating and disseminating knowledge about sustainability topics, connecting networks, and supporting research²¹². It is financing important initiatives for IS and I-US, such as the Synapse Network and the ELIPSE Tool, explained below under support instruments²¹³.

Other important entities include OREE (Association of enterprises, territories, and environment) and the Circular Economy Institute which gathers diverse stakeholders, including regions. Haut-de-France does not appear to be a member of the latter²¹⁴ but certain actors from the region are member of the former network²¹⁵.

²⁰⁸ Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion | February 7, 2019, 'What is industrial and territorial ecology?', [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/lecologie-industrielle-et-territoriale>

²⁰⁹ Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion | March 24, 2024, 'National Circular Economy Council', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/conseil-national-leconomie-circulaire>

²¹⁰ Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion | March 5, 2024, 'National Ecological Transition Council', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/cnte>

²¹¹ Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion | November 17, 2023, 'National Circular Economy Council', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/commissariat-general-au-developpement-durable-cgdd>

²¹² The French Agency for Ecological Transition, Our organisation, [online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.ademe.fr/en/ademe-the-french-ecological-transition-agency/our-organisation/>

²¹³ Synapse Network, FAQ, [In French], [Online] Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.reseau-synapse.org/static/h/questions-frequentes-faq.html>

²¹⁴ National Circular Economy Institute, Full list of members, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://institut-economie-circulaire.fr/membres/>

²¹⁵ OREE, List of Members, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: http://www.oree.org/collectivites-gestionnaires.html#article_2511

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At regional level, the following actors are relevant:

- DREAL (Regional Directorate for Environment; land planning and housing) Haut-de-France (energy, climate, land planning, transport and its infrastructures, sustainable transition)²¹⁶
- DREETS (Regional Directorate for economy, work and employment and solidarity)²¹⁷
- Chamber of Commerce and Industry²¹⁸ (CCI) which is a network of business associations in Haut de France
- Innovation and Development Agency of Haut-de-France
- Others such as the Synapse Network, OREE and ECOPAL as support structures, usually financed/supported by the regional authorities or the industrial stakeholders

Funding mechanisms and other support instruments

Big lines of funding: greening and decarbonising the industry

The most important sources of funding for initiatives related to IS and I-US come from the EU, as well as national and regional funding. France is an important beneficiary of ERDF, with 9€ billion, European Social Fund with 6,7€ billion and the Just Transition fund with 1€ billion for 2021-2027 period²¹⁹. The cross-border aspect of the ERDF is worth mentioning due to the cluster's international composition. For instance, one of the programs include Flanders (BE) and Haut de France, as well as Wallonia (BE)²²⁰ with a total budget of 416M€ for 201-2027. Another one includes all three regions of the Flanders cluster: the North Sea, with a total budget of 280€ million for the same time²²¹. Further, due to its economic and industrial profile, Haut-de-France qualifies for the Just Transition Fund (JTF). The region receives the highest amount among the six JTF regions in France with 325M€²²². These funding instruments are potentially useful to encourage IS and I-US projects, however due to a lack of specific earmarking for IS or I-US within the thematic objectives of these programs, it is not possible to have a more specific overview without going to project level.

Haut-de-France in national and regional policy: making the leap to revive the industry

The EU funds are used in conjunction with the regional programs. In this regard, the Resilience and Recovery Funds are important. The overarching strategic vision of RRF in Haut-de-France fits well with

²¹⁶ Regional Prefect of Haut-de-France, 'Regional Directorate of Environment, Land Planning and Housing', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.hauts-de-france.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/>

²¹⁷ Regional Prefect of Haut-de-France, 'Regional Directorate of Economy, Employment, Work and Solidarity' [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://hauts-de-france.dreets.gouv.fr/La-DREETS-Hauts-de-France>

²¹⁸ Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Haut-de-France, [Website] [In French]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://hautsdefrance.cci.fr/>

²¹⁹ Europe in France, 'European Funds 2021-2027', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 11, 2024. Available: <https://www.europe-en-france.gouv.fr/fr/fonds-europeens>

²²⁰ Europe in France, 'Interreg Programs: European territorial cooperation in France 2021-2027', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.europe-en-france.gouv.fr/fr/programmes-europeens/les-programmes-interreg-2021-2027-la-cooperation-territoriale-europeenne-en-france>

²²¹ Europe in France, 'European Programs', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.europe-en-france.gouv.fr/fr/programmes-europeens>

²²² Europe in France, 'European Funds for Just Transition', [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.europe-en-france.gouv.fr/fr/fonds-europeens/fonds-europeen-pour-une-transition-juste>

the opportunities that IS and I-US present, namely the axis combining sustainability and reinventing of a competitive industry through innovation. For instance, in Haut de France, the funding available from RRF has been used by 30 businesses under the thematic 'ecology' and sub-thematic 'decarbonisation of the industry' amounting to an investment of 600M€. Further, under the thematic 'competitiveness' and sub-thematic 'support to industrial projects in the territories', 800M€ was awarded to different projects²²³.

There are many other funding instruments available which are potentially relevant for IS and I-US projects. In line with the above and similar to other countries analysed in the report, this entails a sustainable, competitive, and innovative industry. It is not possible to provide an exhaustive list, however the following can be mentioned as the most important examples:

- **The regional funding stemming from the France 2030 program launched in 2021, replacing the previous 'Future investments Program'.** France 2030 is a national investment program in the line of French Recovery Plan, with a budget of 54€ billion over five years. Its main ambition is to realise the leap for the French industry of tomorrow, which is innovative, sustainable, and therefore competitive²²⁴. France 2030 is implemented at regional level with joint national/regional investment. 500M€ is earmarked for projects to encourage regional industrial competitiveness²²⁵. In Haut-de-France, the funding mobilised was around 58M€ between 2022-2025²²⁶. These are used to support innovative character of businesses of all sizes in the region. For instance, under the pillar 'Innovation Projects' businesses can receive up to 500K€ and up to 50% of the costs of the project. This funding can be used for IS related projects since one of the priority objectives is 'circular economy and new functionalities for materials'²²⁷. The funding is dispersed through various channels, including BPI France (support and investment bank for companies)²²⁸.
- **The Industrial Territories Programme, launched in 2018** with the main ambition of supporting the 'reindustrialisation' of the French regions. This program invested around 2€ billion during its first phase in various projects²²⁹. Currently in its second phase, running from 2023 to 2027²³⁰, it has a total budget of 100M€²³¹ and is aligned with the ambitions of the Law on

²²³ Ministry of Economy, Finances and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty, Progress of use for the Recovery Funds for France, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Tableau de bord | economie.gouv.fr](#)

²²⁴ Ministry of Economy, Finances and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty, France 2030: An Investment Plan for France, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.economie.gouv.fr/france-2030#>

²²⁵ The French Government, At the heart of territories, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Au cœur des territoires - France 2030 | info.gouv.fr](#)

²²⁶ Region of Haut-de-France, France 2030 : Acting together for innovation in Haut-de-France, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [France 2030 : agir ensemble pour l'innovation en Hauts-de-France - Région Hauts-de-France \(hautsdefrance.fr\)](#)

²²⁷ Préfecture of Haut-de-France, Call for Innovation Projects, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Projets d'Innovation - France 2030 - Hauts-de-France \(hautsdefrance.fr\)](#)

²²⁸ BPIFrance, Our Mission, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Notre mission | Bpifrance](#)

²²⁹ Bank of Regions, Regions of Industry: an initiative for accelerating industrial development, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Territoires d'industrie | Banque des Territoires](#)

²³⁰ Ministry of Economy, Finances and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty, Regions of Industry, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Territoires d'industrie | entreprises.gouv.fr](#)

²³¹ Ministry of Economy, Finances and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty, Regions of Industry: Launch of 2nd phase: 2023-2027, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Territoires d'industrie : lancement du temps II 2023-2027 | entreprises.gouv.fr](#)

Green Industry adopted in 2023²³². Industrial Ecology (therefore industrial symbiosis) is mentioned as one of the components of the program.

- **The Innovation Territories Programme**²³³, linked to the 3rd wave of the Future Investments Program mentioned above (2017-2021). The program has a budget of 450M€ of which 150M€ in subsidies and 300M€ proper funding to be invested over 15 years. One of the projects is located in Dunkirk, namely Dunkirk Creative Energy. The latter is one of the 24 projects selected for the programme²³⁴. It gathers 70 stakeholders ranging from municipalities to businesses and universities, working on 15 initiatives to ‘transform the Dunkirk territory’²³⁵. One of them is the ‘Heat Highway’, which will provide the necessary infrastructure to collect, distribute and use of residual heat between Arcelor Mittal²³⁶, the hospital, residences and other buildings within a given radius²³⁷.
- **Regional Funds for Accelerating the 3rd Industrial Revolution (FRATRI)**²³⁸: targeting businesses, public authorities, and associations, FRATRI provides financial support to many phases of project development. The objectives are threefold: decarbonisation of the territory, development of circular economy and new modes of production and consumption and stakeholder engagement for the transition. Under the third pillar, IS is mentioned explicitly as the second priority. The total budget for 2021-2027 is 84M€²³⁹.

Further, the Innovation and Development Agency of Haut-de-France provides an overview of the funding used by the businesses of the region. It is possible to monitor the use of funds by priority thanks to the alignment of the data collected by the innovation agency and the policy objectives. For instance, in 2022, 57 companies located in the region raised funding amounting to 1.2€ billion via 57 projects. Eight of these are within the **materials theme** with 28€ million²⁴⁰. It is not clear which funding programs described above are the source of these funding.

Other support instruments and initiatives

Apart from financing, there are many support instruments available, directly targeting IS and I-US or offering support to the companies in transition to circular economy as well competitiveness in general. Most of these support mechanisms are aligned and/or work in tandem with the funding instruments provided by the same institutions.

²³² French Government, 2023, Press Kit: Green Industry, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [DP_presentation_PJL_industrie_verte.pdf \(economie.gouv.fr\)](#)

²³³ Bank of Regions, Regions of Innovation: Supporting the innovative potential of regional actors, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.banquedesterritoires.fr/territoires-dinnovation>

²³⁴ Dunkirk Energy Creative, About us, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Dunkerque l'énergie créative - Territoire d'innovation \(dk-energie-creative.fr\)](#)

²³⁵ Dunkirk Energy Creative, About us, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Dunkerque l'énergie créative - Territoire d'innovation \(dk-energie-creative.fr\)](#)

²³⁶ One of the biggest producers of steel in Europe, located (among others) in Dunkirk.

²³⁷ Dunkirk Energy Creative, Heat Highway Project, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Dunkerque l'énergie créative - Autoroute de la chaleur \(dk-energie-creative.fr\)](#)

²³⁸ REV3, Funds FRATRI, [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://rev3.hautsdefrance.fr/dispositif/fratri/>

²³⁹ REV3, Funds FRATRI, [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://rev3.hautsdefrance.fr/dispositif/fratri/>

²⁴⁰ Innovation and Development Agency of Haut-de-France, Overview of Use of Funds, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Baromètres des levées de fonds 2022 en région Hauts-de-France - Hauts-de-France Innovation Développement \(hautsdefrance-id.fr\)](#)

Support instruments directly targeting IS and I-US initiatives go up to 2009 with the first explorative studies such as Project Comethe. This project, launched by the French National Research Agency in 2008 and coordinated by OREE, provided a toolbox for those interested in exploring, developing, and implementing an IS project. Dunkirk was one of the five pilot territories²⁴¹. Since then, other initiatives have seen the day which pursue similar ambitions:

- **National program of inter-company synergies (2015-2017):** identified opportunities of IS and I-US in four regions of France, however Haut-de-France is not included²⁴².
- **ACTIF**, also at national level, operates as a platform that lists offers and demands from different economic actors to facilitate the identification of IS opportunities. It was launched by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry in 2013. It has a dedicated section for local and regional authorities (e.g. Municipalities, port authorities, industrial parks) facilitating exchanges between relevant actors²⁴³.
- **ELIPSE tool** is a national level directory for IS projects launched in 2016. It lists projects in each region which are added by the project holders by maturity level²⁴⁴. This tool was developed by OREE, the association mentioned in the previous section.
- **The Synapse Network**, launched in 2017 seems to be the latest of the IS-related initiatives. Operating at national level, it is designed for facilitators of IS whether they are from the public or private networks. First of all, it has a platform where diverse stakeholders can connect and see listed IS initiatives. Second, it helps with peer-to-peer exchanges, knowledge and tools and dissemination of learnings and outcomes to facilitate replication. Different levels of IS development is recognised and services are adopted to the beginners, those who already have an IS initiative in the making or those who want to evaluate or make their initiative economically sustainable. The website of Synapse Network includes information on upcoming financing opportunities, relevant events, and tools²⁴⁵.
- **TOILE Industrielle (Industrial Canvas)** at regional level helps identifying material flows and possible synergies between the businesses of the territory and beyond in the Flanders territory. As such it presents an important entry point for cross-border exchanges as well. This tool was developed by the Flanders-Dunkirk Urbanism Agency around 2018 but seems to be inactive at the moment²⁴⁶.
- **Competitiveness Clusters of Haut-de-France**, which brings together economic operators, training centres and research actors that are located in a given geographical location working in the same sector/value chain or market. This creates synergies between them to 'grow

²⁴¹ Comethe Project Website, Overview of Dunkirk Pilot Territory, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: http://www.comethe.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=78&Itemid=68

²⁴² National Circular Economy Institute, National Inter-companies Synergies Program: 10 Initiatives. [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://institut-economie-circulaire.fr/programme-national-de-synergies-inter-entreprises-10-initiatives-de-synergies-inter-entreprises/>

²⁴³ ACTIF, The Circular Economy Platform: Stimulating the Resource Exchanges between the industries of the region, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://actif-cci.fr/>

²⁴⁴ OREE, Website for the ELIPSE (Evaluation of IS initiatives) TOOL, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Orée - Page d'accueil \(referentiel-elipse-eit.org\)](http://oree.fr/page-daccueil-referentiel-elipse-eit.org)

²⁴⁵ National Network of Industrial and Territorial Ecology Actors (SYNAPSE), Website, [In French], Accessed: June 12, 2024. <https://www.reseau-synapse.org/>

²⁴⁶ Flanders Dunkirk Urbanism Agency, La Toile : A tool at the service of synergies and territorial development, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [Agence d'urbanisme Flandre-Dunkerque - Agur Dunkerque \(agur-dunkerque.org\)](http://agence-urbanisme-flandre-dunkerque-agur-dunkerque.org)

together’, constituting an important entry point to build on for IS projects²⁴⁷. In the region, there are seven clusters, among which the following is potentially important for IS and I-US: TEAM2 (recycling, valorisation technologies for diverse streams as well as recyclability of materials)²⁴⁸. One of its five pillars, ‘innovative circular loops’ is directly targeting IS with the following objective: development of IS platforms²⁴⁹. Another cluster, EuraMaterials, working with industries using materials such as textile, plastics and composites, glass, carton and cellulose. It offers services such as project development, incubation, and identification of funding for innovative projects²⁵⁰.

- Another important dimension to mention is at local level, due to the specific characteristics of the Dunkirk port, which is historically associated with the beginnings of IS. One example is the **ECOPAL, specialising in IS in the Dunkirk port area**. It is an industry-led initiative partially funded by the local authorities, namely the Region, ADEME and the Urban Community of Dunkirk. Its main goal is to identify IS opportunities for the members and to support them to connect to these opportunities²⁵¹.

²⁴⁷ Ministry of Higher Education and Research, Competitiveness Clusters of Haut-de-France, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr/les-poles-de-competitivite-en-hauts-de-france-45875>

²⁴⁸ Team2, The Five Strategic Domains of Activity, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: TEAM2 - les 5 Domaines d'Activités Stratégiques de TEAM2

²⁴⁹ Team2, The Five Strategic Domains of Activity: Innovative Circular Economy Loops, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: TEAM2 - Boucles innovantes d'économie circulaire

²⁵⁰ EuraMaterials, Our Support Services, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: Nos services d'accompagnement – EuraMaterials

²⁵¹ Ecopal, About the Association, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: L'association - Ecopal

The following are the more general support instruments and are potentially relevant for IS and I-US projects:

- **Sustainable Development Resource Centre (Regional):** is a support structure for the regional actors both public and private, through analysis, networking, knowledge dissemination organisation of events and workshops. Two of its four working themes are potentially relevant for IS and I-US: new economic models aligned with the 3rd industrial revolution in Haut-de-France and energy transition and climate change²⁵².
- **Regional Innovation and Development Agency** supports innovative companies and start-ups in line with the regional and national objectives. It provides support for creation of businesses, networking opportunities and encouraging regional research networks²⁵³.
- **REV3**, initiated by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry (CCI) and regional authorities, REV3 is a network of actors working towards sustainability in the region. Four of its six thematic priorities are relevant for IS and I-US: energy mix, decarbonisation, bioeconomy and agriculture and circular economy²⁵⁴. Along with providing a space for exchange, REV3 support SMEs through various tools (such as a baseline analysis of operations), organises trainings and workshops and inform and support applications to some of the fundings available²⁵⁵.
- **Reseau Astride** is a collaborative platform for the stakeholders active within the economic landscape of Haut-de-France. It connects these actors for exchange of information and knowledge²⁵⁶.

A critical reading of the policy

General context

As mentioned throughout this section, the policy strategy aims at turning the challenges into new opportunities for the renewal of industry in France and in Haut-de-France. The context in the region makes this even more relevant; Haut-de-France is bearing the negative impacts of deindustrialisation of France. It has the second lowest income per capita in the country as well as lower educational attainment²⁵⁷. Circular economy fits perfectly with this regional vision of ‘third industrial revolution’, promising to reconcile economic, social, and environmental ambitions, while filling the competitiveness gap for the industry.

Industrial symbiosis: reindustrialisation of the region through innovation

Against this background, IS and I-US are recognised as important levers to achieve the multiple objectives of climate neutrality, less dependence on raw materials and prosperity through re-industrialisation. It is mentioned in many policy documents: the National CEAP underlines its

²⁵² Sustainable Development and Resource Centre, Our mission, Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: Le Cerdd et ses missions / Le Cerdd, qui sommes-nous ? - Centre Ressource du Développement Durable

²⁵³ Regional Development and Innovation Agency of Haut-de-France, About Us, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: L'agence - Hauts-de-France Innovation Développement (hautsdefrance-id.fr)

²⁵⁴ REV3, For a connected and sustainable economy, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 13, 2024. Available: <https://rev3.hautsdefrance.fr/rev3-economie-durable-connectee/>

²⁵⁵ REV3, Support Mechanisms, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://rev3.hautsdefrance.fr/accompagnements/>

²⁵⁶ ASTRIDE, Web Application, [In French], Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: ASTRIDE - Connexion

²⁵⁷ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Plan for Planning, Sustainable Development and Territorial Equality (SRADDET), [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: La Région adopte son SRADDET - Région Hauts-de-France (hautsdefrance.fr)

importance and lays out mechanisms through which it will be supported. This is in turn reflected in other policy documents from national to regional. Almost all other main policy documents at regional level also mention IS, either as ambition in itself (e.g. Waste Management and Prevention Plan for Haut de France) or a pathway for the modernisation of the industry (Regional Scheme for Planning, Sustainable Development and Territorial Equality, Climate and Energy Strategy of Haut-de-France). Others underline the importance of embedding the principles of IS in the relevant policy areas (Regional Strategy for economic development, innovation, and cross-border relations) or consider IS as a way to reduce industrial waste (Waste Management and Prevention Plan for Haut de France) or move towards sustainable energy production. For the latter, there is a target of 775 Gwh/year of energy production from residual heat from the industrial processes and solar energy²⁵⁸.

These strategic considerations are supported through a multitude of policy tools. The main examples include integrating the principle of IS into regional policy documents, providing support to exchange of materials, coordination of actors in diverse sectors and value chains²⁵⁹. Addressing the issues related to end-of waste is also mentioned²⁶⁰, which is an important barrier to IS and I-US. There are multiple mentions to 'encouraging IS networks' as well awareness raising and training of professionals²⁶¹. There is also support for companies to analyse their waste streams and identify IS opportunities through the financial and technical instruments mentioned above.

The placed-based, context dependant nature of IS and I-US is also recognised: in some cases, IS is considered an exercise of 'good governance'. In return, good governance and including diverse stakeholders, regions, and local authorities in particular, is seen a pre-condition to building successful IS initiatives.

An understanding of IS and I-US evolving with time

The relative importance given to IS in the policy is partially due to the history of the concept in France dating back to several decades. The country hosts some of the early examples of what can be called a precursor to IS: already in 1962, a thermal powerplant was installed in Dunkirk to use residual heat from the processes of ArcelorMittal (known as Usino at the date), a steel producer²⁶². Research found other examples of IS projects dating to 1999, also in Dunkirk²⁶³. For the post-2000 period, the Synapse Network provides an overview of the development of IS and I-US in the country: the explorative period between 2009-2014 with the Comethe project mentioned above, the experimentation period between 2015-2017 when ELIPSE and ACTIF have seen the day, the period of implementation and tackling the barriers between 2018-2020 with the Synapse Network and finally, a more structural, supportive

²⁵⁸ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Plan for Planning, Sustainable Development and Territorial Equality (SRADDET), [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: La Région adopte son SRADDET - Région Hauts-de-France (hautsdefrance.fr)

²⁵⁹ Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Coherence, 2019, National Circular Economy Plan: 50 Actions, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: Feuille-de-route-Economie-circulaire-50-mesures-pour-economie-100-circulaire.pdf (ecologie.gouv.fr)

²⁶⁰ Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Coherence, 2019, National Circular Economy Plan: 50 Actions, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: Feuille-de-route-Economie-circulaire-50-mesures-pour-economie-100-circulaire.pdf (ecologie.gouv.fr)

²⁶¹ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Plan for Planning, Sustainable Development and Territorial Equality (SRADDET), [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: La Région adopte son SRADDET - Région Hauts-de-France (hautsdefrance.fr)

²⁶² Douaran LL, Dunkirk : an example of industrial ecology proving successful, published: 12 February 2021, Les Horizons, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://leshorizons.net/dunkerque-exemple-ecologie-industrielle/>

²⁶³ http://www.comethe.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=78&Itemid=68

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framework pursuing the initiatives between 2021-2024²⁶⁴. This evolution shows an increasing understanding of the barriers to, and opportunities presented by IS and I-US. It is reflected in the support tools provided: for instance, the Comethe Project is considered ‘too slow’ for the ever-changing business landscape as it opted for a full-scale material flow analysis. Therefore, tools such as Synapse seem to have evolved towards a more dynamic approach, giving more space to businesses, and favouring ‘quick decision making’²⁶⁵. This awareness both at national and regional scale provide a good basis to integrate IS and I-US into policies, as can be seen from the documents.

Sectors targeted by the policy documents relevant for IS and U-IS

All sectors identified in the analysis are mentioned in relevant documents, particularly steel, non-ferrous metals, and chemicals. Since Haut-de-France is an important area with important agricultural activity, bioeconomy is also mentioned. The documents such as the regional waste plan provide a detailed overview of the situation in terms of waste generation.

Challenges to IS and I-US

There are very few mentions of barriers to IS and I-US specifically. The following is nevertheless relevant:

- The traditional characteristics of the industry in the region with lack of digital skills and mismatch between educational skills and what is needed for the industry of tomorrow²⁶⁶
- Lack of entrepreneurial spirit²⁶⁷
- Low R&D spending²⁶⁸
- Certain waste streams remain difficult to valorise due to their low quality, difficulties of transport and treatment costs²⁶⁹

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving IS and I-US

Research findings suggest that both at national and sub-national levels, the public authorities play a role of facilitator for IS and I-US related initiatives. The documents underline a willingness to take on the role of ‘conversation starter’ and coordinator²⁷⁰, reaching out to many actors from NGOs to businesses²⁷¹. The support instruments mentioned throughout this document complement this

²⁶⁴ Synapse Network, Deployment of Industrial and Territorial Ecology in France, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.reseau-synapse.org/static/h/deploiement-de-l-eit-en-france.html>

²⁶⁵ Synapse Network, Deployment of Industrial and Territorial Ecology in France, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: <https://www.reseau-synapse.org/static/h/deploiement-de-l-eit-en-france.html>

²⁶⁶ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) 2021-2027, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [s3hautsdefrance151220.pdf](#)

²⁶⁷ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) 2021-2027, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [s3hautsdefrance151220.pdf](#)

²⁶⁸ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) 2021-2027, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [s3hautsdefrance151220.pdf](#)

²⁶⁹ Haut-de-France Region, 2019, Regional Waste Management and Prevention Plan, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [La Région vote un plan d'action pour aller vers le zéro déchet - Région Hauts-de-France \(hautsdefrance.fr\)](#)

²⁷⁰ Haut-de-France Region, 2019, Regional Waste Management and Prevention Plan, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [La Région vote un plan d'action pour aller vers le zéro déchet - Région Hauts-de-France \(hautsdefrance.fr\)](#)

²⁷¹ Haut-de-France Region, 2019, Regional Waste Management and Prevention Plan, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: [La Région vote un plan d'action pour aller vers le zéro déchet - Région Hauts-de-France \(hautsdefrance.fr\)](#)

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facilitation role in concrete ways, including exchange platforms, technical analysis support²⁷² and anticipating changes to the regulatory framework to help impacted stakeholders²⁷³.

Further, the collaboration between the industrial stakeholders and the public authorities are seen as indispensable to create new value chains²⁷⁴. As such, while public authorities fulfil a facilitation role, industrial stakeholders are expected to respond and take on the leading role.

The third dimension is the relationship between the national and sub-national levels and the hierarchy of norms. The policy making process integrate the overarching visions into the regional policy ensuring each policy document respect certain lines and is coherent with the whole²⁷⁵. This however is couple with the consideration of the unique characteristics and needs of each region. This is also why the policy recognises the territorial dimension and considers the regions [*collectivités* in French] indispensable in the transition process.

²⁷² Regional Strategy for economic development, innovation and cross-border relations

²⁷³ Haut-de-France Region, 2019, Regional Waste Management and Prevention Plan, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: La Région vote un plan d'action pour aller vers le zéro déchet - Région Hauts-de-France (hautsdefrance.fr)

²⁷⁴ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Strategy for economic development, innovation and internationalisation 2022-2028, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: Schéma Régional de Développement Économique, d'Innovation et d'Internationalisation - La stratégie économique des Hauts-de-France pour la période 2022-2028 - Hauts-de-France Entreprises (hautsdefrance.fr)

²⁷⁵ Haut-de-France Region, Regional Strategy for economic development, innovation and internationalisation 2022-2028, [In French], [Online]. Accessed: June 12, 2024. Available: Schéma Régional de Développement Économique, d'Innovation et d'Internationalisation - La stratégie économique des Hauts-de-France pour la période 2022-2028 - Hauts-de-France Entreprises (hautsdefrance.fr)

4.3. I-US potential analysis

4.3.1. Material flows mapping

Industrial Waste Generation

The material flows analysis was conducted using the E-PRTR database. Figure 16 and Figure 17 respectively illustrate the total and disposed industrial waste flows in the Flanders region. Each year, 44.4 Mtons of waste are generated in the region, 14.2 Mtons of which is disposed. Without considering the waste treatment and disposal sectors, sewerage is the main emitting sector with an amount of waste of 1.13 Mtons/year (2.6% of total waste). The next biggest emitting sectors are manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys, construction of roads and motorways, processing and preserving of potatoes and manufacture of other organic basic chemicals. These five sectors represent around 11.6% of the total waste flows on the territory, and when adding the waste treatment and disposal sector waste flows, then 81.5% of the regional flows are accounted for.

Regarding the disposed waste, sewerage treatment is still one of the most emitting sectors with 0.7 Mtons of disposed waste (4.9% of the total disposed waste), meaning landfilled, buried, or incinerated without energy recovery. Then, 0.46 and 0.22 Mtons are disposed respectively by the manufacture of other organic and inorganic chemicals (3.2 and 1.5% of total disposed waste). The Figure 18 illustrates all the waste flows in the area and their sectorial distribution.

The following maps show that the waste flows are highly concentrated in port areas such as Rotterdam, Antwerpen or Gent. In contrast, the Lille/Courtrai/Roulers cluster illustrated Figure 16 and surrounding areas show a higher concentration of industrial sites but with less waste generation.

Figure 16: Total waste flows in the Flander region.

Figure 17: Disposed waste flows in the Flanders region.

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Figure 18: Waste flow diagram and waste sectorial analysis in the Flanders region (quantities in kt/year in the table, icons from icons8.com)

I-US Flow Mapping

The table below shows the main sectors responsible for waste material flows in the Flanders region. Waste processing companies have been discounted from this analysis, as although required actors in managing the flows of waste, the data in its current form prevents us from having a complete understanding of what these waste processes and associated materials are specifically, and therefore their potential end uses. This is not an issue with the other sectoral waste streams as we can use ISL experience of IS delivery globally to list typical associated resource flows against each specific sector.

Significant volumes of waste can be seen to be going into recovery operations which is likely to inhibit its commercial availability for industrial symbiosis synergies as it will have lower associated rates of cost (no landfill tax). The largest area of potential opportunity is the relatively high volume of sewage treatment material going to disposal and not to recovery activities, where energy recovery is a widely implemented solution in a number of counties for sewage treatment solids.

Table 5 Primary Waste Flow Data for Flanders

NACE sector	Waste destined for disposal (t/year)	Waste destined for recovery (t/year)	Total of waste (t/y)
Sewerage	6,993,689	432,865	1,132,234
Recovery of sorted materials	515,452	3,825,601	4,341,053
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	457,800	429,771	887,571
Remediation activities and other waste management services	321,842	435,018	756,860
Manufacture of other inorganic basic chemicals	218,532	26,498	245,030
Treatment and disposal of hazardous waste	195,690	1,491,588	1,687,278
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	99,076	346,052	445,128
Manufacture of refined petroleum products	89,142	262,267	351,409
Freight transport by road	82,592	230,348	312940
Treatment and coating of metals	70,375	116,100	186,475
Lead, zinc and tin production	65,244	4,547	69,791
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys	60,650	1,029,198	1,089,848
Manufacture of dyes and pigments	51,686	3,191	54,877

The priority sectors with the most significant waste volumes going to disposal have been identified as:

- Sewerage Treatment
- Manufacture of steel, iron and ferro alloys
- Construction
- Processing & preserving of potatoes
- Basic Organic chemicals

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- Sugar manufacture
- Repair and maintenance of ships and boats

The following table outlines the main resources associated with each of the priority sectors. Although the granularity of data is a little lacking, with knowledge of the priority sectors in Flanders, it is still possible to produce a list of the typical byproducts and wastes arising from each sector. This still represents a sufficient overview of the opportunity present to allow a mapping of synergistic opportunities across sectors.

The following resources have been identified for each priority sector in turn.

Table 6 Flanders Region Priority Sector Flow Analysis

Sector	No. of sites	Outputs /By-products
Sewerage	78	Sludges
		Treated effluent
		Biosolids
		Mixed Plastics
		Contaminated paper
Manufacture of steel, iron, and ferro-alloys	25	Slag
		Mill scale
		Dust (Zinc rich)
		Process gases and steam
		Scrap metal
Construction of roads and motorways	12	Excavation soil
		Asphalt and concrete
		Demolition waste
		Excess building materials
Processing and preserving of potatoes	15	Peelings and trimmings
		Starch
		Vegetable pulp
		Waste cooking oil
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	68	Chemical residues
Manufacture of sugar	10	Bagasse
		Molasses

		Press Mud
		Beet pulp
Repair and maintenance of ships and boats	11	Scrap metal
		Paint and coatings
		Oil and lubricants
		Fibreglass
		Wood
Electricity generation	58	Although a significant sector Electricity generation in Flanders is predominantly nuclear which precludes it from significant IS opportunity

4.3.2. I-US Infrastructure Mapping

Figure 19, Figure 20 and Figure 21 illustrate the key infrastructure for I-US in the Flanders region.

In terms of transport infrastructures, the region has 3900 km (0.12 km/km²) of motorways and around 12 000 km (0.37 km/km²) of railways. For the energy infrastructures, 45 and 34% of the electricity are produced from nuclear and gas plants respectively while coal (11%), wind (5%), biomass (2%), waste (1%), solar (1%) and oil (1%) share the rest of the mix. Using modelling data from the HRE4 project, 92.3 PJ/year and 20.0 PJ/year of excess heat from respectively industrial sites and WWTP have been identified. For the heat demands, urban area would consume around 359.9 PJ/year. Regarding the education, 35 universities (science and technical schools) are in the region. The region also shows a high innovation appeal with 9 I-US demo cases:

- [ENGIE](#)
- [C2FUEL](#)
- [C4U](#)
- [INITIATE](#)
- [Torero](#)
- [RecHycle](#)
- [Holland Hydrogen](#)
- [MultiPLHY](#)
- [UNIPER](#)

Figure 19: Transport infrastructures in the Flanders region.

Figure 20: Electricity production and excess heat in the Flanders region (icons from icons8.com).

Figure 21 : Education and innovation in the Flanders region (icons from icons8.com).

4.3.3. Regional readiness assessment for I-US and general conclusions

The following table outlines the main industrial symbiosis synergy opportunities available for each identified resource (from the analysis in section 4.3.1).

Table 7 Industrial Symbiosis Opportunities in Flanders

Sector	Outputs /By-products	Uses
Sewerage	Sludges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anaerobic Digestion - Biogas for heat/ energy / fuel Agriculture – soil conditioner and fertilizer.
	Treated effluent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrigation - (crops, landscaping, golf courses)
	Biosolids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture - soil conditioner and fertilizer Land reclamation – restoration of degraded soils.
Manufacture of steel, iron, and ferro-alloys	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – aggregate and cement substitute Agriculture – soil amendment Marine – coral reef repair and construction
	Mill scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Iron recovery or substitute for virgin iron ore
	Dust (Zinc rich)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metal recovery and recycling
	Process gases and steam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Power or steam generation Heat recovery Fuel
	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle / re-use Feedstock for furnace
Construction of roads and motorways	Excavation soil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction Landscaping & land remediation
	Asphalt and concrete	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction
	Demolition waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction
Processing and preserving of potatoes	Peelings and trimmings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture - animal feed and compost Anaerobic Digestion - biogas production Food Industry (i.e. powdered potato flakes)
	Starch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Starch recovery and reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - plastic packaging - food industry - thickener
	Pulp	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture - animal feed and compost Anaerobic Digestion - biogas production Food Industry (i.e. soups, sauces, baked goods)

	Used cooking oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuel alternative – biodiesel • Chemical - bio-based chemicals, soap / detergent • Industrial lubricants
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	Chemical residues Carbon dioxide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical sector • Energy recovery • Agriculture/horticulture • Food and drink
Manufacture of sugar	Bagasse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biofuel - energy generation • Bioplastics • Pulp and paper production • Agriculture - animal feed and composting • Waste water - adsorbent for heavy metal removal
	Molasses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anaerobic Digestion - biogas • Ethanol production • Binding agent - Steel and coal briquettes • Bioremediation • Agriculture - liquid fertiliser • Food & Drink - yeast and flavourings
	Press Mud	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture - animal feed, soil amendment, fertiliser, composting • Anaerobic digestion - biogas and energy production • Fish feed
	Beet pulp	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture - animal feed and compost • Anaerobic digestion - biogas and energy production • Biodegradable packaging • Bioethanol • Paper and fibrous products
Repair and maintenance of ships and boats	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle / re-use • Feedstock for furnace
	Paint and coatings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy recovery
	Oil and lubricants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oil & Solvent recovery • Energy recovery
	Fibreglass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement manufacture
	Wood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Furniture manufacture • Biomass pellets
Electricity generation	<p><i>Note; although there is a high number of sites for Electricity Generation, the waste figures are very low. Most of Belgium's electricity is produced by nuclear</i></p>	

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A significant number of synergies present themselves across the priority sectors at a high level with a good balance of high and low value end applications. With some well-established anchor industries in regard to IS and I-US then this means that Flanders has the basic building blocks in place in respect of a good spread of complimentary industrial sectors and resource flows.

In regard to drawing some initial conclusions on Flanders' readiness for industrial symbiosis then we will again use the readiness assessment produced as part of the EU Circlean²⁷⁶ project as a framework.

Awareness of IS and Potential Benefits

Policy analysis has shown that although no specific IS policy is in place in the Netherlands, there is significant enabling policy that will support industrial symbiosis in a number of the priority sectors for Flanders. The French part of the territory has established an IS specific policy already in place. There has been historic funded IS activity across Flanders, particularly regarding the port locations. There are also several significant examples that highlight that industry in the region is already embracing the IS concept, which in turn provides a library of case studies to promote future activity. Some examples of which are provided below:

- North C Methanol Project²⁷⁷, a €140M investment in the North Sea Port development which stretches from Vlissingen to Ghent and has partners such as ArcelorMittal, Mitsubishi Power, and Alco Biofuel. Carbon capture and utilisation technologies are turning CO₂ into methanol, with products such as oxygen, heat and water all being utilised by local partner industries.
- Estener²⁷⁸, located in La Havre, is the first French factory to be producing biodiesel from animal fats which are unsuitable for food production purposes. Taking byproducts from the meat processing sector, the factory produces 70,000 tonnes of base material to produce biofuels.
- Biopark Teneuzen²⁷⁹, also associated with the Netherlands North Sea Port development, but this time with a focus on agri-industrial sustainability. Here the accent is on industrial clustering to foster the use of byproducts and waste as the valued input into another. Examples include Yara (chemical company) providing CO₂, heat, and water to a nearby horticulture business for use in its greenhouses. The biomass material arising from the horticulture operations are then in turn used in energy generation.

²⁷⁶ <https://circlean-symbiosis.eu/the-project/>; accessed April 2024

²⁷⁷ A Sustainable Industrial Symbiosis in Flanders, Accessed June 2024, Available at <https://www.chemanager-online.com/en/news/sustainable-industrial-symbiosis-flanders>

²⁷⁸ Recycling complex fats coming from the agri-alimentary industry in the production of bio-diesel; Accessed June 2024 ; available at: <https://circularports.vlaanderen-circulair.be/portfolio/estener-le-havre/>

²⁷⁹ Biopark represents a new way of thinking to create agro-industrial sustainability ; Accessed June 2024 ; Available at : <https://circularports.vlaanderen-circulair.be/portfolio/biopark-terneuzen-north-sea-port/>

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Initial Ideas of Where a Company Can Engage / Resources suiting IS / Processes Mapped & Targeted for IS

Given the symbiosis examples in existence listed above, along with historical and ongoing symbiotic activity in both the Dutch and French elements of the Flanders region, this provides evidence that some (if limited) mapping of opportunity and resources has been concluded.

In respect to the available resources then flows associated with the food/agri sector, chemical sectors, steel manufacture, construction and energy are present with their well-established symbiotic cases across the world.

Internal Data Sources Identified for Quantification / Resources identified, quantified, and characterised for IS High levels waste data flows have been obtained for the Flanders region, but benefit would be realised through the provision more granular and visible waste data. This would allow businesses to more readily identify the type, quantities, and location of resources available them.

Check Costs, regulations and other technology specifications to be met for IS opportunities

As an EU member state then the necessary regulation and drivers are in place to provide a framework for industrial symbiosis uptake by industry. This is supported by regional policy, particularly in the French territories which make specific mention of industrial symbiosis. Fiscal drivers are in place in the form of landfill tax which will help create the commercial case for synergies.

Resources Prioritised for IS with Industry Buy In / All Resources Quantified and Posted on Matching Tool

A platform for the Dutch part of the Flanders region has been identified in Circular.biz that seeks to convene businesses with an interest in industrial symbiosis. Although not an open access resource platform per se, it does provide a forum for convening interested industry partners.

From the detailed research concluded, and with a number of existing high profile IS cases linked to CO₂ capture and energy production, then Flanders appears to have all the requisite building blocks in place for industrial symbiosis to thrive. This includes a robust policy framework and a strong supporting academic and research infrastructure.

5. Regional analysis: Midlands – United Kingdom

5.1. Local Context

5.1.1. Geographical landscape

The Midlands, centrally located in England, is a region that significantly contributes to the country's geography, economy, and culture. This area blends rural charm with extensive agricultural activities and boasts a wealth of cultural and historical sites reflective of its varied landscape.

Traditionally, the Midlands is divided into the East Midlands and the West Midlands, each possessing unique characteristics and landscapes.

East Midlands

The East Midlands encompasses the counties of Derbyshire, Leicestershire, Lincolnshire, Northamptonshire, Nottinghamshire, and Rutland, covering an area of 15,811 km². Known for its diverse landscapes and spatial development, the region features a mix of urban areas, rolling

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countryside, significant natural landmarks like Sherwood Forest in Nottinghamshire, and fertile agricultural lands in Lincolnshire and Northamptonshire, ideal for crops like wheat, barley, and sugar beet, and livestock grazing in Derbyshire's hills.

Key cities include Derby, Leicester, Lincoln, and Nottingham, while prominent towns are Boston, Chesterfield, Coalville, Corby, Glossop, Grantham, Kettering, Loughborough, Northampton, Mansfield, Oakham, Swadlincote, and Wellingborough.

The highest point, Kinder Scout in the Peak District, reaches 636 meters. The area divides into the White Peak, with its limestone gorges and caves, and the Dark Peak, known for gritstone edges and expansive moorlands. The Lincolnshire Wolds, an Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONB), offers rolling chalk landscapes and fertile agricultural soils, while the southern part of Lincolnshire features the Fens, a flat, fertile agricultural region known for extensive drainage systems.

Major rivers, including the Nene, Soar, Trent, Welland, and Witham, flow through the region, contributing to agriculture and industry. The Trent flows through Nottinghamshire and Derbyshire before entering the West Midlands, while the Witham flows through Lincolnshire, providing picturesque riverside settings.

The region is rich in natural resources, including limestone, coal, ironstone, and the East Midlands Oil Province, which spans across northeastern East Midlands. The Welton oil field is the largest onshore oil field in the UK.

The National Forest, covering 520 km² across north Leicestershire, south Derbyshire, and southeast Staffordshire, aims to blend ancient woodland with new plantings. This initiative stretches from Leicester to Burton upon Trent, linking the ancient forests of Needwood and Charnwood²⁸⁰.

The East Midlands experiences a temperate maritime climate, with moderate rainfall, mild to warm summers, and cool to cold winters.

West Midlands

The West Midlands, the only UK region without a coastline, features extensive canal systems and covers 13,000 km², making it the third smallest English region by area. It borders the North West, East Midlands, South East, South West, and Wales.

The region includes the counties of Herefordshire, Shropshire, Staffordshire, Warwickshire, West Midlands, and Worcestershire. It contrasts bustling cities like Birmingham, Coventry, and Wolverhampton with the rural countryside of Herefordshire and Shropshire²⁸¹. Notable natural areas include the Wyre Forest on the Worcestershire-Shropshire border, one of England's largest ancient woodlands.

The West Midlands has the third largest green belt area (270,000 hectares), accounting for 21% of the region, and includes five Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONBs) – Shropshire Hills, Malvern

²⁸⁰ The National Forest, Explore the Forest, Accessed: June 18, 2024, Available: <https://www.nationalforest.org/explore>

²⁸¹ Portrait of the Regions - UNITED KINGDOM - WEST MIDLANDS - Geography and history, 2004, Accessed: June 18, 2024, Available: https://circabc.europa.eu/webdav/CircaBC/ESTAT/regportraits/Information/ukg_geo.htm

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Hills, Cannock Chase, and parts of Wye Valley and The Cotswolds – covering 127,000 hectares (10% of the region)²⁸². The Peak District National Park extends into Staffordshire.

The highest point is Black Mountain, at 703 meters, in Herefordshire. Predominantly lowland, the region has sandstones, clays, limestone, ironstone, and coal deposits, especially around Birmingham, where the Rivers Stour, Avon (Upper Avon), and Tame drain southward²⁸³. Major rivers include the Severn, the longest river in the UK, flowing through Shropshire and Worcestershire.

The West Midlands' climate varies, with milder, wetter weather in the west and drier, colder conditions in the east. Birmingham, for instance, has a notable annual temperature range, with relatively high summer and low winter temperatures.

5.1.2. Social landscape

The Midlands, comprising the East Midlands and West Midlands, presents a diverse and vibrant social landscape. This region includes various urban centers, rural areas, and cultural communities, contributing significantly to the UK's social fabric.

East Midlands

The East Midlands is home to approximately 4.9 million people, with a population density of 312.4 residents/km²²⁸⁴, making it the region with the second-lowest overall population density in England. The population is spread across urban and rural areas, with significant concentrations in Nottingham, Leicester, Derby, and Lincoln.

Approximately 86% of the population identifies as White British, but urban areas exhibit significant ethnic diversity. Leicester, for example, has a large South Asian community, making it one of the most diverse cities in the UK. Nottingham and Derby also host large Eastern European and African communities.

Residents often identify themselves by county or town, and the region has distinct spoken dialects. In the northern areas like North Nottinghamshire and North Derbyshire, the dialect is more akin to Northern English.

The East Midlands has a balanced age distribution with a significant elderly population (corresponding to 20% of the overall population at the region), especially in rural areas. Cities have younger populations due to universities and colleges. Notable higher education institutions include the University of Nottingham, University of Leicester, and Loughborough University, which drive research and attract international students, significantly contributing to the local economy.

Education levels vary, with urban areas seeing higher rates of higher education attainment. However, the overall effectiveness of schools is below the national average, with about 180,000 pupils attending schools that are not rated as good. It is important to note that urban secondary schools have higher

²⁸² Office for National Statistics, Portrait of the West Midlands, 2011, Accessed: June 18, 2024, Available: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.sustainabilitywestmidlands.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/portraitw_tcm77-2260021.pdf

²⁸³ Britannica, West Midlands, Accessed: June 18, 2024, Available: <https://www.britannica.com/place/West-Midlands>

²⁸⁴ Nomis, East Midlands Region, 2021 Census Area Profile, Accessed: June 14, 2024, Available: https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/sources/census_2021/report?compare=E12000004

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truancy rates compared to the national average, while rural secondary schools tend to be lower than the national average²⁸⁵.

The workforce is concentrated in lower-skilled occupations than the national average, and future growth will require adaptability and re-skilling, as well as maximising the potential of young people entering the labour market²⁸⁶.

The East Midlands counts with numerous hospitals and healthcare facilities operating across the counties, providing comprehensive healthcare services. However, public health challenges include obesity, smoking, and mental health issues, with disparities between urban and rural areas. Initiatives like social prescribing link residents to community services to improve health and wellbeing²⁸⁷.

The region is known for strong community engagement, with numerous local groups, charities, and initiatives fostering social cohesion and support. Despite this, urban areas face social challenges like crime, poverty, and social exclusion.

The region offers a range of housing options but faces affordability and availability issues, especially in cities like Nottingham and Leicester. Thus, the government collaborates with organizations like the East Midlands Mayoral Combined County Authority (MCCA) to address these challenges, as well as to develop capital funding and upfront investment in housing and Net Zero projects.

West Midlands

The West Midlands has a population of about 6 million people, accounting for 11% of England's total population, and a density of 458/km² ²⁸⁸. The population distribution is 49.36% in the West Midlands county, 20.17% in Staffordshire, 10.49% in Worcestershire, 9.91% in Warwickshire, 8.56% in Shropshire, and 3.37% in Herefordshire.

The region is one of the largest urban area outside London and is highly accessible due to its central location and extensive transport networks and international connections. The region is linked to the north and south, east, and west by rail and road networks. It has several motorways serving the area and it is home to the Birmingham International Airport (the second largest airport in England outside of the London area).

The West Midlands is notably ethnically diverse, especially in urban areas, with a significant non-White population. Asian, Asian British, or Asian Welsh individuals make up 13.3% of the population. This multiculturalism is reflected in the region's cultural festivals, religious institutions, and community organizations. Therefore, community centers and local organizations play a pivotal role in fostering social cohesion and supporting marginalized groups.

²⁸⁵ Ofsted, East Midlands regional report, 2014, Accessed: June 14, 2024, Available: chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7f0dd240f0b62305b84c84/Ofsted_Annual_Report_201314_East_Midlands.pdf

²⁸⁶ GOV.UK, East Midlands devolution deal, 2022, Accessed: June 14, 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/east-midlands-devolution-deal/east-midlands-devolution-deal#skills-and-education>

²⁸⁷ Canal & River trust, Social Prescribing in the East Midlands, Accessed: June 14, 2024, Available: <https://canalrivertrust.org.uk/about-us/where-we-work/east-midlands/social-prescribing-in-the-east-midlands>

²⁸⁸ Nomis, West Midlands Region, 2021 Census Area Profile, Accessed: June 17, 2024, Available: https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/sources/census_2021/report?compare=E12000005

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Similar to the East Midlands region, the West Midlands has a growing elderly population, with 19% of the population being between 50 and 64 years old. On the other hand, it has the highest total fertility rate in the UK, at 2.08 births per woman.

The region is the biggest higher education cluster outside London, enjoying several renowned universities like the University of Birmingham, Coventry University, and Aston University, attracting international students (Around 45% of students are from the region, and 35% from other parts of the UK, while 20% are from overseas) and contributing to a highly educated workforce.

However, the region faces significant socio-economic challenges, including disparities between the densely populated metropolitan areas and the sparsely populated rural areas²⁸⁹, poverty, youth unemployment, low skills, and education²⁹⁰. Thus, there are ongoing efforts to improve educational and employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups and emphasizing on inclusive growth, such as the Social Economy Drive 2023. Moreover, health challenges in the region include higher rates of hypertension, obesity, and smoking, as well as increased anxiety and decreased life expectancy, with significant disparities between the most and least deprived areas. Public health initiatives focus on reducing inequalities, promoting mental health, and enhancing healthcare access²⁹¹.

Moreover, the West Midlands faces significant social deprivation, with about 30% of the population living in the most deprived quintile. Urban areas face higher levels of deprivation, while rural areas struggle with access to services and economic opportunities. Initiatives focus on tackling unemployment, poverty, and social exclusion, promoting an inclusive, green economy²⁹².

5.1.3. Economical and Industrial landscape

The industrial profile of both East and West Midlands is robust, with the West Midlands having a high number of major industrial cities²⁹³. The West Midlands contribute significantly to the UK economy, accounting for £99 billion in Gross Value Added (GVA) in 2019, or 5% of the country's total production. It's a large, diversified area with a long history of innovative production, manufacturing, and design²⁹⁴.

The Midlands is most often linked to success in manufacturing, especially in the automotive industry, which continues to thrive and is still an example of strength today as Midlands-based businesses seize

²⁸⁹ Portrait of the Regions - UNITED KINGDOM - WEST MIDLANDS - Geography and history, 2004, Accessed: June 17, 2024, Available: https://circabc.europa.eu/webdav/CircaBC/ESTAT/regportraits/Information/ukg_geo.htm

²⁹⁰ WMREDI, State of the region 2020 Full report, 2020, Accessed : June 17, 2024, Available: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://www.wmca.org.uk/media/4290/state-of-the-region-2020-final-full-report.pdf>

²⁹¹ Office for health, improvement & disparities, Health Profile for the West Midlands 2021, Accessed: June 17, 2024, Available: https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/static-reports/health-profile-for-england/regional-profile-west_midlands.html

²⁹² West Midlands Combined Authorites, West Midlands' Circular Economy Routemap, 2021, Accessed: June 17, Available: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://www.wmca.org.uk/media/wxrfkpfq/wmca-circular-economy-routemap.pdf>

²⁹³ Encyclopaedia Britannica, Midlands region, England, United Kingdom. Accessed: Jun. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Midlands>

²⁹⁴ HM Government, West Midlands Local Industrial Strategy, May 2019. Accessed: Jun. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/west-midlands-local-industrial-strategy>

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the appealing opportunities brought by vehicles electrification, industrial digitalization, and autonomous vehicles²⁹⁵.

The industrial landscape and industrial sectors distribution of the Midlands region are detailed in Figure 22 and Figure 23. The south of the North West and Yorkshire & The Humber is also mapped because of the high number of clusters identified in T2.1. Industrial areas are mainly concentrated in big cities: Manchester, Liverpool, Leeds, Sheffield, Birmingham, and Hull.

As shown in Figure 23, 4 major industrial sectors are identified along with their number of sites as a percentage of the total number of sites (the waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery sector is removed from the analysis because of its overrepresentation in the E-PRTR database for the UK.) :

- Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment (26% with a high concentration around Birmingham)
- Manufacture of chemical, pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic (16%)
- Manufacture of food products, beverage, and tobacco products (13%)
- Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products (12%)

Despite the region industrial strengths, the coronavirus pandemic had a significant impact on the macroeconomy of the Midlands. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) increased steadily in the Midlands from 2009 to 2019, growing by 44.8% annually, but a 5.3% decrease in GDP from 2019 to 2020 was caused by the coronavirus pandemic, while the UK saw a 5.8% decline in GDP during the same period. The East Midlands mitigated partially this decrease. The GDP begun to show indications of recovery since 2020, as UK's GDP has climbed by 7.9%, whereas the Midlands' GDP has increased 8.1%. Except for London and the South East, no other UK region had a larger GVA in 2021 (£252.6 billion), making up 12.4% of the country's total GVA²⁹⁶.

One way to overcome the pandemic impact was found in the UK government previously announced Midlands Engine Strategy as part of its commitment to turn the Midlands into a "growth engine" for the nation. This strategy lays out the steps to address productivity barriers throughout the Midlands, allowing businesses to increase productivity, export more goods and services, and create more jobs²⁹⁷. The Midlands Engine comprises local authorities and local enterprise partnerships from both the East and West Midlands.

Based on ONS Business Demography data from November 2023, the Midlands had 404,955 businesses in 2022, showing a decline of 0.7% comparing to 2021, data consistent with the broader national trend of 0.5% reduction. Regarding enterprise launches, the region saw 48,395 new enterprises in 2022, a decrease of 10.4% compared to 2021. A higher decrease when compared to the reduction of 7.4% in the UK. Looking to the third quarter of 2023, the enterprise launches rose by

²⁹⁵ Pates et al. (2020). Midlands engine independent economic review, a final report to the midlands engine partnership. Accessed: Jun. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sqw.co.uk/application/files/8216/2384/9028/Midlands-Engine-IER-Full-Report.pdf>

²⁹⁶ The Midlands Engine (2023), STATE OF THE REGION, EXECUTIVE SUMMARY, Dec 2023. Accessed: Jun. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://midlandsendengine.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/ME_StateoftheRegion_2023.pdf

²⁹⁷ Department for Communities and Local Government (March 2017). Midlands Engine Strategy. Accessed: Jun. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/midlands-engine-strategy>

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3.6% when compared to the same quarter in the previous year while the enterprises closing decreased by 16.5%²⁹⁶.

As of June 2023, the Midlands employment rate stood at 74.3%, while the UK's general rate was 75.5%. The region equalled the UK growth rate of 0.1 percentage points when compared to the year ending June 2022. An extra 77,705 working-age inhabitants must find employment in the Midlands for it to achieve national levels²⁹⁶.

The Midlands region imported £76.2 billion of goods and exported almost £60.0 billion in the year ending in the second quarter of 2023²⁹⁸. The trade deficit was reduced from £21.1 billion to £16.2bn from the previous year, and the Midlands' goods exports grew £11.6 billion²⁹⁶.

More than London and the South East combined, the Midlands region accounted for 22.0% of England's total exports. With £41.2 billion, or 68.7% of the total, machinery and transportation accounted for the highest SITC (Standard International Trade Classification) category for goods exports in the Midlands region. Thus, this SITC area has increased by £10.0 billion during the year ending in the second quarter of 2022, which is indicative of an improvement in the automotive and broader manufacturing industries²⁹⁶.

The Midlands has some distinct advantages when it comes to established sectors, such as transport technologies and logistics, advanced manufacturing, construction, education, energy and low carbon, healthcare and life sciences, and retail. These sectors present higher than the UK-wide proportion for the GVA. The region priority sectors for growth were identified and include green growth, advanced manufacturing, food & agri-tech, med-tech and life sciences, and new market opportunities. The green growth in the Midlands currently produce £26.6 billion in GVA annually with the low carbon and environmental sectors. Ample growth opportunities exist due to the need for decarbonization of the economy and regional industrial strengths in several areas, such as utilities, alternative fuels, fuel cells, and wind. In relation to GVA, advanced manufacturing is the second largest in the Midlands. The region is responsible for 22.1% of the total manufacturing output of the country. Several manufacturing subsectors were recognized as clusters in the Midlands by the recently completed Midlands Engine Cluster Project, which included textiles, metals and minerals, food, and drink, automotive, aerospace, and rail. Advanced manufacturing will be essential for achieving net zero and industry digitization²⁹⁶.

The Midlands has the highest concentration of agricultural production and food processing in the UK. Which also serves as the country's reference in logistics and distribution for these sectors. In 2021, the Midlands accounted for 21% of all jobs in the UK related to agriculture, food and drink industries, and packaging. Growth potential can be achieved focusing on skilled employment supported by more investment and the use of new technologies. The life sciences sector, which employs over 32,000 people, has been on the two UK regions with the highest number of enterprises over the past ten years, and outperforms its share of the national economy due to its high productivity. The Midland's GVA is predicted to be about £6 billion just from med-tech and life sciences²⁹⁶.

Some areas were identified as new market opportunities in the region, in particular hydrogen related, with hydrogen production and distribution, power generation and heat and transport applications. Another potential opportunity is found in the smart energy area, aiming to control the energy

²⁹⁸ HM Revenue & Customs, UK Regional Trade in products Statistics Quarter 2 2023, September 2023

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requirements with the use of new and emerging digital technologies, artificial intelligence, and machine learning. Quantum technology as the potential to improve healthcare systems, boost smart cities, and promote innovation in sectors like manufacturing, logistics, and cyber security. Additionally, there is a growing cluster of AI technology in the Midlands. The development and installation of Advanced Modular Reactors and Small Modular Reactors, along with nuclear fusion, present further opportunities for the Midlands to become a major player in the nuclear power industry²⁹⁶.

With linkages to important industries and a robust supporting infrastructure of universities and other centers, the Midlands' business base seems to be more innovative overall when compared to the general UK businesses²⁹⁶. One example can be seen with the West Midlands Innovation Accelerator Programme and its objective to promote innovation, assisting companies in creating new services, products, and processes in the fields of CleanTech, HealthTech, and MedTech, with a strong involvement of universities²⁹⁹.

²⁹⁹ Riley et. al. (Feb. 2024). The West Midlands Regional Economic Development Institute and the

City-Region Economic Develment Institute. West Midlands Monthly Economic Impact Monitor. Accessed: Jun. 17, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://blog.bham.ac.uk/cityredi/category/west-midlands-weekly-economic-impact-monitor/>

Figure 22: Mapping of industrial sites in the Midlands region (without the waste treatment and disposal sector for better visibility, icons from icons8.com)

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Figure 23: Industrial sectors distribution and zoom into the Manchester cluster (icons from icons8.com).

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5.2. Local Policy Analysis

The West Midlands, United Kingdom

Overview

The midlands is the central area of England, which forms part of the wider United Kingdom (UK). There are two official regions, the West Midlands, and East Midlands. Since 2016, the West Midlands has had a West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA) which has strategic authority over economic development in the region, including the transition to the circular economy. Further relevant to I-US in the midlands, industrial strategy and decarbonisation is also governed by the region. This greatly contrasts governance in the East Midlands, where a combined authority has only come into place in April 2024, meaning prior to this, matters related to the circular economy are either governed at the level of local authority, or at central UK government level. Despite leaving the European Union (EU) in 2020, the UK adopted the European Commission's Circular Economy Action Plan 2020, and remains committed to moving towards a more circular economy which promotes resource efficiency³⁰⁰.

Due to its history as the birthplace of the UK's National Industrial Symbiosis Programme (NISP), and its recently revived support for industrial symbiosis³⁰¹, **the West Midlands region** is the focus of this analysis of I-US related policy. An interview with Jordan Gerrard, Circular Economy Project Delivery Officer of the WMCA, has also provided additional background and regional context.

Policies specifically targeting I-US and their origins

No one policy is dedicated to I-US, however many support I-US as an enabling lever for achieving sustainability goals - including the circular economy, resource efficiency and decarbonisation. 25 relevant policy documents were identified using the methodology outlined above, of which 14 were selected for in-depth analysis based on keyword screening.

Due to the long-standing centralised nature of the UK, national documents usually refer to initiatives to be implemented at the level of the UK or England, by the UK government. These initiatives range from action plans to recommendations for departments and collaborating partners, as well as vision and goal setting. Whilst only 6 short-listed documents are from the regional competency, these initiatives best support I-US in the West Midlands region, namely the new Industrial Symbiosis Programme launched by the WMCA. A complete list is provided in Annex 2: List of the documents screened for policy analysis section. The documents can be categorised as follows:

Strategies related to UK decarbonisation:

- The Clean Growth Strategy (2017)
- Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener (2021)
- Industrial decarbonisation strategy (2021)
- Sixth Carbon Budget, Climate Change Committee (2020)

³⁰⁰ UK Government, 2020, Policy paper Circular Economy Package policy statement. Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/circular-economy-package-policy-statement/circular-economy-package-policy-statement>

³⁰¹WMCA, 2023, West Midlands' Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region's journey to a green industrial revolution. Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.wmca.org.uk/media/wxrfkpfq/wmca-circular-economy-routemap.pdf>

Resource recovery and waste in England:

- The Resources and Waste Strategy for England (2018)
- Position Paper from The Resource Recovery from Waste programme: The National Materials Datahub Can Improve Governance for Better Material Use by Industry: An Evidence Briefing from the Resource Recovery from Waste Programme
- Waste prevention programme for England: Maximising Resources, Minimising Waste (2023)

West Midlands' development:

- The West Midlands' Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region's journey to a green industrial revolution (2023)
- West Midlands Local Industrial Strategy (2019)
- Home of the Green Industrial Revolution (2022)
- West Midlands Plan for Growth (2022)
- Delivering a Deeper Devolution Deal for the West Midlands (2023)

Sector-specific documents:

- Manufacturing: Materials and Manufacturing Vision 2050 (2023)
- Metals: Innovation action plan for aluminium in a circular economy, InnovateUK (2023)

Main Actors with work relevant for Industrial-Urban Symbiosis

Based on the policy analysis, it can be concluded that at the regional level, **the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA)** plays the primary role of developing policy and implementing I-US related-initiatives. The WMCA was set up to improve the region's economy and is the central contact for engaging relevant industry and public partners, including the encompassing local councils. The WMCA developed the Circular Economy Routemap for the West Midlands and follow-on newly established pilot IS programme - West Midlands Industrial Symbiosis Network (WMISN).³⁰² The WMCA will contract manage the new pilot IS programme in the region, with **International Synergies Limited (ISL)** serving as an external facilitator. Additional roles of WMCA include securing programme funding long term and advocating for policy changes at national level. Sustainability West Midlands will also contribute to stakeholder engagement through their members and wider networks.

Whilst Local Enterprise Partnerships (LEPs) were previously named as potentially key relationships to facilitate resource efficiency/IS³⁰³, post-Brexit LEPs have dissolved in combined authority areas, and their role taken over in the West Midlands by the newly established **Business Growth West Midlands**³⁰⁴.

³⁰²Sustainability West Midlands, 2024, West Midlands Industrial Symbiosis Network (WMISN), Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.sustainabilitywestmidlands.org.uk/news/west-midlands-industrial-symbiosis-network-wmisn/>

³⁰³ UK Government 2017, National Clean Growth Strategy, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/clean-growth-strategy>

³⁰⁴ Business Growth West Midlands, Website, Accessed: 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.businessgrowthwestmidlands.org.uk/>

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In the long term, the WMCA envisions that this business support agency could manage the new IS programme alongside other economic initiatives.

At national level, the UK departments, which are working on sectors related to I-US, include the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (**DESNZ**), working on decarbonisation of industry, clean growth and zero waste. The Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (**DEFRA**), which issued both the waste prevention programme and resource and waste strategies for England, alongside the **Environment Agency**. DEFRA also funds national research in relation to improving data management and accessibility around secondary material use, in collaboration with DESNZ. The initiatives are implemented by national departments or national research agencies given the centralised nature of the UK. **Innovate UK** are the national innovation agency and part of UK Research and Innovation, a non-departmental public body funded by grant-in-aid from the UK Government. Innovate UK developed the materials and manufacturing vision 2050, the Innovation action plan for aluminium in a circular economy 2030 and provide a huge amount of funding for industrial innovation around resource reuse and manufacturing.

At both the national and regional level, **Universities** have a strong presence leading on several circular economy (including industrial resource efficiency) research initiatives with industry, via national funding and self-funded projects. For example, the research and development cluster with University of Birmingham, Aston University and Tyseley Energy Park³⁰⁵.

Funding Mechanisms and other support instruments for I-US

The recently launched pilot IS programme WMISN in the West Midlands is funded directly by the board of the **WMCA**, made up of all the municipalities under the authority, e.g. Birmingham, Coventry, and the West Midlands Innovation Accelerator.

The following funding instruments potentially relevant for I-US are provided at the UK level, and directed towards **businesses, industry, and Universities**. These can be grouped into two main categories:

A number of **industrial green transition-related funding** programmes have launched at national level, which can be used to enable I-US. These stem from a variety of over-arching policy objectives including climate neutrality, decarbonisation and achieving a circular economy. For example, the Industrial Energy Transformation Fund (IETF) supports the development and deployment of technologies that enable businesses with high energy use to transition to a low carbon future. Run by the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, and previously the Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, it is now headed into Phase 3, which will provide up to £185 million in funding between 2024 and 2028³⁰⁶. Another large potential source of funding for industry, universities and NGOs is UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), through the various calls launched on a rolling basis under its 5 strategic themes research programme, in particular the theme of “build a green future”. This research

³⁰⁵ WMCA, 2023, West Midlands' Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region's journey to a green industrial revolution. Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.wmca.org.uk/media/wxrfkpfq/wmca-circular-economy-routemap.pdf>

³⁰⁶ UK Government, 2024, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/industrial-energy-transformation-fund>

programme runs until 2029, with an initial commitment of up to £185 million in total from 2023 to 2025³⁰⁷.

A second range of funding instruments support **innovation, namely in manufacturing, with a focus on resource efficiency**. These stem mainly from the Innovative UK Materials and Manufacturing Vision 2050, funding UK manufacturing's efforts to achieve Net Zero by 2050³⁰⁸. Whilst the £210 million Transforming foundation industries Fund which funded many projects³⁰⁹ across the UK on resource efficiency (I-US projects included), ended in 2024,³¹⁰ other similar programmes run by UKRI are following such as an ongoing innovative feasibility studies call on advanced low carbon manufacturing³¹¹. UK registered organisations, including public sector organisations in this case, can apply for a share of up to £1 million. This call is part of the wider £15 million Resource Efficiency for Materials and Manufacturing (REforMM) programme which aims for the UK to be a leader in resource efficiency.³¹² Similarly, the national Made Smarter Innovation (MSI) Fund is providing funding for UK manufacturers and technology providers to collaboratively solve industry challenges³¹³. For small or medium-sized manufacturers in the West and East Midlands, match funded grants of up to £20K for the purchase of hardware and software are available, as well as impartial advice³¹⁴. To further scale-up or boost particular projects, the Innovate UK Investor Partnerships programme allows investors to apply to partner with Innovate UK to invest in innovative SMEs aligned with grant funding³¹⁵.

Exchange support instruments:

Besides financial support, an important pillar for encouraging industrial symbiosis is facilitation of linkages between the companies. As part of WMCA's pilot IS programme WMISN, exploring exchanges between companies will be facilitated in the West Midlands by Industrial Synergies Limited (ISL). In terms of longer-standing networks:

- The Black Country Industrial Cluster is a not-for-profit organisation that supports, informs, and represents its more than 3000 Energy Intensive manufacturing businesses and local industry

³⁰⁷ UK Research and Innovation, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.ukri.org/who-we-are/our-vision-and-strategy/ukri-strategic-themes/>

³⁰⁸ UK Research and Innovation, 2023, Innovate UK materials and manufacturing vision 2050, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/innovate-uk-materials-and-manufacturing-vision-2050/>

³⁰⁹ UK Research and Innovation, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.ukri.org/news/improving-resource-and-energy-efficiency-in-foundation-industries/>

³¹⁰ UK Research and Innovation, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/transforming-foundation-industries/>

³¹¹ UK Research and Innovation, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.ukri.org/opportunity/resource-efficient-or-bio-based-materials-and-manufacturing-fs-2/>

³¹² Innovate UK, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/programme/manufacturing-materials-reformm/>

³¹³ Made smarter, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: [HYPERLINK "https://www.madesmarter.uk/"https://www.madesmarter.uk/](https://www.madesmarter.uk/)

³¹⁴ Made smarter, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.madesmarter.uk/adoption-support/>

³¹⁵ Innovate UK and Business Connect, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/opportunities/innovate-uk-investor-partnerships-investor-selection-april-2024/>

members through the transition to net zero³¹⁶. It serves as an interface for a big share of relevant businesses for WMCA to engage regarding I-US locally.

- The West Midlands Green Business Clubs Network who meets to share best practice and policy information, including on resource efficiency. It is established and coordinated by Sustainability West Midlands.³¹⁷

A critical reading of the policy: the vision of a resource efficient manufacturing industry and the role of I-US in decarbonising industry in the West Midlands

General context

The West Midlands region remains the manufacturing hub of the UK following the industrial revolution and is now looking to drive the green industrial revolution. The region has a net-zero target by 2041, demonstrating even greater ambition than the 2050 UK target.³¹⁸ The industry present is highly energy intensive, and faces challenges to decarbonise given it does not have easy access to renewables like wind energy, that other UK industrial hubs do. The West Midlands therefore has a focus on developing sustainable, circular material usage. In addition to decarbonising, a slow developing appreciation of the economic and social benefits of transitioning to a circular economy is also driving policy.³¹⁹

Industrial symbiosis as a pathway to a resource efficient and net-zero industrial revolution

The need to decarbonise UK industry is a driving force for the support of I-US in national policy, beginning with the UK Clean Growth Strategy (2017) in which IS is mentioned as a supporting process of resource efficiency, to be used to achieve the Government's target of a zero avoidable waste economy by 2050. At national level IS is very much seen through the lens of resource efficiency, with the Resources and Waste Strategy (2018) setting out the national ambition to become a world leader of resource efficiency in production, including using by-products and recovery and use of other secondary materials as inputs. An additional target is set to double resource productivity by 2050.

One of the key themes of the Industrial Decarbonisation Strategy (2021) is to improve resource efficiency, with IS identified as one of the tools which should be supported (Figure 24), in part via commissioned research on industrial resource efficiency, focused on materials including cement, steel and chemicals, with the last round of research ending 2024. A 2025 action included is focused on seeking to incentivise industry to practice IS by running a discovery project to better understand the role of industrial symbiosis. However, no such programme has been found yet at national level. The Net Zero Strategy (2021) similarly mentions supporting IS, as well as carrying out research on barriers, drivers, and pathway to better resource efficiency to inform policy. There is no specific mention of

³¹⁶ Black Country Industrial Cluster, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://bcinc.org.uk/>

³¹⁷ Sustainability West Midlands, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.sustainabilitywestmidlands.org.uk/networks/west-midlands-green-business-clubs-network/>

³¹⁸ WMCA, 2022, Home of the Green Industrial Revolution, Home of the Green Industrial Revolution, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: [HYPERLINK "https://www.wmca.org.uk/documents/environment-energy/home-of-the-green-industrial-revolution/"https://www.wmca.org.uk/documents/environment-energy/home-of-the-green-industrial-revolution/](https://www.wmca.org.uk/documents/environment-energy/home-of-the-green-industrial-revolution/)

³¹⁹ Jordan Gerrard, Circular Economy Project Delivery Officer of WMCA, Interviewed 23 April 2024

urban waste involvement but reuse of industrial energy to power urban settings is a focus within the decarbonisation policy.

Figure 8.1: Illustrative example of the five channels of potential growth from decarbonisation (BEIS analysis, 2020).

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Figure 24: Including IS as a tool towards decarbonisation. Source: Industrial decarbonisation strategy (2021)

There is also real support and drive coming through national policy for improving data availability for better use of secondary materials and industrial by-products in manufacturing.³²⁰ Innovate UK’s Materials and Manufacturing Vision 2050 includes IS as part of its strategy for a re-imagined clean-tech manufacturing sector which is resilient and net zero (Figure 24).

³²⁰ UK Government, 2023, The waste prevention programme for England: Maximising Resources, Minimising Waste, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/waste-prevention-programme-for-england-maximising-resources-minimising-waste>

Figure 25: High-level logic model of action of the UK’s Materials and Manufacturing Vision 2050.

Despite the relatively high prevalence of IS support in national documents, implementation of I-US in the West Midlands is best practically supported via the new IS pilot programme WMISN, and the enabling strategy The West Midlands’ Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region’s journey to a green industrial revolution (2023). Circular Manufacturing one of the 3 sectors focused on in the West Midlands Circular Economy Roadmap, with the Industrial symbiosis delivery programme named as a strategic intervention, including a detailed action plan.

Overall, the West Midlands is using I-US as a tool to address a unique opportunity to creating the first regional manufacturing ecosystem, that is low carbon and supports the principles of the circular economy.

Sectors targeting by the policy documents relevant to I-US:

At the West midlands regional level, sectors targeted by policy are manufacturing-focused (Figure 26), guided by the transport industries present, as well as what the WMCA has competence over. Unsurprisingly, metals are a primary focus for resource efficiency and IS, given more than 4,000 businesses in the West Midlands work in metal recycling, reprocessing with a particular strength in aluminium recycling. Batteries are also a focus, with 40% of all cars exported from the UK made in the West Midlands.³²¹ On the side of symbiosis’ created from urban waste, recovery of fertiliser and sand from urban wastewater sewage sludge for reuse in agriculture and construction, respectively, are focus areas. This is in part due to WMCA being able to access sewage sludge, as compared to other urban waste streams which are within the competence of local authorities, and often managed by contracted external parties. Industrial-scale food processing is also a prevalent industry in the region, with “Circular Food” being selected as another of the priority areas of the Circular Economy Routemap. The potential to create symbioses between local excess food and food processing industries is being

³²¹ WMCA, 2023, West Midlands’ Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region’s journey to a green industrial revolution. Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.wmca.org.uk/media/wxrfkpfq/wmca-circular-economy-routemap.pdf>

explored with local authorities, as part of planning for mandatory source-separation of organic waste in 2025.³²²

Priority Sector	Strategic Interventions	Overall Aim
Circular Manufacturing	Circular battery manufacturing	Design the first truly circular battery factory, distinguishing the West Midlands Gigafactory from other similar projects.
	Industrial symbiosis delivery programme	Implement a place-based industrial symbiosis delivery programme to cross-fertilise opportunities across the three priority areas.
	High-value fuels from waste	Use advanced processing technologies to turn residual, municipal and industrial waste into high-value fuels for aviation, logistics, heavy plant and other manufacturing sectors.
	Circular manufacturing centre of excellence	Establish a Circular Manufacturing Centre of Excellence to support circular design best practice and to develop advanced technologies (robotics, AI etc.).

Figure 26: Circular Manufacturing is one of the three selected Circular Economy high priority areas in the West Midlands. Source: West Midlands’ Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region’s journey to a green industrial revolution (2023).

Challenges to I-US

Challenges highlighted relating to industry adopting increased use of secondary materials and resource efficiency (including I-US), are as follows;

- A lack of knowledge, resourcing constraints, and access to data on potential IS opportunities.³²³ It is worth noting the breakdown of IS exchanges amongst SMEs in the West Midlands following the loss of government-funded facilitation in 2009 (the NISP programme), highlighting the challenge to incentivise businesses to invest time and money in I(-U)S, if facilitation is not 100% publicly funded.³²⁴
- Availability of sufficient and compatible data, was additionally identified as a major barrier for decision-making around government policy and public and private investments.³²⁵
- Complex proposals necessary to access national funding: despite the availability of money to innovate. A lot of businesses don’t have capacity for developing these proposals.³²⁶
- The UK government does not automatically provide funding for regional governments on this topic, nor are many funding calls available to them – this led to lobbying by WMCA to access long-term funding to support IS. WMCA can subsequently facilitate the matching of funding with interested businesses.³²⁷

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving industrial symbiosis

³²² Sustainability West Midlands, 2024, West Midlands Industrial Symbiosis Network (WMISN), Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.sustainabilitywestmidlands.org.uk/news/west-midlands-industrial-symbiosis-network-wmisn/>

³²³ HM Government, 2021, Industrial Decarbonisation Strategy, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6051cd04e90e07527f645f1e/Industrial_Decarbonisation_Strategy_March_2021.pdf

³²⁴ Jordan Gerrard, Circular Economy Project Delivery Officer of WMCA, Interviewed 23 April 2024

³²⁵ UK Government, 2023, The waste prevention programme for England: Maximising Resources, Minimising Waste, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/waste-prevention-programme-for-england-maximising-resources-minimising-waste>

³²⁶ Jordan Gerrard, Circular Economy Project Delivery Officer of WMCA, Interviewed 23 April 2024

³²⁷ WMCA, no date, Trailblazing Devolution for the West Midlands, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.wmca.org.uk/what-we-do/trailblazing-devolution-for-the-west-midlands/>

When it comes to I-US, the UK government is setting the national vision and high-level goals regarding industrial decarbonisation and resource efficient manufacturing, laying the foundations for regional strategy development supporting I(-U)S. There is an impressively strong focus on research at national level to inform the development of these national policies, which is carried out by national agencies. This includes collaborating with cross-sectoral non-profit researchers like Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP).³²⁸ Provision and co-ordination of funding for innovation to industry and universities in the region is also to date provided at the national level via a wealth of calls. This extends to piloting public-private partnerships to provide bigger investment to scale-up decarbonisation.³²⁹ Driving the shift to greater transparency and availability of materials data to enable I-US also lies with national government.³³⁰ Given the need to affect legislation, and the oversight the national government has, this is a key role which they have done a great deal of research on to date, in particular regarding creating a national materials data hub,³³¹ however progress seems to have somewhat stalled since 2019.³³²

The policy demonstrates that in the West Midlands, IS is being implemented by the regional government. This is possible because the WMCA has regional oversight, funds, and ability to advocate to national government to support IS. In the long term, more secure and long-term funding has been secured by WMCA from April 2025 thanks to the landmark Trailblazer devolution deal and single settlement, which provides the WMCA with the competencies to agree priorities for the region and directly allocate funding for net zero-driven initiatives, including I-US.³³³ The importance of a regional level government to financially support IS can be seen when compared to for example Hull and East Yorkshire (located in the adjacent Yorkshire and the Humber region), which is yet to form and benefit from the additional funds associated with a combined authority. A recent IS scoping report funded by the North East and Yorkshire Net Zero Hub highlighted a requirement for significant public funds which are currently not available to implement and manage an effective IS programme.³³⁴

As discussed, the Midlands implemented a publicly-funded facilitated model of Industrial Symbiosis from 2003 – 2009, mainly via the National Industrial Symbiosis Programme (NISP).³³⁵ In the lead up to implementing the new IS programme, a scoping study was carried out to evaluate facilitation, amongst other aspects of an IS programme. Whilst not publicly available, it is confirmed that the study

³²⁸ Wrap, 2019, Resource Efficiency Clusters Case Study Research, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://wrap.org.uk/resources/case-study/case-study-resource-efficiency-clusters>

³²⁹ Innovate UK, Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/>

³³⁰ UK Government, 2023, The waste prevention programme for England: Maximising Resources, Minimising Waste, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/waste-prevention-programme-for-england-maximising-resources-minimising-waste>

³³¹ Anne P.M. Velenturf, Resource Recovery from Waste, University of Leeds, 2019, The National Materials Datahub Can Improve Governance for Better Material Use by Industry: An Evidence Briefing from the Resource Recovery from Waste Programme, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: https://rrfw.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/rrfw-evidence-briefing-nmdhub_v2.0.pdf

³³² letsrecycle.com, 2022, Web Article, Circular economy experts call for 'national materials data hub', Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.letsrecycle.com/news/circular-economy-experts-call-for-national-materials-data-hub/>

³³³ WMCA, no date, Trailblazing Devolution for the West Midlands, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.wmca.org.uk/what-we-do/trailblazing-devolution-for-the-west-midlands/>

³³⁴ Phil Glover, Business Development Manager, Hull and East Yorkshire Business, Growth and Skills Hub, via email received April 18 2024

³³⁵ WMCA, 2023, West Midlands' Circular Economy Routemap Kickstarting the region's journey to a green industrial revolution. Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.wmca.org.uk/media/wxfkpfq/wmca-circular-economy-routemap.pdf>

recommended the continuation of external facilitation, as is planned for the new programme. It can be assumed that positive experiences with this facilitated model in the past, and an established relationship with ISL, influenced this decision. General reasons for selecting external over internal facilitation include an existing governance structure in the UK which tends towards external contracting, and the costs of hiring new expert staff or building the necessary expertise inhouse.³³⁶

5.3. I-US Potential Analysis

5.3.1. Material Flows Mapping

Industrial Waste Generation

The material flows analysis was conducted using the E-PRTR database. In this part, the Midlands region refers to East Midlands, West Midlands and south of the North West and Yorkshire & The Humber. As shown in Figure 27, the analysed region in this section is extended to areas further north because of the high number of clusters identified in T2.1, and as such, cities outside The Midlands will be mentioned in the descriptions that follow.

Figure 27: Scope of study for the waste flows analysis.

³³⁶ Jordan Gerrard, Circular Economy Project Delivery Officer of WMCA, Interviewed 23 April 2024

Figure 26 and Figure 27 respectively illustrate the total and disposed industrial waste flows in the Midlands. Each year, 81.3 Mtons of waste are generated in the region, 32.6 Mtons of which is disposed. The production of electricity is the main emitting sector with an amount of waste of 1.4 Mtons/year (1.7% of total waste). Without considering the waste treatment and disposal sectors, the next biggest emitting sectors are the manufacture of motor vehicles, other non-ferrous metal production and sewerage. These four sectors represent around 4.4% of the total waste flows on the territory, and when adding the waste treatment and disposal sector waste flows, then 37% of the regional flows are accounted for.

Regarding the disposed waste, production of electricity is still the most emitting sector with 841 ktons of waste (2.6% of the total disposed waste) either landfilled, buried, or incinerated without energy recovery. Then, 289 and 276 ktons are disposed respectively by the manufacture of other organic basic chemicals and the sewerage sectors. Figure 29 illustrates all the waste flows in the area and their sectorial distribution.

The following maps show that the waste flows are highly concentrated in the Manchester, Liverpool Leeds, and Birmingham industrial clusters. In contrast, the centre and south-west of the region generate much less waste.

Figure 28: Total waste flows in the Midlands region.

Figure 29: Disposed waste flows in the Midlands region.

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Figure 30: Waste flows diagram and waste sectorial analysis in the Midlands region (quantities in ktons in the table, icons from icons8.com)

I-US Flow Mapping

The table below shows the main sectors responsible for waste material flows in the Midlands region, discounting waste processing companies. Using ISL experience of global IS delivery, we have listed typical associated resource flows against each specific sector.

Significant volumes of waste generated in the manufacture of motor vehicles and the production of non-ferrous metal sectors already go into recovery operations. This is likely to inhibit its commercial availability for industrial symbiosis synergies as it will have lower associated rates of cost (no landfill tax). The largest area of potential opportunity is the relatively high volume of waste from the production of electricity going to disposal and not to recovery activities. Similarly, the manufacture of other organic basic chemicals has a low recovery rate at 35.6% and presents another significant opportunity for IS implementation.

Table 8 Primary Waste Flow Data for the Midlands

NACE sector name	Waste destined for disposal (t/year)	Waste destined for recovery (t/year)	Total of waste (t/year)
Production of electricity	841,199	573,551	1,414,750
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	289,146	159,615	448,762
Sewerage	276,035	383,770	659,805
Manufacture of other inorganic basic chemicals	275,490	91,132	366,622
Manufacture of other parts and accessories for motor vehicles	272,400	969	273,369
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys	224,349	407,599	631,947
Treatment and coating of metals	173,127	52,100	225,227
Raising of swine/pigs	165,800	12,140	177,940
Manufacture of veneer sheets and wood-based panels	126,670	14,310	140,980
Casting of iron	84,649	62,670	147,319
Support activities to performing arts	81,295	10,260	91,555
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	70,357	413,662	484,020
Other non-ferrous metal production	61,997	644,557	706,554
Raising of poultry	53,584	178,375	231,959
Extraction of salt	51,003	58,501	109,504

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Manufacture of metal structures and parts of structures	48,526	112	48,639
Warehousing and storage	47,900	13,000	60,900
Manufacture of refractory products	37,034	1,893	38,927
Production of meat and poultry meat products	35,603	263,839	299,442

The priority sectors with either the most significant waste volumes, or the lowest recovery rates have been identified as:

- Production of electricity
- Manufacture of motor vehicles
- Other non-ferrous metal production
- Sewerage
- Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys
- Manufacture of paper and paperboard
- Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals
- Raising of pigs and poultry

Although the data is a little lacking in granularity, with ISL knowledge of these priority sectors it is still possible to produce a list of the typical byproducts and wastes arising from each sector. The following table outlines the main resources associated with each of these priority sectors.

Table 9 Midlands Priority Sector Flow Analysis

Sector	No. of sites	Outputs /By-products
Production of electricity	52	Fly ash
		Bottom ash
		Sludge
		Waste water / cooling water
Manufacture of motor vehicles	22	Scrap metal
		Plastic trimmings and rejects
		Paint sludge
		Solvent waste
		Used oils and lubricants
		WEEE
		Rubber

		Glass
Other non-ferrous metal production	16	Bauxite residue (red mud)
		Slag
		Dross / skimmings
		Sludge / filter cake
Sewerage	24	Sludges
		Treated effluent
		Biosolids
Manufacture of steel, iron, and ferro-alloys	28	Slag
		Mill scale
		Dust (Zinc rich)
		Process gases and steam
		Scrap metal
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	15	Waste paper / paperboard
		Ash
		Sludge
		Wood residue
		Black Liquor / other spent liquors
		Chemical waste
Manufacture of other organic basic chemical	43	Chemical residues
		Carbon dioxide
Pig and Poultry Farming	67	Manure
		Feathers
		Contaminated straw and sawdust

There is a cluster of similar materials arising from the metal forming and metal casting sectors, as well as end users of ferrous and non-ferrous metals such as automotive. For IS and I-US purposes there is a number of potential high value resources with established cross sector uses, which gives some encouragement on IS potential for the region.

5.3.2. I-US Infrastructure Mapping

Figure 31, Figure 32 and Figure 33 illustrate the key infrastructures for I-US in the Midlands region.

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In terms of transport infrastructures, the region has 2294 km (0.09 km/km²) of motorways and around 8917 km (0.35km/km²) of railways. For the energy infrastructures, 46 and 31% of the electricity are produced from gas and coal plants respectively while solar (6%), cogeneration (6%), wind (4%), waste (3%), biomass (3%) and storage (1%) share the rest of the mix. Using modelling data from the HRE4 project, 29.1 PJ/year and 30.9 PJ/year of excess heat from respectively industrial sites and WWTP have been identified. For the heat demands, urban area would consume around 389.7 PJ/year. Regarding the education, 88 universities (science and technical schools) are in the region. No, I-US demo cases have been identified.

0.09 km of motorway per km²

0.35 km of railway per km²

Figure 31: Transport infrastructures in the Midlands region.

Figure 32: Electricity production and excess heat in the Midlands region.

3.5 universities per 1000 km²

No I-US demo cases identified

*Only technical and science schools are considered

Figure 33: Education and innovation in the Midlands region (icons from icons8.com).

5.3.3. Regional readiness assessment for I-US and general conclusions

The following table outlines the main industrial symbiosis opportunities for the resources identified in the resource flow analysis provided in section 5.3.1.

Table 10 Industrial Symbiosis Opportunities in the Midlands

Sector	Outputs /By-products	Uses
Production of electricity	Fly ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – cement substitute in concrete production. • Agriculture – soil improvement
	Bottom ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – aggregate substitute in concrete, road bases, embankments, and structural fill • Cement substitute • Brick and ceramic manufacture • Land reclamation • Agriculture – soil improvement • Water treatment – filtration medium
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction materials • Agriculture – soil improvement
	Waste water / cooling water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-use in cooler system • Agriculture and landscaping, irrigation
Manufacture of motor vehicles	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and reuse
	Plastic trimmings and rejects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and reuse • Construction and insulation materials • Textile Fibres • Asphalt and concrete additives • Energy recovery
	Paint sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement production • Construction materials • Asphalt additive • Metal recovery • Lime / ceramic production
	Solvent waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distill and reuse • Alternative fuel • Chemical industry feedstock • Industrial cleaning products
	Used oils and lubricants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refine and reuse • Energy recovery
	WEEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precious metal recovery
	Rubber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and reuse • Asphalt material • Energy recovery
	Glass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and reuse • Construction aggregate

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ceramic production
Other non-ferrous metal production	Bauxite residue (red mud)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction industry (bricks / tiles) • Metal recovery
	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement and concrete production • Aggregate in road construction
	Dross / skimmings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ceramic production • Metal recovery • Cement and concrete additive • Road construction • Abrasive manufacture • Fluxing agent
	Sludge / filter cake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery • Construction materials
Sewerage	Sludges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anaerobic Digestion - Biogas for heat/ energy / fuel • Agriculture – soil conditioner and fertilizer.
	Treated effluent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation - (crops, landscaping, golf courses)
	Biosolids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture - soil conditioner and fertilizer • Land reclamation – restoration of degraded soils.
Manufacture of steel, iron, and ferro-alloys	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – aggregate and cement substitute • Agriculture – soil amendment • Marine – coral reef repair and construction
	Mill scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iron recovery or substitute for virgin iron ore • Cement production
	Dust (Zinc rich)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery and recycling
	Process gases and steam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power or steam generation • Heat recovery • Fuel
	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle / re-use • Feedstock for arc furnace
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	Waste paper / paperboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle (new paper products) • Soil amendment through composting • Animal bedding
	Ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement substitute • Soil amendment
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture – soil amendment • Energy production (biomass fuel) • Cement and bricks manufacture
	Wood residue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil amendment

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy production (biomass fuel)
	Black Liquor / other spent liquors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy recovery • Chemical recovery • Biofuel production
	Chemical waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recovery and reuse
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	Chemical residues, carbon dioxide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical sector • Energy recovery • Agriculture/horticulture • Food and drink
Pig and Poultry Farming	Manure and slurry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anaerobic Digestion • Agriculture • Land remediation
	Bedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composting and soil amendment
	Feathers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal feed • Insulation material

The above table shows the diversity of industrial symbiosis opportunities across and within sectors. This when considered with the clustering of key industries within the region means that there is considerable IS potential to be tapped into.

Awareness of IS and Potential Benefits

There are also several significant examples that highlight that industry in the region is already embracing the IS concept, which in turn provides a library of case studies to promote future activity. The region has a successful history of delivering facilitated industrial symbiosis projects which started with NISP.

Some examples of which are provided below:

- Interface Commercial Carpet Tile Reclamation & Recycling: The business model is centred around the collection of old carpet tiles, which the company then seeks to rehome within its own client base. The supplier of the carpet material is provided with certification once a home is found to reuse the items they've supplied. Interface supplies a varied range of furniture items which have been designed for reuse and repurposing at the end of their 'first life'.
- Paint360 England: Paint360 collect waste paint from clients such as the construction industry and local authorities. The paint is then recycled and reengineered to be resold into new markets. Each litre of paint supplied by the company contains a minimum of 50% recycled content.
- West Midlands Resource Reuse Network (WMRRN): The latest in a historic line of facilitated industrial symbiosis support projects, which began with the National Industrial Symbiosis Programme (NISP). The pilot project was launched in March 2024 with a focus on sand, wastewater and metal waste streams and represents a realisation of the opportunity identified in the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA) Routemap to a Circular Economy strategy.

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Initial Ideas of Where a Company Can Engage / Resources suiting IS / Processes Mapped & Targeted for IS

High level data was obtained for the main aggregated waste flows for each sector in the Midlands. A baseline mapping exercise was also undertaken to appraise industrial symbiosis potential in 2022 which formed part of the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA) business case for industrial symbiosis implementation.

Internal Data Sources Identified for Quantification / Resources identified, quantified and characterised for IS

As above, a baseline study detailed study was completed by WMCA in 2022 which identifies the main resource flows, assesses their suitability for IS activity and prioritised them accordingly. This has led to the resource streams of sand, metal and wastewater being the focal point of the pilot project launched in 2024. The rest of the Midlands region does not currently have this level of analysis available.

Check Costs, regulations and other technology specifications to be met for IS opportunities

Although no longer a member of the EU, the UK still has a landfill tax regime and supporting regional and national legislation and policy regime that supports IS delivery.

Resources Prioritised for IS with Industry Buy In / All Resources Quantified and Posted on Matching Tool

As part of the WMRRN project a direct company access resource platform, called SYNERGie® has been launched which will positively increase the visibility of available resources to participating businesses. This is limited to business in the West Midlands but with investment could have the potential to extend its geographical reach.

Overall, the Midlands has consistently proved itself to be a fertile ground for IS and I-US activities, with the latest pilot project, WMRRN, running until the end of March 2025. The analysis concluded as part of the regional study does nothing to disprove the case that this should continue into the future with the right support mechanisms in place.

6. Regional analysis: North Rhine-Westphalia – Germany

6.1. Local Context

6.1.1. Geographical landscape

North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) is located in central-west Germany, the state shares borders with Belgium, the Netherlands, and the German federal states of Hessen, Rhineland-Palatinate, and Lower Saxony. The northern part of North-Rhine Westphalia is characterized by green meadows and woodlands in the lowlands of Westphalia and the Lower Rhine region. In contrast, the southern part features the hilly regions of Sauerland, Bergisches Land, Siegerland, and parts of the Eifel. The agglomeration of Rhine-Ruhr in the center of the state consists of twenty towns and cities, making it one of the largest urbanised areas in the world. The Ruhr area promotes fast economic development based on the industrialization and the coal, iron, and steel industry. Thanks to its strategic location and a dominance of heavy industry, North Rhine-Westphalia is committed to the energy transition. The region leads in phasing out coal, set to achieve over 70% of the country's brown coal capacity

reductions by 2029³³⁷. In 2020, despite challenging site conditions and high population density, North Rhine-Westphalia also led the nation in onshore wind energy expansion becoming Europe's key energy hub³³⁸. Because of its moderate climate and typical continental European vegetation, agriculture is performed on a surface of 16,500 square kilometres, which is almost 50 % of the state. Almost 25 % of North Rhine-Westphalia is covered by forests; nearly 9,000 square kilometres. Christmas trees, for example, are cultivated on an area of 15,000 hectares in the Sauerland, which makes it the biggest area for growing Christmas trees in Germany³³⁹. NRW is traversed by forty-four rivers, with the most significant being the Rhine, the industrious Ruhr, and the winding Lippe. Among its two hundred mountains, Kahler Asten stands out as the tallest at 841.9 meters.

6.1.2. Social landscape

North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) is not only the most populous state in Germany, but it is also one of the most diverse and dynamic regions in the country. Located in the western part of Germany, NRW has a population density that is significantly higher than the national average with 18.01 million inhabitants³⁴⁰. Düsseldorf serves as the capital of NRW, known for its finance, fashion, and art scenes. It is an important economic hub, but not the largest city in the state. That title belongs to Cologne (Köln), which is renowned for its cathedral, cultural heritage, and as a major media center in Germany³⁴¹.

NRW is known for its multicultural environment. Cities like Cologne, Düsseldorf, and Dortmund feature vibrant communities representing a wide range of ethnic backgrounds. This multiculturalism is celebrated through various festivals, religious ceremonies, and culinary offerings. Historically, the region's industrial boom attracted workers from across Europe, particularly from Italy, Turkey, and the former Yugoslavia during the 1950s and 1960s. These workers were initially called "Gastarbeiter" or guest workers, many of whom settled permanently in the region. Despite being the most populous state in Germany, NRW has a growing elderly population due to low birth rates, and higher life expectancy. On the contrary, immigration has also influenced the age distribution, with younger migrants contributing to the region's demographic profile.

In terms of education, North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) is home to several of Germany's most prominent universities, making it a crucial hub for higher education and research. They contribute significantly to regional development, innovation, and the local economy. There are a total of 68 higher education

³³⁷ Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Industrie, Klimaschutz und Energie des Landes NRW, 2024. Energy and Climate Protection. Accessed: June 28, 2024 [online] Available: <https://www.wirtschaft.nrw/en/energy-and-climate-protection>

³³⁸ Ibid.

³³⁹ Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen, 2017. North Rhine-Westphalia - Regions and people. Accessed June 28, 2024 [online] Available: <https://www.landwirtschaftskammer.de/ialb2017/en/nrw/landnrw.htm>

³⁴⁰ Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder- Nordrhein-Westfalen [In German]. Accessed: July 1, 2024 [Online] Available: <https://www.statistikportal.de/en/node/121>

³⁴¹ Landeshauptstadt, Düsseldorf. Düsseldorf – seven centuries of urban development. Accessed July 2, 2024 [Online]. Available: <https://www.duesseldorf.de/int/duesseldorf-from-fishing-village-to-metropolis>

institutions, of these 68 universities, 42 are state-owned, 8 are church-owned and 18 are private universities ³⁴².

Furthermore, the state's investment in sustainability through bonds supports numerous social and environmental initiatives. The 2023 budget allocated funds to over 50 projects, prioritizing education, research, and renewable energy ³⁴³. Despite the regions' economic vitality, NRW faces several challenges such as structural changes in traditional industries, integration of immigrants, and balancing economic development with environmental sustainability. To effectively transition to a knowledge-based society, people in North Rhine-Westphalia need to develop essential skills and receive focused support, adapting to changes in business, governance, industry, and education. The region's diverse demographic landscape presents both opportunities and challenges in this development. Such as related social factors in the region with the ageing population and shortage of skilled workers, that can be compensated with young immigration and the opportunity to access to higher education.

6.1.3. Economical and Industrial landscape

The state of North Rhine–Westphalia (NRW) holds a leading position in Germany's economy, playing a prominent role nationally ³⁴⁴.

NRW plays a front role in the import and export of goods. In 2023, NRW exported €232B, making it the third largest exporter out of the country's 16 states. The main exports were pharmaceutical products, chassis, bodies, engines, etc. for motor vehicles, other articles of iron, iron sheet, metal, plastics, and machinery for electricity production, and distribution. In 2023, NRW imported €317B, making it the largest importer out of the country's 16 states. The main imports include pharmaceutical products, petroleum oil and petroleum gases, motor cars and motor caravans, and office and automatic data processing machines³⁴⁵.

NRW has seen significant economic growth, particularly due to its energy-intensive industries such as steel, metals, chemicals, cement, glass, paper, building materials, machinery, and automobile. One example of the automobile sector growth can be seen with the new production facility for electric vehicle drives established on the Ford factory site, in Cologne, by the Japanese automotive supplier Marelli. The facility manufactures 800-volt electric motors for German vehicle manufacturers.

The Rhine-Ruhr region, situated in NRW, is Germany's most relevant industrial area and serves as the primary hub for mining and energy production. NRW contributes with the highest share to Germany's raw steel production. In addition to steel, the region produces chemicals, textiles, glass, heavy machinery, electrical equipment, precision instruments, and beer. The Berg area, located in the southern part of the Rhine-Ruhr region, is known for its iron, metallurgical industries, and textiles.

³⁴² Privathoch Schulen, website. Study in North Rhine-Westphalia (Germany): All private universities at a glance. Accessed: July 1, 2024 [online] Available: www.privathochschulen.net/en/universities/north-rhine-westphalia

³⁴³ Finanzverwaltung, 2024. Land of North Rhine-Westphalia | Rating Report, SCOPE. A. Lennkh-Yunus; E. Klare; J. Zimmermann. Accessed: July 3, 2024 [Online], Available: https://www.finanzverwaltung.nrw.de/system/files/media/document/file/Scope%20Rating_0.pdf

³⁴⁴ Encyclopaedia Britannica, North Rhine–Westphalia state, Germany. Accessed: May 23, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.britannica.com/place/North-Rhine-Westphalia>

³⁴⁵ Observatory of Economic Complexity - North Rhine-Westphalia. Accessed: May 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://oec.world/en/profile/subnational_deu/north-rhine-westphalia

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However, the Ruhr region has faced challenges with high costs and declining competitiveness in its heavy industries like coal mining and metallurgy, prompting efforts to transform its economic structure and reputation³⁴⁵.

The industrial landscape and industrial sectors distribution of the NRW region are detailed in Figure 34 and Figure 35. Industrial areas are mainly concentrated in the Dortmund/Duisburg/Köln cluster which is the largest industrial cluster in Europe identified in task T2.1.

As shown in Figure 35, 3 major industrial sectors are identified along with their number of sites as a percentage of the total number of sites:

- Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment (31%)
- Waste collection, treatment, and disposal activities; materials recovery (21%)
- Manufacture of chemical, pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic (15%)

Regarding energy, Germany is aiming for 40–45% of it to be sourced from renewable sources by 2025, and a substantial 80% by 2050. North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), being Germany's largest consumer and producer of electricity, plays a crucial role in this transition. NRW is home to five of the world's top suppliers of wind turbine gearboxes and for Statkraft Europe's largest renewable energy generator. Other energy sources include photovoltaics and geothermal energy.

Despite its history of heavy industry and coal, NRW is making impressive achievements toward sustainability. It met its 2020 climate targets as early as 2017 and has plans to double its wind and photovoltaic energy production by 2030 to align with the Paris Climate Targets. In the renewable energies industry, over 46,000 employees are already working in more than 4,700 companies in NRW. Green industries are an important growing industry in NRW. The sector is responsible for the employment (2019) of about 468,000 people. Every 20th job is related to the green industry, presenting a rising trend. At 35.8 billion euros, the environmental industry accounts for about 6% of the federal state's gross value added. This sector is also relevant on the global market, where from 2010 to 2019, exports from North Rhine-Westphalia's green industry grew by an average of 1.4 % annually, reaching a volume of 11.6 billion euros in 2019³⁴⁶.

NRW presents the densest research network in Europe, creating optimal conditions for technology transfer, especially in the energy sector. With 120 institutes across over 30 universities, about 20 non-university research institutes, and the research divisions of many companies, the region is actively engaged in both studying and teaching energy technology.

A significant emphasis is placed on the transformation of the "Rheinisches Revier" coalmining region, with a crucial role played by real-world laboratory projects. One such project is the RWE "StoretoPower," which is repurposing a coal-fired power station into a high-capacity storage facility for electricity generated from renewable sources. Collaborating partners in this project include the German Aerospace Center (DLR) and Aachen University of Applied Sciences. Additionally, the TransUrbanNRW

³⁴⁶ Green Economy Report North Rhine-Westphalia 2020 - Oliver Lühr, Jannis Lambert, Richard Simpson, Myrna Sandhövel, Lukas Eiserbeck, Hanne Hagedorn, Johann Weiß, Saskia Reuschel, Stephan Kling. Accessed: May 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.prognos.com/en/project/green-economy-report-north-rhine-westphalia-2020>

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project by E.ON Energy Solutions is working on 5th generation heating networks in real-world laboratories as part of the transition towards intelligent, low-CO₂ energy solutions.

Hydrogen plays a pivotal role in meeting climate targets and modernizing North Rhine-Westphalia's economy and energy infrastructure. NRW is set to become one of Germany's largest consumers of hydrogen and is also finding the way to be the country's leading production location. In addition to attracting significant investment from local companies, North Rhine-Westphalia is drawing substantial foreign investment. An example is the American company Plug Power, which is the world's top provider of hydrogen fuel cells for electric mobility. Recently, Plug Power selected the Ruhr region as the location for its European headquarters. Enapter, a Thai company specialized in hydrogen technology, is constructing a mass production facility for highly efficient hydrogen generators in Saerback. The company aims to produce and develop modular systems to produce green hydrogen³⁴⁷.

³⁴⁷ North Rhine-Westphalia - Germany Trade & Invest - Economic Development Agency of the Federal Republic of Germany. Accessed: May 24, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://germanyworks.com/nrw/>

Figure 34: Mapping of industrial sites in the NRW region (icons from icons8.com).

- Industrial sectors (NACE Rév. 2) :
- Mining and quarrying
 - Manufacture of food products, beverage and tobacco products
 - Manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products
 - Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture, manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials
 - Manufacture of paper and paper products, printing and reproduction of recorded media
 - Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products
 - Manufacture of chemical, pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic products
 - Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products
 - Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
 - Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, electrical equipment, motor vehicles and other transport equipment
 - Manufacture of furniture; jewellery, musical instruments, toys; repair and installation of machinery and equipment
 - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply
 - Water collection, treatment and supply; sewerage; remediation activities and other waste management services
 - Construction
 - Others sectors

5.8 industrial sites per 100 km²

3 main industrial sectors :

- Treatment and coating of metals (144 sites)
- Treatment and disposal of non-hazardous waste (103 sites)
- Treatment and disposal of hazardous waste (102 sites)

Figure 35: Industrial sectors distribution and zoom into the Dortmund cluster (icons from icons8.com).

6.2. Local Policy Analysis

North-Rhine Westphalia, Germany

Overview

As a federal state of Germany with its own constitution, NRW has almost full competency over matters related to energy, industry and the circular economy, governed across its eleven ministries of parliament³⁴⁸. The region is strongly focused on reducing its GHG emissions in energy, industry, buildings and transport and is striving to be climate neutral by 2045, at the latest³⁴⁹. Whilst there is currently no state-level or national German Circular Economy strategy, NRW is advancing its circular transition and began developing a circular economy strategy in 2023³⁵⁰, aiming to be completed in 2024³⁵¹.

Policies specifically targeting I-US and their origins

No dedicated I-US policy document was identified at national or NRW state level, however several documents make reference to I(-U)S, and a further subset support I(-U)S as an enabling lever towards achieving resource efficiency goals and the decarbonisation of industry. 16 relevant policy documents at national and NRW state-level were identified using the methodology outlined above. 12 documents were selected for in-depth analysis based on key word screening (e.g. industrial, metals, waste heat), with the most relevant documents found at regional level. National documents refer to actions to be taken by the national government, whilst also referring to related actions by state governments, and sometime include initiatives looking to enable municipal level action. NRW state level documents refer to initiatives at state level and can support municipal action. These initiatives include strategies, programmes, position papers, legislation and recommendations for multiple levels of government. A complete list is provided in Annex 2: List of the documents screened for policy analysis section. The documents can be categorised as follows:

Industry-focused strategies

- Industrial policy in changed times. Safeguarding our industrial base, renewing our prosperity, boosting our economic security (2023)
- Industry is the Future. Industrial policy mission statement of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, 2019.
- Sustainability Strategy North Rhine-Westphalia (2020)

Energy and climate

³⁴⁸ The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website, No date, Ministries and Representations, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available <https://www.land.nrw/ministerien-und-vertretungen>.

³⁴⁹ NRW.Energy4Climate, Who are we? Website, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/en/about-us>.

³⁵⁰ The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, 2023, Press release, Faster pace of the circular economy strengthens North Rhine-Westphalia as a business location, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.land.nrw/pressemitteilung/mehr-tempo-bei-der-kreislaufwirtschaft-staerkt-wirtschaftsstandort-nordrhein>.

³⁵¹ Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2023, Industrial policy in changed times, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: https://www.plattform-i40.de/Redaktion/EN/Publikationen/Industry/industrial-policy-in-changing-times.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=5

- Energy Supply Strategy NRW, 2021.
- Energy Report North Rhine-Westphalia 2022.
- Carbon Management Strategy NRW, 2021.
- Process heat for a climate-neutral industry, Impulse paper, IN4climate.NRW, 2022.
- Climate-neutral industrial heat: strategies and prerequisites for transformation, Discussion paper of the heat working group, IN4climate.NRW, 2021.
- Circular Economy in materials industry: Potentials and needs framework conditions for success rich transformation, Discussion paper from the Circular Economy working group, IN4climate.NRW, 2021.

Raw materials

- German Resource Efficiency Programme (2020 - 2023)
- Federal Government's raw material strategy (2020)
- Status quo of recycling in metal production and processing in Germany, the German Mineral Resources Agency (DERA), 2023

Main Actors with work relevant for Industrial(-Urban) Symbiosis

Based on the policy analysis, the **Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU)** is a primary national government department setting a vision for governmental support of I(-U)S. BMU set out the German Resource Efficiency Programme 2020 – 2023 (REP)³⁵², which whilst not yet revised past 2023, includes “Industrial symbiosis” as an instrument towards resource efficiency which should be supported by government, without going into detail of specific measures or targets. In terms of providing funding to industry to implement I-US, the **Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control** is providing grants and loans to industry to invest in use of waste heat between industry and district heating. The **municipal (district) government of Arnsberg**; located within NRW, is also involved in providing this funding.

At the regional level, ministries are founding and implementing local initiatives which can support I-US. The **Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Transport (MUNV)** is leading the development of the NRW Circular Economy strategy, as well as running the CircularCities.NRW funding initiative, funded by the European regional funding programme (ERDF/JTF program NRW 2021-2027)³⁵³. Alongside the **Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Protection**, MUNV is also leading the GreenEconomy.IN.NRW funding programme for entrepreneurs regarding innovative solutions to transitioning to the circular economy³⁵⁴.

³⁵² Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2023, The German Resource Efficiency Programme III 2020 – 2023 Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: https://www.plattform-i40.de/Redaktion/EN/Publikationen/Industry/industrial-policy-in-changing-times.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=5.

³⁵³ IN.NRW, The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website, No date, Circular Economy - CircularCities.NRW, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.in.nrw/massnahmen/circular-cities-nrw>.

³⁵⁴ IN.NRW, The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website, No date, Innovation competition GreenEconomy.IN.NRW, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available <https://www.in.nrw/massnahmen/green-economy>.

In terms of setting a vision for regional industrial investment in I(-U)S, the **Ministry of Economy, Industry, Climate Protection and Energy (WIKE)**, formally the Ministry of Economy, Innovation, Digitalisation and Energy, published the Industrial policy mission statement of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia 2019, in which the ministry sets out to “support cross-industry and cross-sector approaches to the development of cross-industry innovations and industrial symbiosis”. WIKE also leads the NRW Circular Value Creation Round Table network. **The State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection (LANUV)** has carried out research to provide an evidence base to spotlight the huge potential benefits of implementing I-US in NRW, specifically regarding usage of waste-heat between industries and district heating.

Working closely with LANUV is another key actor - the state-founded agency **NRW.Energy4Climate**, which was set up to address energy and climate protection in the region. NRW.Energy4Climate acts as a researcher and informer of various stakeholder groups and its advocacy covers I-US-related actions. Guides and recommendations published to date include focus on reuse of waste industrial heat by other industry and for local district heating, namely Process heat for a climate-neutral industry³⁵⁵, and Climate-neutral industrial heat: strategies and prerequisites for transformation³⁵⁶, directed towards policy makers, industry and municipalities alike. In addition, best practice examples of symbiotic collaborations are published e.g. *Cooperation TRIMENT Aluminium SE and Iqony Fernwärme GmbH to use industrial heat*³⁵⁷, and funding opportunities and advice provided to industry and municipalities wanting to implement such measures.

Funding Mechanisms and other support instruments for I-US

The following funding and support instruments relevant for I-US are provided at national and state level often supported by some EU funding, directed towards municipalities and industry. These can be grouped into three categories:

1. There are a number of funding programmes and resources available to increase **resource-efficiency** in NRW, a concept which includes implementing I-US to reduce dependency on virgin materials. To support the cities of NRW to become more resource efficient, the funding programme "Circular Economy - CircularCities.NRW" launched 2024, for which a total of around 27 million euros in state and EU funding is available³⁵⁸. In parallel to support industry to innovate and take action, a Resource Efficiency Consulting Programme launched by WIKE is providing over 4.1 million euros in support to Industry, from EU and State funds as part of the ERDF/JTF program North Rhine-Westphalia 2021-2027³⁵⁹. The Efficiency Agency NRW

³⁵⁵ NRW.Energy4Climate, 2022, Process heat for a climate-neutral industry, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/energiebedarf-der-industrie/industrielle-abwaerme>

³⁵⁶ NRW.Energy4Climate, 2021, Climate-neutral industrial heat: strategies and prerequisites for the transformation, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/energiebedarf-der-industrie/industrielle-abwaerme>

³⁵⁷ NRW.Energy4Climate, No date, Web Article, Waste heat from aluminium production, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/praxisbeispiele-industrietransformation/abwaerme-aus-der-aluminiumproduktion>

³⁵⁸ IN.NRW, The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website, No date, Circular Economy - CircularCities.NRW, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://www.in.nrw/massnahmen/circular-cities-nrw>

³⁵⁹ Ministry of Economic Affairs, Industry, Climate Action and Energy of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website: Resource Efficiency Consulting. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.efre.nrw.de/wege-zur-foerderung/foerderungen-in-2021-2027/ressourceneffizienzberatung/>

(EFA), state-founded in 1998, is also providing supports for medium-sized companies in NRW to implement resource-efficiency. Services include best practice case studies in NRW, an advisory service, events, training and workshops in developing new circular business models³⁶⁰. At the national level, the German Centre for Resource Efficiency (VDI-ZRE) is providing industry-specific information on enabling resource efficiency and the circular economy in the form of guides, videos and tools, however there is no apparent explicit mention of I-US to date³⁶¹.

2. There is also available funding on the topic of **innovation** which can support I-US. For example, the broad GreenEconomy.IN.NRW funding programme launched by Minister of Economy and Climate Protection Mona Neubaur is earmarked to provide a total of 100 million euros from EU and state funding (ERDF/JTF programme NRW) to support solutions to achieve the circular economy and climate adaptation in a competitive manner³⁶².
3. The form of I-US most supported by policy in NRW is related to reusing unavoidable waste heat in other industries or as district heating. Subsequently there is a selection of financial supports for the use of **waste heat in heating networks**. The NRW ministry is providing private industrial partners, as well as public and private heat network operators funding to support the use of waste heat in heating networks³⁶³. The Förder.Navi from NRW.Energy4Climate provides an overview of all current funding opportunities for waste heat extraction and utilisation projects as of March 2023³⁶⁴. In terms of additional supports, the heat registers available via NRW.Energy4Climate provides an overview of which potential waste heat sources are available in a given network and which heating network is located near a given industrial site, thereby allowing planning for new symbiosis. Further background information including planning status³⁶⁵ is also provided³⁶⁵.

Exchange support instruments:

NRW's Circular Value Creation Round Table was set up in 2018, co-initiated by the regional government to create the central platform for circular economy in NRW. The aim of the group is to establish an exchange and coordination of activities between local actors including companies, educational institutions and municipalities, representing different positions in the value chain, and

³⁶⁰ Ministry of the Environment, Nature and Transport of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia is part of the government of the German state of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website: The Efficiency Agency NRW. . Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.umwelt.nrw.de/themen/umwelt/wer-macht-was/effizienz-agentur-nrw>

³⁶¹ Resource Efficiency Centre, Website, No date, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.resource-germany.com/>

³⁶² IN.NRW, The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, Website, No date, Innovation competition GreenEconomy.IN.NRW, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available <https://www.in.nrw/massnahmen/green-economy>

³⁶³ NRW.Energy4Climate, Website, No date, Industrial Waste Heat, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/energiebedarf-der-industrie/industrielle-abwaerme>

³⁶⁴ NRW.Energy4Climate Förder-Navi, Website, No date, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://tool.energy4climate.nrw/foerder-navi>

³⁶⁵ NRW.Energy4Climate, Website, No date, Industrial Waste Heat, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/energiebedarf-der-industrie/industrielle-abwaerme>

thus develop a basis for joint circular economy projects and strategies in NRW. Activities include providing funding for such projects and organising events on locally relevant circular topics³⁶⁶.

NRW.Energy4Climate work in collaboration with many organisations to set up working groups of mixed stakeholders on the topic of energy, climate and industry to bring together the opinions and needs of industry, research and municipalities. IN4climate.NRW is a further connected thinktank platform launched in 2018, which offers a space for public and private stakeholders to collectively develop innovative strategies for a climate-neutral industry in NRW. In addition, the state of North Rhine-Westphalia is launching a new sustainability portal to transform NRW into the leading climate and environmentally friendly industrial region in Europe³⁶⁷.

A critical reading of the policy: the vision of a resource efficient, decarbonised manufacturing industry in NRW

General context

NRW faces a particular challenge and responsibility to transition away from fossil fuels, with its industry accounting for around one third of Germany's GHG emissions³⁶⁸. Given the major process industries present, NRW is increasingly focused on resource efficiency (e.g. metals, energy, water) and overall transitioning to a circular economy as part of its decarbonisation plans. Supportive policy for I-US can be viewed through the lens of these collective ambitions to be a climate neutral industrial hub by 2045, a leader in resource efficiency and to create a strong, innovative future industrial economy. These goals are reflected also at national level, with the ambition to reduce the country's overall energy consumption by 26.5% compared to 2008 by latest 2030³⁶⁹.

Industrial(-urban) symbiosis as a pathway to a circular industrial resource management and climate-neutral energy supply

I-US is supported and framed by national policy as one of the means towards improving resource efficiency in Germany. The need to generally support industry in developing synergies is prevalent, however specific actions are not laid out at national level. One exception being The German Resource Efficiency Programme (REP) stating national government can promote I-US via supporting competence centres for commercial and industrial networks. The REP is noted as sometimes being somewhat detached from state or municipal-level government strategy planning³⁷⁰, however research and

³⁶⁶ Round table, Circular Value Creation North Rhine-Westphalia; Website, No date, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.zirkulaere-wertschoepfung-nrw.de/zirkulaere-wertschoepfung/>

³⁶⁷ NRW.innovativ, 2022, Website: The state of North Rhine-Westphalia is launching a new sustainability portal. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://nrwinnovativ.de/en/the-state-of-north-rhine-westphalia-is-launching-a-new-sustainability-portal/>

³⁶⁸ The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, 2020, Sustainability Strategy North Rhine-Westphalia, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://nachhaltigkeit.nrw.de/en/sustainability-in-north-rhine-westphalia/sustainability-strategy-nrw-2020>

³⁶⁹ DLA PIPER, 2023, Website, Web Article: The state of North Rhine-Westphalia is launching a new sustainability portal. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.dlapiper.com/en-de/insights/publications/2023/05/energieeffizienzgesetz-enefg-neue-gesetzliche-anforderungen-fur-unternehmen>

³⁷⁰ Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action, 2023, The German Resource Efficiency Programme III 2020 – 2023 Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: https://www.plattform-i40.de/Redaktion/EN/Publikationen/Industry/industrial-policy-in-changing-times.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=5

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subsequent efforts have been made since the 2016 programme to better involve municipalities in the programme development, and to provide practical examples of resource-efficiency actions that can be implemented at the local level – resulting in the 2020 *Resource policy at local and regional level(kommRess)* guide. This guide includes IS as an example of implementing resource efficiency, as well as two of its benefits for participating companies - resource savings and improved competitiveness³⁷¹. Further brief mention of consideration of the value of investing in I-US is found in the objectives and indicators of the German Sustainability strategy supporting resource efficiency, and the Federal Government's raw material strategy which includes an action to reduce obstacles to greater use of raw material substitution in industrial manufacturing processes.

Within regional policy, more specific supports to develop I-US are found within the scope of decarbonising industry and its heat and energy usage. Developed by the now replaced NRW Ministry of Economic Affairs, Innovation, Digitalisation and Energy, the Industrial policy mission statement of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia 2019 includes supporting “cross-industry and cross-sector approaches to the development of cross-industrial innovations”, as an action towards climate protection in the region. As outlined above in “Funding Mechanisms and other support instruments for I-US” there is a lot of funding available from regional level for resource efficiency and thus potentially usable for I-US. Symbiotic exchange of unavoidable industrial waste heat with other industrial processes as well as for district heating, is specifically supported at regional level. This appears to be a key action as a part of a wider climate-neutral industrial heat transition. The State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection (LANUV) published a study in 2019 showing that thanks to the high concentration of production industries in NRW, available waste heat exceeded the local district heating demand by more than three times the amount. Advice on future-proofing waste heat projects and considering emerging sources of waste heat from the hydrogen are provided by NRW.Energy4Climate³⁷², as well as funding opportunities for heat exchange projects. The Energy Supply Strategy NRW 2021 includes brief mention of strategically utilising waste heat potential, as well as the latest Energy Report North Rhine-Westphalia 2022³⁷³.

Developing waste heat usage is further supported via EU and German legislation. Whilst existing district heating systems are largely based on fossil fuels, according to Section 29 of the Heat Planning Act, “*from 2030 at least 30 percent and from 2040 at least 80 percent of the heat in the German heating network must come from renewable energies and/or unavoidable waste heat*³⁷⁴. The Energy Efficiency Act obliges companies to avoid waste heat. Unavoidable waste heat must be used by the

³⁷¹ Umwelt Bundesamt, 2020, Resource Policy Municipal and Regional Level, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1410/publikationen/2021-12-10_texte_170-2020_ressourcenpolitik_auf_kommunaler_und_regionaler_ebene_kommress.pdf

³⁷² NRW.Energy4Climate, Website, No date, Industrial Waste Heat, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/energiebedarf-der-industrie/industrielle-abwaerme>

³⁷³ Ministry of Economic Affairs, Industry, Climate Action and Energy of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia, 2022, Energy Report North Rhine-Westphalia. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.wirtschaft.nrw/system/files/media/document/file/energiebericht-nordrhein-westfalen-2022.pdf>

³⁷⁴ NRW.Energy4Climate, Website, No date, Industrial Waste Heat, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.energy4climate.nrw/industrie-produktion/energiebedarf-der-industrie/industrielle-abwaerme>

company itself or made available for external use (Section 16), whereby data on the waste heat generated must be reported to the Federal Office for Energy Efficiency (Section 17)³⁷⁵.

It is interesting to note that within the variety of process industry in NRW, industrial symbiosis is already well established in the production of aluminium, cement and concrete, as well as the chemical and steel industry amongst others (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Secondary raw material and by-product use in the aluminium production and the cement and concrete industry in Germany, Source: page 14, Circular Economy Working Group, IN4climate.NRW.

According to a position paper on the circular economy developed by a working group of mixed industry stakeholders established by IN4climate.NRW, to date IS within the basic materials industry has developed for economic reasons, as opposed to any particular policy. However, great potential remains regarding greater reuse of residual materials and waste between industry and support in alleviating systemic barriers are needed for this³⁷⁶. As visible from policy, transitioning heating and energy infrastructure requires greater support from government from the beginning than industry-to-industry material exchange, suggesting this could be why heat exchange currently remains the most visibly supported form of I-US in NRW to date.

Sectors targeting by the policy documents relevant to I-US

At the regional level, use of waste industrial heat for district heating is the main I-US exchange focused on across policy. Within the diversity of industrial processes in NRW, the chemical and steel industries are amongst the most energy-intensive, therefore a focus on reducing energy emissions and resource

³⁷⁵ Bundesministeriums der Justiz sowie des Bundesamts für Justiz, 2023, Law to increase energy efficiency in Germany (Energy Efficiency Act - EnEFG). Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/enefg/EnEFG.pdf>

³⁷⁶ IN4climate.NRW, 2021, Circular Economy in materials industry: Potentials and needs framework conditions for success rich transformation, Discussion paper from the Circular Economy working group. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: https://www.energy4climate.nrw/fileadmin/Service/Publikationen/Ergebnisse_IN4climate.NRW/2021/in4climatenrw-diskussionspapier-circular-economy-sekundaerrohstoffe-grundstoffindustrie_01.pdf

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efficiency within these industries is found in the NRW Strategy for Sustainability³⁷⁷. The work carried out via IN4climate.NRW focuses on the four highest-emitting sectors in NRW which are energy, industry, buildings and transport. Cumulatively these are responsible for more than 90 percent of greenhouse gas emissions in NRW.

Challenges to I-US

Challenges highlighted relating to advancing secondary material usage and resource efficiency (including I-US) in NRW's industries are as follows³⁷⁸;

- Large gaps in published data on material flows of raw materials at state and federal level,
- Technology-development gaps for improved separation of metal, glass, organic and aggregate residues, amongst other process industries, to allow IS,
- A lack of digitalisation for information transfer in NRW, as well as across Germany.,
- Missing regulatory supports and product standards to allow secondary material usage e.g. no regulation on the use of recycled sand in concrete and on the use of crushed sand fines as (main) cement,
- Sufficient regional availability of secondary material to replace virgin material needs, in part due to export of scrap waste,
- The shift away from fossil-based or contaminant-heavy process inputs means a change in availability of residual materials for use to replace virgin materials in other processes. This affects the cement industry in particular, but also the rust slag in the aluminium industry,
- Subsidies are often provided for use of raw materials in the processing sectors, hindering competitiveness of secondary materials (OECD 2019)
- Unreliable demand for recycled materials due to lack of legal requirement for use in process industries.

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving industrial symbiosis

Analysis of relevant policies suggest that in the case of NRW, public authorities are playing a number of roles to enable I-US. Firstly, municipalities are transferring the national vision of I(-U)S into local action, as indicated in the *2020 Resource policy at local and regional level(kommRes)* guide for implementing the German Resource Efficiency Programme (REP)³⁷⁹. It appears that leveraging the ownership of public infrastructure and utilities is a powerful tool municipalities are using in NRW to

³⁷⁷ The State government of North Rhine-Westphalia, 2020, Sustainability Strategy North Rhine-Westphalia, Accessed 12 June 2024, Available: <https://nachhaltigkeit.nrw.de/en/sustainability-in-north-rhine-westphalia/sustainability-strategy-nrw-2020>

³⁷⁸ IN4climate.NRW, 2021, Circular Economy in materials industry: Potentials and needs framework conditions for success rich transformation, Discussion paper from the Circular Economy working group. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: https://www.energy4climate.nrw/fileadmin/Service/Publikationen/Ergebnisse_IN4climate.NRW/2021/in4climatenrw-diskussionspapier-circular-economy-sekundaerrohstoffe-grundstoffindustrie_01.pdf

³⁷⁹ Umwelt Bundesamt, 2020, Resource Policy Municipal and Regional Level, Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1410/publikationen/2021-12-10_texte_170-2020_ressourcenpolitik_auf_kommunaler_und_regionaler_ebene_kommress.pdf

invest in the necessary infrastructure for district heating and procure waste industrial heat for use, amongst other exchanges. A key example being Stadtwerke Düsseldorf using industrial waste heat from the company Henkel, for district heating since 2024³⁸⁰. Whilst it is clear that the regional government of NRW and its agencies, namely NRW.Energy4Climate, play a key role in facilitating exchange of relevant stakeholders, local government can be interpreted as an important facilitation bridge to implementing symbiotic exchanges between and with industry in NRW.

6.3. I-US Potential Analysis

6.3.1. Material Flows Mapping

Industrial Waste Generation

The material flows analysis was conducted using the E-PRTR database. Figure 37 and Figure 38 respectively illustrate the total and disposed industrial waste flows in the NRW region. Each year, 27.5 Mtons of waste are generated in the region, 9.9 Mtons of which is disposed. Without considering the waste treatment and disposal sectors, the production of electricity is the main emitting sector with an amount of waste of 5.72 Mtons/year (20.8% of total waste). The next biggest emitting sectors are manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys, manufacture of other organic basic chemicals, and sewerage. These four sectors represent around 31.3% of the total waste flows on the territory, and when adding the waste treatment and disposal sector waste flows, then 78.8% of the regional flows are accounted for.

Regarding the disposed waste, production of electricity is still the most emitting sector with 5.2 Mtons of disposed waste (52.5% of the total disposed waste), either landfilled, buried or incinerated without energy recovery. Then, 469 and 427 ktons are disposed respectively by the manufacture of lime and plaster and the sewerage sectors (4.7 and 4.3% of total disposed waste) Figure 39 illustrates all the waste flows in the area and their sectorial distribution.

³⁸⁰ Energate Messenger, 2023, Web Article: Public utility company Stadtwerke Düsseldorf uses waste heat from Henkel. Accessed June 04, 2024, Available: <https://www.energate-messenger.com/news/235811/public-utility-company-stadtwerke-duesseldorf-uses-waste-heat-from-henkel>

Figure 37: Total waste flows in the NRW region.

9.9 Mtons of disposed waste each year

59.9 % recovering rate

- Around 5.2 Mtons/year of waste disposed by the production of electricity sector (52.5% of total disposed waste)
- 469 and 428 ktons disposed respectively by the manufacture of lime and plaster and the sewerage sectors (4.7 and 4.3% of total disposed waste)

Figure 38: Disposed waste flow in the NRW region.

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Figure 39: Waste flows diagram and waste sectorial analysis in the NRW region (quantities in kt in the table, icons from icons8.com)

I-US Flow Mapping

The table below shows the main sectors responsible for waste material flows in the NRW region. Waste processing companies have been discounted from this analysis, as although required actors in managing the flows of waste, the data in its current form prevents us understanding what these waste processes and associated materials are specifically, and therefore their potential end uses. This is not an issue with other sectoral waste streams as we can use ISL experience of IS delivery globally to list typical associated resource flows against each specific sector.

Significant volumes of waste can be seen to be going into recovery operations, with the exception of electricity production and the manufacture of lime and plaster. With much waste already being recovered, the commercial viability for industrial symbiosis is likely to be inhibited, as it will have lower associated rates of cost. One of the largest areas of potential opportunity is the relatively high volume of sewage treatment material going to disposal and not to recovery activities, where energy recovery is a widely implemented solution in a number of countries for sewage treatment solids.

Table 11 Primary Waste Flow Data for North Rhine-Westphalia

NACE sector	Waste destined for disposal (tons/year)	Waste destined for recovery (tons/year)	Total of waste (tons/year)
Production of electricity	5,203,356	514,508	5,717,863
Treatment and disposal of hazardous waste	570,016	2,604,223	3,174,238
Manufacture of lime and plaster	469,102	42	469,144
Sewerage	427,983	187,797	615,779
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys	303,444	1,176,303	1,479,747
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	254,307	501,226	755,533
Other personal service activities n.e.c.	225,670	105,690	331,360
Lead, zinc and tin production	197,721	52,002	249,723

Collection of non-hazardous waste	140,799	636,466	777,265
Manufacture of dyes and pigments	138,580	58,465	197,045
Mining of lignite	106,189	20,058	126,247
Casting of iron	80,571	496,823	577,393
Manufacture of sugar	73,893	88,224	162,117
Manufacture of pesticides and other agrochemical products	55,174	57,097	112,271
Manufacture of refined petroleum products	40,499	103,440	143,939
Steam and air conditioning supply	37,872	73,230	111,102
Manufacture of plastics in primary forms	33,116	22,406	55,522
Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products	30,293	20,692	50,984
Manufacture of household and sanitary goods and of toilet requisites	28,075	49,822	77,897
Casting of steel	22,534	27,497	50,031

The priority sectors with the most significant waste volumes in the NRW region have been identified as:

- Production of electricity
- Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys
- Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals
- Sewerage
- Casting of iron
- Manufacture of paper and paperboard
- Manufacture of lime and plaster

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The table below details the main high-level byproduct and waste outputs expected for each of these sectors in turn.

Table 12 North Rhine-Westphalia Priority Sector Flow Analysis

Sector	No. of sites	Outputs /By-products
Production of electricity (coal)	50	Fly ash
		Bottom ash
		Sludge
		Waste water
Manufacture of basic iron, steel, and ferro-alloys	29	Slag
		Mill scale
		Dust (Zinc rich)
		Process gases and steam
		Scrap metal
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	61	Chemical residues
		Carbon dioxide
Sewerage	45	Sludges
		Treated effluent
		Biosolids
Casting of Iron	25	Molding sand and clay
		Waste metal
		Used foundry sand
		Wastewater and process water
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	24	Waste paper / paperboard
		Ash
		Sludge
		Wood residue
		Black Liquor / other spent liquors
		Chemical waste
Manufacture of lime and plaster	4	Carbon dioxide
		Lime kiln dust
		Limestone fines
		Waste gypsum and gypsum dust

		Carbon dioxide
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6.3.2. I-US Infrastructure Mapping

Figure 40, Figure 41 and Figure 42 illustrate the key infrastructure for I-US in the NRW region.

In terms of transport infrastructures, the region has 6 785 km (0.33 km/km²) of motorways and around 12 702 km (0.63 km/km²) of railways. For the energy infrastructures, 66.4 and 29.2% of the electricity are produced from coal and gas plants respectively while waste (1.4%), hydro (1.2%), oil (0.7%), other sources (0.6%), biomass (0.3%) and solar (0.1%) share the rest of the mix. Using modelling data from the HRE4 project, 66.5 PJ/year and 32.5 PJ/year of excess heat from respectively industrial sites and WWTP have been identified. For the heat demands, urban area would consume around 403.2 PJ/year. The heat sources registered in the HRE4 project are not exhaustive, which explains the discrepancy with the LANUV 2019 study cited above. Regarding the education, 23 universities (science and technical schools) are in the region. The region also shows a high innovation appeal with 4 I-US demo cases:

- [ECO2Fuel](#)
- [intelWATT](#)
- [MefCO2](#)
- [REFHYNE](#)

0.33 km of motorway per km²

0.63 km of railway per km²

Figure 40: Transport infrastructures in the NRW region.

Figure 41: Electricity production and excess heat in the NRW region (icons from icons8.com).

1.1 universities per 1000 km²

*Only technical and science schools are considered

4 I-US demo cases identified

Figure 42: Education and innovation in the NRW region (icons from icons8.com).

6.3.3. Regional readiness assessment for I-US and general conclusions

The following table outlines the main industrial symbiosis synergy opportunities available for each identified resource in turn, from the analysis in section 6.3.1.

Table 13 Industrial Symbiosis Opportunities in North Rhine-Westphalia

Sector	Outputs /By-products	Uses
Electricity Generation (assuming coal generation)	Fly ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – cement substitute in concrete production. • Agriculture – soil improvement
	Bottom ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – aggregate substitute in concrete, road bases, embankments and structural fill • Cement substitute • Brick and ceramic manufacture • Land reclamation • Agriculture – soil improvement • Water treatment – filtration medium
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction materials • Agriculture – soil improvement
	Waste water / cooling water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-use in cooler system • Agriculture and landscaping, irrigation
Manufacture of steel, iron and ferro-alloys	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – aggregate and cement substitute • Agriculture – soil amendment • Marine – coral reef repair and construction
	Mill scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iron recovery or substitute for virgin iron ore • Cement production
	Dust (Zinc rich)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery and recycling
	Process gases and steam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power or steam generation • Heat recovery • Fuel
	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle / re-use • Feedstock for arc furnace
Manufacture of other organic basic chemicals	Chemical residues, carbon dioxide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical sector • Energy recovery • Agriculture/horticulture • Food and drink
Sewerage	Sludges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anaerobic Digestion - Biogas for heat/ energy / fuel • Agriculture – soil conditioner and fertiliser.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological extraction of nutrients such as phosphorus
	Treated effluent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation - (crops, landscaping, golf courses)
	Biosolids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture - soil conditioner and fertiliser • Land reclamation – restoration of degraded soils. • Nutrient extraction – phosphorous etc.
Iron casting	Moulding sand and clay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land reclamation (fill material) • Construction (aggregate for road bases and building foundations etc)
	Waste metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle or remelt and re-use. • Feedstock for Electric Arc Furnace
	Used foundry sand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reclaim and re-use in foundry (requires chemical treatment) • Construction (backfill, embankments etc)
	Wastewater and process water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wastewater treatment for re-use.
Manufacture of paper and paperboard	Waste paper / paperboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle (new paper products) • Soil amendment through composting • Animal bedding
	Ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement substitute • Soil amendment
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture – soil amendment • Energy production (biomass fuel) • Cement and bricks manufacture
	Wood residue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil amendment • Energy production (biomass fuel)
	Black Liquor / other spent liquors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy recovery • Chemical recovery • Biofuel production
	Chemical waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recovery and reuse
Manufacture of lime and plaster	Carbon dioxide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food & drink industry (i.e. carbonation of drinks) • Chemical industry (i.e. production of chemicals)
	Lime kiln dust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction (soil stabiliser) • Agriculture (soil amendment) • Road construction (filler in asphalt mixtures)
	Limestone fines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filler in asphalt and concrete • Aggregate in road base or other construction applications

	Waste gypsum and gypsum dust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture (soil amendment) • Production of plasterboard • Cement production
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The analysis for industrial symbiosis matching potential shows a good mix of high value and low value end uses, all with proven case study examples to give confidence that this could be replicated within region.

Awareness of IS and Potential Benefits

There are several significant examples that highlight that industry in the region is already embracing the IS concept, which in turn provides a library of case studies to promote future activity. These include a number IS demonstration sites which are identified in the maps provided.

Some further examples of IS activity within Westphalia are provided below:

- Chemiapark Marl, in NRW, is one of the largest chemical sites in Germany. There are approximately 100 production plants on the site, and they are all linked in a tightly integrated material and energy network. North Rhine-Westphalia has a ‘Trilateral strategy for the chemical industry³⁸¹’ which is driving the regions transition towards a more circular and sustainable chemical sector.
- [Circular Economy - Evonik Industries](#) (located at Chemipark Marl) is a speciality chemicals company that is embedding a circular economy approach into its raw material selection. This includes bio and non-biobased wastes and byproducts from processes such as olive oil production. The company also uses feedstocks obtained through mattress recycling activities.
- [In4Climate](#): In4Climate is a cluster opportunity involving the chemical, steel and cement industries seeking to find opportunities to collaborate, share resources and move towards being ‘climate neutral’. At its heart is activity seeking to transition to hydrogen fuel usage and using byproducts and residues from industry as its source. This includes symbiosis such as furnace slag from steel production going into cement clinker production and caustic soda from chlorine production into the aluminium sector.

Initial Ideas of Where a Company Can Engage / Resources suiting IS / Processes Mapped & Targeted for IS

The mapping provided within this regional analysis gives some high-level indication of where resources suitable for IS can be located. It also shows where the main material flows going to disposal are located and therefore those with the highest cost to industry. Those resources will be the ones which represent a strong commercial driver for diverting into IS end uses. Sewerage sludge, particularly in relation to energy and nutrient recovery, would appear to be an area of high opportunity,

Internal Data Sources Identified for Quantification / Resources identified, quantified and characterised for IS

³⁸¹ Trilateral Strategy For The Chemical Industry; Accessed June 2024; Available at: https://www.wirtschaft.nrw/sites/default/files/documents/trilateral_strategy_chemical_industry.pdf

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High level resource flow data is available, as it is for other regions, which gives a good indication of the main material flows aligned to priority sectors. The lack of granularity and visibility does inhibit its usefulness for the purpose of informing IS synergy opportunities and is something which could be improved (as for all the regions assessed).

Check Costs, regulations and other technology specifications to be met for IS opportunities

As an EU member state, the legislation supporting IS has already been adopted at a national level. Local policy does not specifically address IS activity but does provide a framework for supporting key sectors and circularity. A landfill tax regime is in place which will provide fiscal incentives for IS synergies.

Resources Prioritised for IS with Industry Buy In / All Resources Quantified and Posted on Matching Tool

The research undertaken for this regional appraisal has located no platform or existing mechanism for making resource location and availability more visible to industry. This is an opportunity and could in part be addressed through the initiatives addressing the chemical clusters in the region with a view to acting as an initial pilot application for a regional platform supporting industrial symbiosis.

The analysis presented demonstrates that the component parts are in place for an industrial symbiosis network to be established. Sector clusters with associated waste resource flows with well-established end uses, supporting academic and research institutions and a policy framework which in general is supportive of IS activity. Improvements could be made in linking sectors to realise help these cross-sector opportunities, making waste resource data more visible and detailed, and developing specific regional policy to further drive IS uptake.

7. Regional analysis: Silesian Voivodeship – Poland

7.1. Local Context

7.1.1. Geographical landscape

The Silesian Voivodeship, one of Poland's sixteen provinces, is located in the south of the country. It borders four Polish voivodeships: Opolskie to the west, Łódzkie to the north, Świętokrzyskie to the northeast, and Małopolskie to the east.

Covering over 12,294 km², the Silesian Voivodeship constitutes nearly 3.9% of Poland's total area³⁸². The region features the Silesian Upland (Wyżyna Śląska) in the center and northwest, and the Krakowsko-Częstochowska Upland (Jura Krakowsko-Częstochowska) in the northeast. The southern border is defined by the Beskid Mountains (Beskid Śląski and Beskid Żywiecki). The northern region is predominantly flat and rural, while the mountainous south serves as a greenbelt. The hilly center of Silesia is heavily industrialized, housing the majority of the population.

The main rivers in the voivodeship include the Vistula, which originates in the Beskid Śląski, as well as the Odra, Warta, Pilica, Mała Panew, Liswarta, and Soła. Forests cover 31.7% of the voivodeship, compared to the national average of 28.4%. The most densely wooded areas are Tarnogórski (51.6%), Lubliniecki (51%), and Żywiecki (50.8%). The largest forested areas are located along the Mała Panew

³⁸² Śląskie Voivodeship, Geography, Accessed: May 21, 2024, Available: https://slaskie.pl/content/1293523792_2010-12-28?page=34

River, in the Beskidy Mountains, and northwest of Rybnik. The region counts with many natural resources, such as: deposits of coal, zinc, lead, methane, natural gas, marl, limestone, aggregates, as well as therapeutic, thermal and mineral waters³⁸³.

The climate of Silesian Voivodeship is transitional, influenced by both the warm marine climate of Western Europe and the continental climate from the East. This results in the collision of moist air masses from the Atlantic and dry air masses from the continent above the region, causing significant day-to-day weather variability and marked differences in seasonal conditions from year to year. The region's uplands and mountains contribute to heavy rainfall and considerable variation in local climatic conditions.

7.1.2. Social landscape

Silesia, a vibrant region nestled in the southern part of Poland, stands as a region rich in history, culture, and economic significance. Its landscape, both geographical and socio-economic, tells a story of resilience and transformation through the ages. Home to over 4.4 million people, Silesia stands as Poland's most populated and urbanized area (comprising 12.5% of the whole population of the country), with a staggering 76% of its inhabitants residing in bustling cities³⁸⁴. These urban centers, such as the province's Capital Katowice, and others such as Gliwice, and Sosnowiec, serve as cultural and industrial hubs while rural areas maintain their distinct charm, rooted in agrarian traditions and community bonds.

The demographic diversity of Silesia is reflected in its mosaic of ethnic groups including Polish, German, Czech, and Silesians, who converge here reflecting centuries of cultural interplay shaped by historical events such as border changes and conflicts at the crossroads of Central Europe, along with waves of internal and external migration. Such migration has been driven by the allure of employment opportunities and urban life that came along with the industrialization of Silesia, which can be traced back to the 18th and 19th centuries when the region experienced rapid economic growth driven by the exploitation of its rich natural resources, particularly coal and iron ore. The abundance of coal reserves, combined with advancements in mining technology, enabled Silesia to become a major producer of coal, which was essential for powering steam engines, heating homes, and fueling industrial processes. The region's coal mines have also supplied raw materials for the iron and steel industry, which flourished alongside coal mining. The growth of the coal mining and metallurgical industries spurred rapid urbanization and population growth in Silesia.

To combat labor exploitation and poor working conditions that came along with industrialization, strong traditions of community engagement were formed, and civic participation rose, characterized by solidarity and mutual support, leading to social capital flourishing in Silesia, thus fostering social cohesion, supporting vulnerable populations, and driving local development initiatives. However, today Silesia is facing a demographic challenge of a decline number of inhabitants and a process of rapid aging of the population, as a consequence of the low rate of natural increase and of emigration to other regions or abroad, particularly in communities that rely on coal. "By 2030, the percentage of

³⁸³ Polska Multimedialna, Slaskie, Accessed: May 21, 2024, Available: <https://slaskie.polskamultimedialna.pl/en/wielkopolskie-2/>

³⁸⁴ European Commission, Regional Profile. Silesia, Poland, 2023, Accessed: March 20, 2024, Available: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-12/Silesia_2023.pdf

working-age people (aged 15-64) in the population of the voivodeship will fall to 62% – almost 10 p.p. lower than in the year 2000.”³⁸⁵

The region enjoys relatively high literacy rates and a skilled workforce, especially in the field of medical, natural, exact, and technical sciences, bolstered by a well-developed educational infrastructure, comprising numerous universities, technical schools, and vocational training centres such as the University of Silesia, Silesian University of Technology, and the University of Economics in Katowice. It is important to draw attention to the number of academic teachers employed in technical universities, which places the Silesian Voivodeship among the national leaders, and the large number of students at technical universities (3rd place in the country). However, between 2016 and 2018, the number of academic teachers employed at higher technical schools in the Silesian Voivodeship decreased by 6.6%, while the percentage of students in technical and natural sciences decreased by over 7%³⁸⁶.

Similarly, healthcare, a cornerstone of well-being, is characterized by a well-developed system, with a network of hospitals, clinics, and healthcare facilities. Nevertheless, challenges persist particularly regarding infrastructure and allocation of resources, as well as addressing disparities in educational and healthcare attainment, especially in rural and less affluent areas, requiring targeted interventions to ensure equitable access to these services for all residents in the region.

The region faces a range of structural challenges, including an ageing population, declining population figures, elevated levels of air pollution, mining-related environmental damage, inadequate local infrastructure, and a notable crime rate. Thus, efforts are needed to attract new inhabitants, improve the job market and the living conditions, to address the demographic challenges.

7.1.3. Economic & Industrial Landscape

Silesia is a vital and robust economic hub in Poland, contributing 12.4% of the national GDP³⁸⁷ ranking the second highest GDP in Poland after the Masovian region. A diverse array of industries fuels the region's economic vitality, including its well-developed automotive, energy, metallurgical and mining industries (which historically served as the cornerstone of the local economy until the close of the 20th century), as well as food, electromechanical and IT industries, making Silesia the most industrialized region in Poland. In fact, it is the largest coal mining region in terms of the quantity, production, and employment of coal miners, in the European Union. There are eight subregions in the region, and coal mining and related sectors have a significant influence on six of them. The central and western subregions, such as the city of Katowice, which is the capital of the Silesian Voivodeship, is where most miners reside. The local economy still heavily depends on coal mining, although it has been progressively losing ground as seen by diminishing output quantities, profitability, and productive capacity. The contribution of mining to the GVA of the region faced a 3.5% reduction from 2000 to

³⁸⁵ Bukowski et. Al, From restructuring to sustainable development, The case of Upper Silesia, 2018, Accessed: March 28, 2024, Available: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://www.wwf.de/fileadmin/fm-wwf/Publikationen-PDF/Klima/WWF-Report-From-restructuring-to-sustainable-development-The-case-of-Upper-Silesia.pdf>

³⁸⁶ Evaluation - Possibilities of technological development of the Silesian Voivodeship after 2020, Recommendations for the project "Regional Innovation Strategy of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2021-2027", Report prepared on behalf of the Marshal's Office of the Silesian Voivodeship, Central Mining Institute, Ecorys Polska sp. z o. o., Katowice - Warsaw, 2019

³⁸⁷ Strategic Diagnosis for the Development of the Silesian Voivodeship, Regional Center for Strategic Analysis and Planning, Department of Regional Development, Marshal's Office of the Silesian Voivodeship, Katowice, 2020

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2019, but in 2021 the sector was still responsible for 72,051 jobs, making up 4.3% of the total employment in Silesia. It is anticipated a decrease, in the sector employment, of less 12,300 jobs by 2030, reaching less 48,700 jobs by 2050. As of 2021, there were 16 operational coal mines producing 54.4 million tons of hard coal annually³⁸⁸.

Using the E-PRTR database, the industrial landscape and industrial sectors distribution of the Silesia Voivodeship region are detailed in Figure 43 and Figure 44. Industrial areas are mainly concentrated around the cities of Katowice, Chorzow, and Gliwice in the south of the region.

As shown in Figure 44Figure 35, 3 major industrial sectors are identified along with their number of sites as a percentage of the total number of sites:

- Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment (25%)
- Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply (19%)
- Mining and quarrying (14%)

The region is currently grappling with the imperative of transitioning from an energy-intensive and resource-intensive economy, to one that is sustainable, low-emission, and circular in nature making finding a new basis for the local economy vital for the region³⁸⁹. This transformation involves building upon the momentum initiated in 2015 with the Paris Agreement and directives emanating from the European Union aimed at fostering a greener continent. The goal is to normalize sustainable products, services, and business models while reshaping consumption patterns to proactively mitigate waste generation. These factors have reshaped the labor market dynamics, manifesting in challenges such as unemployment, job displacement, and skills shortages, particularly in post-industrial zones. Despite a significant reduction in the workforce within the mining and metallurgy industries, these sectors still contribute to one-third of the goods originating from the Silesian Voivodeship, thereby sustaining the industrial character of the region's economy. This transition encompasses not only the restructuring of the mining and energy sectors but also extends to various other industries entrenched within crucial value chains. Sectors including electronics and ICT, batteries, accumulators and vehicles, packaging, plastics, textile products, construction and buildings, food, water, and nutrients are all poised to undergo significant change. The automotive sector is one good example of a sector that is carrying out this transition, a sector that is deeply embedded in the economic framework of the Silesian Voivodeship and that plays an increasingly role in the region's smart specialization. This sector is transitioning towards manufacturing cars and components for hybrid and electric vehicles while leveraging the network of connections among companies in the region and the skilled workforce with extensive industry experience. The Silesian Voivodeship also possesses considerable potential in the realm of green economy initiatives, with a notable opportunity for the establishment of photovoltaic farms. Moreover, the region stands as one of Poland's production leaders in components for photovoltaic modules. Aiming to facilitate material recovery at the end of product life cycles, the

³⁸⁸ Silesia, Poland - Regional Profile, 2023 – European Commission. Accessed: Feb. 21, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-12/Silesia_2023.pdf

³⁸⁹ The Approach of the Silesia Region to Smart Specialisation Strategy Monitoring, 2020 – European Commission, Smart Specialization Platform. Accessed: Feb. 21, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/w/the-approach-of-the-silesia-region-to-smart-specialisation-strategy-monitoring>

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region's robust industrial nature makes it a perfect place to develop and deploy novel material solutions³⁸⁸.

Although the mining sector faces great challenges, on the other hand, a successful restructuring of the post-mining areas presents an opportunity to attain a higher level of wealth, even exceeding the European average. In the case of Upper Silesia, it must ensure the creation of good quality jobs for coal industry employees and include all the stakeholders, especially the employees of traditional sectors in the process of change. To address these challenges, initiatives aimed at modernization, diversification, and innovation are imperative, fostering the adoption of sustainable and circular economic models. This necessitates proactive policies and strategic investments in human capital and infrastructure to ensure long-term prosperity and resilience, by both the central and regional authorities. Notably, the Silesian Voivodeship stands to benefit from special European Union instruments like the Just Transition Fund, designed to support the green transformation, enhancing the region's appeal for residency, investment, and employment. The Just Transition Fund program for the Silesian Voivodeship is designed to bolster local economic heterogeneity, focusing on investments in small and medium-sized businesses involved in renewable energy, clean transportation, and other environmentally friendly sectors. Additionally, investments in digitization, waste management, and circular economy initiatives are gaining momentum, exemplified by projects such as the Industrial Symbiosis Park in Gliwice and the Silesian Industrial and Technological Park in Katowice³⁸⁸.

Industrial parks and logistics hubs, like the Special Economic Zone in Katowice, bolstered by special conditions such as, tax reliefs (from 30% to 60%), strategic location and enhanced infrastructure, underscore Silesia's commitment to economic vibrancy, investment attractiveness, and job creation³⁹⁰. Such endeavors, combined with digital connectivity and sustainable development initiatives, are pivotal for facilitating the transition to new economic sectors, ensuring Silesia's position as a beacon of prosperity and progress in Poland and beyond.

³⁹⁰ Polish Investment & Trade Agency, PFR Group, KSSE, No date. Accessed: Jun. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.paih.gov.pl/en/why_poland/investment_incentives/polish_investment_zone/katowice/

Figure 43: Mapping of industrial sites in Silesia Voivodeship (icons from icons8.com).

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Figure 44: Industrial sectors distribution and zoom into the Katowice cluster (icons from icons8.com).

7.2. Local policy analysis

Overview

Poland is unitary state with regions (voivodships) and local governments sharing some competence with the central government, depending on the policy area. For the policy fields relevant for this report, regional levels have important roles in designing policies at their level which reflect those at national level. These include, but are not limited to economic development, spatial planning, environmental protection. In return, energy policy is mostly decided at central level and regional authorities have a more limited role³⁹¹.

Policies specifically targeting IS and/or U-IS and their origins

There are no policy documents or strategies specifically targeting IS or I-US. Further, various relevant policy documents mention industrial symbiosis and I-US in a very limited way. The initial list contained 15 documents, mainly at regional level and covering waste plans, circular economy action plan and industrial as well as climate strategies. A complete list is provided in Annex 2: List of the documents screened for policy analysis section.

We screened the documents using the keywords and this resulted in a shortlist of 8 documents. It is important to note that only two of them explicitly mentioned the concept. To provide a more comprehensive overview, we analysed six more documents that are potentially relevant for industrial symbiosis:

- Road Map Towards the Transition to Circular Economy (national)
- National Raw Materials Policy (national)
- Energy Policy of Poland (national)
- Development strategy Silesian Voivodeship (regional)
- Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia (regional)
- Technology Development Program of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2019-2030 (regional)
- Waste management plan for Silesia 2016-2022 (regional)
- Waste management plan for Silesia 2023-2028 (regional)

Main Actors with work relevant for industrial-urban symbiosis

The policy initiatives listed above stem from different areas, with the following ministries working at times in tandem to ensure coherence:

- Ministry of Development and Technology
- Ministry of energy and climate
- Ministry of state assets, for mineral deposits management
- Ministry of the economy, construction, planning and spatial development and housing
- Ministry of economy
- Ministry of public finance

³⁹¹ 'Division of Powers Portal | Committee of the Regions, Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://portal.cor.europa.eu/divisionpowers/Pages/default.aspx>

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Due to the importance of mining for the economy, another actor worth mentioning at national level is the Chief National Geologist which has the capacity to act as the Government Plenipotentiary for the National Raw Materials Policy, linked to one of the documents analysed³⁹².

Other actors such as The Polish Agency for Enterprise Development (PARP) are also important, working with the private sector. The PARP coordinates diverse activities with the SMEs and working with national and international programs, primarily supported via EU structural funds³⁹³. It has a leading role in the area of circular economy working with all governance levels³⁹⁴.

At regional level, voivodships are responsible for the management of landfills, recycling and other treatment facilities and issuing relevant contracts³⁹⁵. Further, they are responsible for the implementation of energy policy and plan energy activities at regional and local level³⁹⁶.

Funding Mechanisms and other support instruments

The main funding instruments are EU (common funding instruments to all MS but also Cohesion Policy funds since Poland is a beneficiary) as well as national and regional funding. Several policy documents analysed for this study mention an expected decline of EU funding over the next period, and that more national funding will be needed to compensate for this change³⁹⁷. All funding instruments mentioned below aim at addressing the particular challenge of Silesia: moving away from the polluting industrial activities and decarbonising the economic activity while retaining employment levels through innovation and new jobs. Since industrial symbiosis might provide answers to these interrelated challenges, the funding can be used – at least in theory – to support relevant projects. It is however not explicitly mentioned in any of the resources identified for this analysis.

EU funding for green transition in Poland and in Silesia

The EU funds have an important place in the development and transformation of the Silesian region. As the largest hard coal mining region in the EU³⁹⁸, it receives funding from different financing

³⁹² Ministry of Climate and Environment of Poland, National Raw Materials Policy, 2022. Available : <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/national-raw-materials-policy>

³⁹³ Polish Agency for Enterprise Development, accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://en.parp.gov.pl/>

³⁹⁴ Future Industry Platform accessed: May 17, 2024 [In polish]. Available: <https://przemyslprzyszlosci.gov.pl/gospodarka-obiegu-zamknietego-tematem-kolejnego-spotkania-z-cyklu-idea-rozwoju-twojego-biznesu/>

³⁹⁵ International Trade Administration, Poland Country Commercial Guide, [Online], Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/poland-environmental-technologies>

³⁹⁶ Ministry of Climate and Environment of Poland, Energy Policy of Poland until 2040, 2021. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>

³⁹⁷ See for instance: Development Strategy Silesian Voivodeship: Green Silesia [In Polish]

³⁹⁸ The European Commission, EU Cohesion Policy: €3.85 billion for a just transition toward climate neutral economy in five Polish regions, 2022. [Online] Available: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/whats-new/newsroom/12-05-2022-eu-cohesion-policy-eur3-85-billion-for-a-just-transition-toward-climate-neutral-economy-in-five-polish-regions_en

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instruments including the European Regional Development Fund, Cohesion Fund and the Just Transition Fund^{399 400}.

For the 2021-2027 period, the total amount of EU funding amounts to 5.14€ billion⁴⁰¹ under three streams: ERDF (around 2€ billion), ESF+ (around 830M€) and JTF (around 2,2€ billion). Relevant program objectives include:

- Under greener Europe, the following are particularly relevant: the energy efficiency, sustainable water and circular economy.
- Under smarter Europe, enhancing research and innovation, reaping the benefits of digitisation and growth and competitiveness of SMEs.

Further, related to the social and economic dimension of transition in the region:

Under 'social Europe' the following objectives are relevant: adaptation of workers and enterprises to change, quality and inclusive education and training systems, lifelong learning and career transitions and active inclusion and employability. Further, the entire Just Transition Fund can be considered relevant⁴⁰².

Another important funding source is the Recovery and Resilience Facility: for the implementation of its National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Poland will receive 59€ billion in total (25.3€ billion in grants and the 34.5€ billion in loans)⁴⁰³. In theory, all three pillars are relevant, namely the green (47% of the budget) and digital transition (21% of the budget) and social spending (22% of the budget) since they can be used for initiatives to support circular economy transition and industrial symbiosis. The following themes and sub-themes are most relevant for IS and I-US:

³⁹⁹ The European Commission, Just Transition Platform. Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/just-transition-fund/just-transition-platform_en

⁴⁰⁰ The European Commission, European Funds for Silesia 2021-2027, [Online], Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/in-your-country/programmes/2021-2027/pl/2021pl16ffpr012_en

⁴⁰¹ Ministry of Development Funds and Regional Policy of Poland, European Commission approved 16 regional programmes for Poland, 2022, Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/funds-regional-policy/european-commission-approved-16-regional-programmes-for-poland#:~:text=European%20Funds%20for%20Lower%20Silesia,2021%2D2027%20%E2%80%93%20EUR%205.14%20billion>

⁴⁰² The European Commission, European Funds for Silesia 2021-2027, [Online], Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/in-your-country/programmes/2021-2027/pl/2021pl16ffpr012_en

⁴⁰³ The European Commission, Poland's recovery and resilience plan, [Online], Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/economic-recovery/recovery-and-resilience-facility/country-pages/polands-recovery-and-resilience-plan_en#country-snapshot

Table 14 Polish National Recovery Plan and its components, budgeted by priority theme and sub-theme.

Pillar	Sub-theme	Amount (Euros) ⁴⁰⁴
Resilience and competitiveness of the economy ⁴⁰⁵	Creating conditions for a circular economy (circular economy)	200 M
	Strengthening cooperation between the science and industry sectors	500 M
	Human resources for a modern economy - improving the matching of skills and qualifications to the requirements of the labour market in connection with the implementation of new technologies in the economy and green and digital transformation	400 M
	Accelerating robotization, digitization and innovation	400 M
Green energy and reducing energy consumption ⁴⁰⁶	Clean air and energy efficiency	4 B
	Improving conditions for the development of hydrogen technologies and other decarbonized gases	800 M
	Facilitating the implementation of the obligation to save energy by energy companies	300 M

However, it is not possible to have a detailed overview regarding how much of this funding is being/will be used for encouraging the industrial symbiosis potential of the area without looking at project level. This information is not available at the moment since the period is on-going. Nevertheless, some relevant examples can be found from the previous period. The Cohesion Fund database provides information on the projects funded by different streams⁴⁰⁷. For instance, under smart growth and research and innovation theme, ArcelorMittal Poland received 9.5M€ from the ERDF between 2018-2023, for: *Development and demonstration of an innovative two-stage blast furnace gas purification technology that meets the assumptions of minimising the amount of waste generated in the form of sludges, increasing the degree of reuse of dust and meeting technological requirements for further energy management of blast furnace gas*⁴⁰⁸. Another project carried out between 2017-2019 aimed at *developing an innovative technology to generate electricity from metallurgical waste gases while reducing the emissions of chlorine ions in wastewater*⁴⁰⁹. The main beneficiary was a private company

⁴⁰⁴ The amounts are in Polish Zlotys, converted to Euros by using 1 to 4.4 exchange rate and rounded up or down.

⁴⁰⁵ Polish National Recovery Plan, no date, [In Polish], Accessed May 17, 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/planodbudowy/odpornosc-i-konkurencyjnosc-gospodarki>

⁴⁰⁶ Polish National Recovery Plan, Green Transition Path, no date, [In Polish], Accessed May 17, 2024, Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/planodbudowy/zielona-energia-i-zmniejszenie-energochlonnosci>

⁴⁰⁷ The European Commission, Database of EU Projects, Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu/en/projects?country=Poland®ion=Silesian-Voivodeship&keywords=residue>

⁴⁰⁸ The European Commission Project Database, Project Details, Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: <https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu/en/projects/Q77675>

⁴⁰⁹ The European Commission Project Database, Project Details, Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: <https://kohesio.ec.europa.eu/en/projects/Q80095>

Huty Cynku Miasteczko Śląskie S.A, receiving 390K Euros from the ERDF. However, these examples seem to aim at reducing waste at company level rather than exchange of flows between companies.

National and regional funding

There is not a specific funding stream dedicated to IS or I-US at national and/or regional level. In the documents included for the analysis, we did not find any specific funding for the IS-related initiatives. Some documents, like the Waste Management Plans have specific budgets dedicated to different activities/operations but not directly mention IS-related activities. Some others such as the National Raw Materials Policy, dedicated budgets are mentioned in a general manner without specific earmarking.

Others have specific priorities potentially relevant for IS, such as waste management or transition to circular economy. Some of these are intertwined with the EU funds. The most notable instruments include the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management⁴¹⁰ and the Voivodship Funds, both of which work together to finance initiatives in environmental protection and water management⁴¹¹ even though they are separate entities. The former is managed by the Minister of Environment whereas the latter is managed by the relevant voivodships⁴¹². Since the fund priority themes and accessible to private companies, they are potentially useful for IS-related initiatives. For instance, The plan for Silesian Voivodship (Action strategy Provincial Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Katowice for 2021-2024) has eight priority areas. For priority area two, namely 'waste management and protection of earth's surface' states the following as the strategic goal: '*Minimizing the amount of waste generated, increasing reuse and limiting the storage of other waste, supporting the circular economy*'⁴¹³. Further, linked to the high air pollution of the region due to industrial activity, priority area three 'Atmospheric and noise protection' emphasises the importance of low-emission economy, improving air quality and a greater use of renewable energy resources as strategic goals⁴¹⁴. The former foresees a budget of 186M Euros for 2021-2024 and the latter 30M Euros⁴¹⁵.

Support instruments targeting industrial stakeholders

⁴¹⁰ Republic of Poland, The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management (NFEP&WM), Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/nfosigw-en/about-us>

⁴¹¹ Ministry of Climate and Environment of Poland, Energy Policy of Poland until 2040, 2021. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>

⁴¹² Republic of Poland, The National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management, Sub-section of Regional Funds for Environmental Protection and Water Management [Online], Accessed May 17, 2024. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/nfosigw/wfosigw>

⁴¹³ Provincial Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Katowice, 2020, Action strategy for Provincial Environmental Protection Fund and Water Management in Katowice for 2021-2024, [In Polish], Available: https://www.wfosigw.katowice.pl/files/Strategia_2021-2024.pdf

⁴¹⁴ Provincial Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Katowice, 2020, Action strategy for Provincial Environmental Protection Fund and Water Management in Katowice for 2021-2024, [In Polish], Available: https://www.wfosigw.katowice.pl/files/Strategia_2021-2024.pdf

⁴¹⁵ Provincial Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management in Katowice, 2020, Action strategy for Provincial Environmental Protection Fund and Water Management in Katowice for 2021-2024, [In Polish], Available: https://www.wfosigw.katowice.pl/files/Strategia_2021-2024.pdf

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Future Industry Platform⁴¹⁶ is an important initiative which is relevant for industrial symbiosis, although this is not explicitly stated as one of its core activity fields (it focuses on the digitalisation of the industry). However, circular economy is one of the areas where the latter is engaged in raising awareness towards the industry through the ‘business development series’. Building ecosystems and clusters are other themes mentioned on the website, but these remain at a ‘general level’ providing an entry level information to the businesses⁴¹⁷.

A critical reading of the policy: juggling priorities to overcome the lock-in effects of the past

General context

As stated previously, the Silesian Voivodship has a specific context that is amply reflected in the policy documents analysed for the study. The economic activity in the region depends on energy and resource-intensive industries, with a very heavy carbon and environmental footprint. There is a clear ambition to transform this activity to address heavy air, soil and water pollution and to achieve a carbon-neutral economy. However, this comes with the disruptive, unpopular impacts on the economic structure of the region, including the job market. Another example is the dependence on coal for energy for households: the region is characterised by the highest level of hard coal consumption by households which remains the cheapest source for heating in the EU⁴¹⁸. Thus, the social dimension and the emphasis on ‘just transition’ is particularly important in Silesian Region.

Acknowledging this, Poland is pursuing an integrated strategy stemming from the Strategy for Responsible Development, with nine integrated strategies covering social and productivity aspects as well as energy and environment (see diagram below)⁴¹⁹. These aim at addressing multiple issues in a coherent manner, making reference to material security and scarcity, water scarcity, critical raw materials, protecting the environment and human health from the negative impacts of a heavily polluting industry and at the same time, the unique issue of coal transition.

In theory, IS and I-US can provide solutions to these intertwined issues. It can create new jobs while delivering positive impacts such as waste minimisation, residual heat provisions or climate benefits. However, industrial symbiosis is mentioned in a very limited manner and as an overarching, generic ambition. Few of the documents explore the range of possibilities that the IS and I-US can provide in delivering a cleaner production. When they do, they do not specify the activities that are envisaged to achieve these general ambitions. It can be said that the policy regarding I-US is at the very early stages, at the conceptual level but without specific actions decided and implemented to realise the ambitions.

⁴¹⁶ Future Industry Platform Website, accessed: May 17, 2024 Available: <https://przemyslprzyszlosci.gov.pl/en/future-industry-platform-set-up-by-the-state-handed-over-to-industry/>

⁴¹⁷ Future Policy Platform Website, 2021, Process optimization in the green transition, [In Polish], Accessed: May 17, 2024. Available: <https://przemyslprzyszlosci.gov.pl/optimalizacja-procesow-w-zielonej-transformacji/>

⁴¹⁸ Silesian Voivodeship, 2022, Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia to 2030, [In Polish]. Available: [1671795836_projekt_terytorialny_2022 - Copy 2.pdf \(slaskie.pl\)](https://www.slaskie.pl/1671795836_projekt_terytorialny_2022_-_Copy_2.pdf)

⁴¹⁹ Ministry of Climate and Environment of Poland, Energy Policy of Poland until 2040, 2021. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>

Figure 45: Overview of integrated strategies, Source: Energy Policy of Poland⁴²⁰

Among all the documents reviewed, IS was explicitly mentioned only in the national Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) and the Technology Development Program of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2019-2030. The CEAP, published in 2019, is structured around four main axes, three of which are directly related to reshaping production processes: ‘Sustainable industrial production’, ‘bioeconomy’ and ‘new business models’⁴²¹. Industrial symbiosis is mentioned under the fourth section, namely ‘encouraging new business models’ and the document acknowledges the potential that it presents. In order to encourage a circular economy-oriented production, the document calls for the development of industry clusters as well as guidelines to increase the ‘circulation of raw materials and waste’⁴²². Further, one of the actions calls for a feasibility study to create a platform for secondary raw materials. Finally, the mining waste is mentioned under a dedicated action which calls for analysis the morphological composition thereof to identify potential further use in Polish industries⁴²³. However, the subsequent documents published after 2019 do not mention this platform and regional initiatives do not refer to these actions.

The second document, Technology Development Program of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2019-2030, provides the regional perspective but it remains more general. Under the dedicated section ‘rational

⁴²⁰ Ministry of Climate and Environment of Poland, Energy Policy of Poland until 2040, 2021. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>

⁴²¹ Government of Poland, 2019, Roadmap to Transition towards Circular Economy, Available: md_goz_final_en_r4_4.pdf (europa.eu)

⁴²² Government of Poland, 2019, Roadmap to Transition towards Circular Economy, Available: md_goz_final_en_r4_4.pdf (europa.eu)

⁴²³ Government of Poland, 2019, Roadmap to Transition towards Circular Economy, Available: md_goz_final_en_r4_4.pdf (europa.eu)

resource management', the concept is mentioned along with the recommendation that it needs to be implemented with the collaboration of diverse stakeholders⁴²⁴. The program has the following priorities potentially relevant for IS related initiatives: high-efficiency (clean) technologies that limit '*greenhouse gas emissions and other environmental pollutants*', *development of high-efficiency co-generation and most importantly, energy production from waste and alternative fuels*'. Further, the document calls for innovative technologies that support waste-free or low-waste production as well identifying new and energy-efficient ways to utilise metal waste⁴²⁵.

Other documents hint at the concept without explicitly mentioning it. Most importantly, they are concerned with the 'recovery and use of secondary raw materials' which comes very close to IS. In a similar way, the latest Waste Management Plan for Silesia (2023-2028) provides a definition of circular economy, specifically focusing on the production side, therefore potentially industrial symbiosis: '*Implementing the circular economy concept also means creating a cooperation network of enterprises from separate industries in order to exchange resources (materials, energy, water, by-products, waste)*'⁴²⁶. The document has sections dedicated to different industries and also to those 'industries whose management poses problems'. The latter has a focus on mining waste and calls for innovative technologies that will increase the recovery of mining waste ultimately reducing waste and landfilling. A specific example is mentioned which demonstrates the approach: '*the use of mining waste or products resulting from recovery processes of mining waste and ashes and slags constituting combustion residues for the production of cement, concrete and aggregates*'.

In a similar way, the Energy Policy of Poland makes reference to the link between innovation and achieve energy efficiency as well as circular economy. It underlines the importance of using waste and by-products from industrial processes to produce energy. The potential of waste biomass is also mentioned particularly waste that cannot be used in other sectors such as sewage waste, municipal waste, forestry residues and residues from agro-food processing industry⁴²⁷.

As mentioned above, the policy landscape includes some elements of IS and sometimes even explicitly mentions it as an ambition or an effective tool to achieve sustainability or clean production. They do not however go into details as to how to transform these initial ideas into concrete implementation.

Sectors targeted by the policy documents relevant for IS and U-IS

All relevant sectors are mentioned and targeted in the policy documents. Unsurprisingly, coal is considered very important, and other industries such as steel, processing, chemical, energy, minerals and mining. We identified some IS-related strategic ambitions about these sectors without much detail: for instance, the Energy Policy of Poland refers to the processing industry as a source for district heating without elaborating further on it.

⁴²⁴ Silesian Voivodship, 2018, Technology Development Program of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2019-2030, Available: <https://ris.slaskie.pl/file/download/1848>

⁴²⁵ Silesian Voivodship, 2018, Technology Development Program of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2019-2030, Available: <https://ris.slaskie.pl/file/download/1848>

⁴²⁶ Silesian Voivodship, 2024, Waste management plan for the Silesian Voivodeship for the years 2023-2028. Available: https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/73515/88654/1.+Projekt_Pgow%25C5%259B2028.pdf

⁴²⁷ Ministry of Climate and Environment of Poland, Energy Policy of Poland until 2040, 2021. Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>

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Challenges to IS and I-US

In the absence of specific focus – we could not identify much targeted information from these documents on the challenges to IS and I-US. Nevertheless, more general challenges are mentioned, and the following is relevant for the analysis:

- Low level of cooperation between sectors and weak links between research and development and industrial activities which leads to limited knowledge transfer⁴²⁸,
- low level of research expenditure⁴²⁹,
- a waste policy that does not take into account the principles of circularity⁴³⁰,
- economic barriers such as the dependency on coal for jobs and energy⁴³¹,
- lack of sufficient investment⁴³² and the considerable capital investment needed for restructuring of the industries⁴³³,
- lack of appropriate technology to reduce waste⁴³⁴,
- lack of full data on the waste generated and stored⁴³⁵,
- some type of waste is considered not suitable for further use: mineral residue deposits (the biggest share of industrial waste) do not have qualities that allow their subsequent use (can be linked back to lack of technology)⁴³⁶.

Governance: the role of public authorities in achieving industrial symbiosis

Since the documents do not go into detail about the implementation of IS-related policies, the role of the local and regional authorities can play in this process remains under-explored. The linkages between the government and other stakeholders are not discussed.

Nevertheless, several documents make reference to the importance of lesser-government levels in the process of policy making. They acknowledge the necessity of place-based and context-sensitive policies therefore developing and implementing policy in close collaboration with sub-government

⁴²⁸ Silesian Voivodship, 2020, Development Strategy Silesian Voivodship, [In Polish], Available: <https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/file/download-file/id.31164>

⁴²⁹ Silesian Voivodship, 2020, Development Strategy Silesian Voivodship, [In Polish], Available: <https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/file/download-file/id.31164>

⁴³⁰ Silesian Voivodship, 2020, Development Strategy Silesian Voivodship, [In Polish], Available: <https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/file/download-file/id.31164>

⁴³¹ Silesian Voivodship, 2022, Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia to 2030, [In Polish]. Available: [1671795836_projekt_terytorialny_2022 - Copy 2.pdf \(slaskie.pl\)](https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/file/download-file/id.31164)

⁴³² According to the United State Department of Commerce, Poland is one of the countries that under-spend in waste management. Country Profile available at: <https://www.trade.gov/poland-country-commercial-guide>

⁴³³ Silesian Voivodship, 2022, Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia to 2030, [In Polish]. Available: [1671795836_projekt_terytorialny_2022 - Copy 2.pdf \(slaskie.pl\)](https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/file/download-file/id.31164)

⁴³⁴ Silesian Voivodship, 2024, Waste management plan for the Silesian Voivodship for the years 2023-2028. Available: https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/73515/88654/1.+Projekt_Pgow%25C5%259B2028.pdf

⁴³⁵ Silesian Voivodship, 2024, Waste management plan for the Silesian Voivodship for the years 2023-2028. Available: https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/73515/88654/1.+Projekt_Pgow%25C5%259B2028.pdf

⁴³⁶ Silesian Voivodship, 2024, Waste management plan for the Silesian Voivodship for the years 2023-2028. Available: https://bip.slaskie.pl/resource/73515/88654/1.+Projekt_Pgow%25C5%259B2028.pdf

levels. This seems to be particularly important for certain sectors such as biomass and energy⁴³⁷. For instance, the role of local authorities in district heating and the development of local energy planning in general is emphasised⁴³⁸.

Also important to mention is the double-sided role of the LRAs in the transition: if the ecological transition represents a dilemma in terms of policy in Poland, local authorities are at the forefront of this. For instance, Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia stresses the considerable challenge of local authorities in facing the employment losses due to phase-out of coal-based economic activities. Further, these structural changes are expected to disrupt economy activity and to undermine revenues for local authorities. This, in turn, will weaken their ability to tackle further problems, creating a negative feedback loop. Therefore, support and capacity building for local authorities is considered important as it is the cooperation between different actors, both economic and social⁴³⁹.

7.3. I-US potential analysis

7.3.1. Material flows mapping

Industrial Waste Generation

The material flows analysis was conducted using the E-PRTR database. Figure 46 and Figure 47 respectively illustrate the total and disposed industrial waste flows in Silesia Voivodeship. Each year, 27 Mtons of waste are generated in the region, 4.5 Mtons of which is disposed. The mining of hard coal is the main emitting sector with an amount of waste of 18 Mtons/year (67% of total waste). Without considering the waste treatment and disposal sectors, the next biggest emitting sectors are the manufacture of basic iron or steel or ferro-alloys, the production of electricity, the steam air conditioning and supply and sewerage. These five sectors represent around 85% of the total waste flows on the territory.

Regarding the disposed waste, mining of hard coal is still the most emitting sector with 4 Mtons of disposed (89% of the total disposed waste), meaning landfilled, buried or incinerated without energy recovery. Then, 83 and 7 ktons disposed by the steam and air conditioning supply and automobile sectors respectively (2.1 and 0.2% of total disposed waste). Figure 48 illustrates all the waste flows in the area and their sectorial distribution.

The following maps show that the waste flows are highly concentrated in the center of the Silesian region around Katowice, Tychy, Gliwice, and Rybnik cities. In contrast, the south and north of the region generate much less waste because of their rural profile.

⁴³⁷ Government of Poland, 2019, Roadmap to Transition towards Circular Economy, Available: [md_goz_final_en_r4_4.pdf](#) (europa.eu)

⁴³⁸ See for instance: Energy policy of Poland, Available: <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>

⁴³⁹ Silesian Voivodeship, 2022, Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia to 2030, [In Polish]. Available: [1671795836_projekt_terytorialny_2022 - Copy 2.pdf](#) (slaskie.pl)

27 Mtons of waste generated each year

5 main emitting sectors :

- Mining of hard coal (18 Mtons/year – 67% of total waste)
- Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys (2.5 Mtons/year – 9.3% of total waste)
- Production of electricity (2.3 Mtons/year – 8.5% of total waste)
- Steam and air conditioning supply (0.32 Mtons/year – 1.2% of total waste)
- Sewerage (0.16 Mtons/year – 0.6% of total waste)

Figure 46: Total waste flows in Silesia Voivodeship

4.5 Mtons of disposed waste each year

83% recovering rate

- Around 4 Mtons of waste disposed by the mining of hard coal sector (89% of total disposed waste)
- 83 and 7 ktons disposed respectively by the steam and air conditioning supply and automobile sectors (2.1 and 0.2% of total disposed waste)

Figure 47: Disposed waste flows in Silesia Voivodeship

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Figure 48: Waste flows diagram and waste sectorial analysis in Silesia Voivodeship (quantities in kt/year in the table, icons from icons8.com)

I-US Flow Mapping

Publicly available data allows for a high-level analysis to be undertaken for Silesia which allows us to observe the quantities of waste being disposed of and recovered in relation to each priority sector. Although lacking in detail, by mapping out the main byproducts and wastes known to be associated with each industry in turn, this provides an indication of the likely industrial symbiosis opportunities that will exist for the Silesia region.

As can be seen from the table below, a high recovery rate is shown against most of the significant waste streams. Waste flows identified as going to disposal options, and therefore subject to landfill tax charges, are more likely to provide a significant commercial driver for businesses to engage in industrial symbiosis options. Recovery options by their nature tend to be less of a financial burden to industry, and therefore the commercial case for action is often less compelling.

Table 15 Primary Waste Flow Data for Silesia

NACE sector name	Waste destined for disposal (t/y)	Waste destined for recovery (t/y)	Total waste (t/y)
Mining of hard coal	3,969,336	14,491,084	18,460,420
Manufacture of basic iron and steel and of ferro-alloys	135,532	2,931,358	3,066,891
Production of electricity	72,140.23	2,613,582	2,685,723
Remediation activities and other waste management services	3,732	2,490,003.56	2,493,735.56
Mining of other non-ferrous metal ores	35,200	1,321,165	1,356,365
Steam and air conditioning supply	314,453	661,920	976,374
Treatment and disposal of non-hazardous waste	224640.73	458338.5	682979.23
Lead, zinc and tin production	809.49	280125.5	280934.99
Sewerage	42740.976	192403.59	235144.566
Casting of iron	47354.61	128827.279	176181.889

As a reminder, the priority sectors for the Silesia region have already been identified as:

- Coal Mining
- Steam & Air Conditioning Supply
- Production of Electricity
- Manufacturing of Steel, Iron and Ferro Alloys
- Iron Casting
- Manufacturing of Automotive Parts & Accessories
- Sewerage

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The table below details the main high-level byproduct and waste outputs expected for each of these sectors in turn.

Table 16 Silesia Priority Sector Material Resource Flow Analysis

Sector	No. of sites	Outputs /By-products
Coal mining	125	Overburden and spoil
		Rock and gravel
		Fly ash
		Coal fines and dust
		Tailings
		Mine water
Steam & Air Conditioning Supply	86	Scrap metals
		WEEE
		Oils and greases
Electricity Generation	79	Fly ash
		Bottom ash
		Sludge
		Waste water / cooling water
Manufacture of steel, iron, and ferro-alloys	54	Slag
		Mill scale
		Dust (Zinc rich)
		Process gases and steam
		Scrap metal
Iron casting	38	Molding sand and clay
		Waste metal
		Used foundry sand
		Wastewater and process water
Manufacture of automotive parts and accessories	33	Metal (offcuts, trimmings etc.)
		Plastic (excess plastic from injection molding etc.)
		Oils and lubricants
		WEEE
Sewerage	41	Sludges
		Treated effluent
		Biosolids

Section 7.3.3 details out the uses and potential sector partners for each of these material flows in turn. A significant volume of the typical sectoral flows outlined below would have limited industrial symbiosis applications beyond construction, cement production and land remediation making most options high volume, low value symbiosis opportunities.

Details are provided in the later section as outlined above.

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7.3.2. I-US infrastructure mapping

Figure 49, Figure 50, and Figure 51 illustrate the key infrastructure for I-US in Silesia Voivodeship.

In terms of transport infrastructures, the region has 249 km (0.02 km/km²) of motorways and around 6000 km (0.48 km/km²) of railways. For the energy infrastructures, 83% of the electricity is produced from coal while hydroelectric, gas and oil share the rest of the mix. Using modelling data from the HRE4⁴⁴⁰ project, 16.3 PJ/year and 5.8 PJ/year of excess heat from respectively industrial sites and WWTP have been identified. For the heat demands, urban area would consume around 69.6 PJ/year. Regarding the education, 9 universities (science and technical schools) are in the region. However, no I-US demo projects have been identified in Silesia Voivodeship.

⁴⁴⁰ « Heat Roadmap Europe ». <https://heatroadmap.eu/>

Figure 49: Transport infrastructures in Silesia Voivodeship

Figure 50: Electricity production and excess heat in Silesia Voivodeship (icons from icons8.com).

Figure 51: Education and innovation in Silesia Voivodeship (icons from icons8.com).

7.3.3. Regional readiness assessment for I-US and general conclusions

The following table outlines the main industrial symbiosis opportunities for the resources identified in the resource flow analysis provided in section 7.3.1.

Table 17 Industrial Symbiosis Opportunities in Silesia

Sector	Outputs /By-products	Uses
Coal mining	Overburden and spoil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land reclamation (restoration of mined land)
	Rock and gravel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – aggregates for roads, embankments, fill material
	Fly ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – cement substitute in concrete production. Fill materials. Agriculture, soil improvement
	Coal fines and dust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fuel (briquettes) – in industrial boilers, furnaces, power plants.
	Tailings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – aggregates for roads, embankments, fill material
	Mine water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrigation and industrial uses (after treatment)
Steam & Air Conditioning Supply	Scrap metals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle / re-use Feedstock for arc furnace
	WEEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recycle or refurb and re-use. Metal recovery (incl. rare earth)
	Oils & Grease	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy recovery
Electricity Generation	Fly ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – cement substitute in concrete production. Agriculture – soil improvement
	Bottom ash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction – aggregate substitute in concrete, road bases, embankments and structural fill Cement substitute Brick and ceramic manufacture Land reclamation Agriculture – soil improvement Water treatment – filtration medium
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction materials

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture – soil improvement
	Waste water / cooling water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-use in cooler system • Agriculture and landscaping, irrigation
Manufacture of steel, iron and ferro-alloys	Slag	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction – aggregate and cement substitute • Agriculture – soil amendment • Marine – coral reef repair and construction
	Mill scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iron recovery or substitute for virgin iron ore • Cement production
	Dust (Zinc rich)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery and recycling
	Process gases and steam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power or steam generation • Heat recovery • Fuel
	Scrap metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle / re-use • Feedstock for arc furnace
Iron casting	Moulding sand and clay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land reclamation (fill material) • Construction (aggregate for road bases and building foundations etc)
	Waste metal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle or remelt and re-use. • Feedstock for Electric Arc Furnace
	Used foundry sand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reclaim and re-use in foundry (requires chemical treatment) • Construction (backfill, embankments etc)
	Wastewater and process water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wastewater treatment for re-use.
Manufacture of automotive parts and accessories	Metal (offcuts, trimmings etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and re-use. • Feedstock for Electric Arc Furnace
	Plastic (excess plastic from injection moulding etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and re-use. • Energy recovery
	Oils and lubricants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle and re-use. • Energy recovery
	WEEE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recycle or refurb and re-use.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metal recovery (incl. rare earth)
Sewerage	Sludges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anaerobic Digestion - Biogas for heat/ energy / fuel • Agriculture – soil conditioner and fertiliser.
	Treated effluent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation - (crops, landscaping, golf courses)
	Biosolids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture - soil conditioner and fertiliser • Land reclamation – restoration of degraded soils. • Nutrient extraction – phosphorous etc.

There are a significant number of potential industrial symbiosis opportunities identified for the priority sectors in Silesia. Most of these are high volume and low value going into construction applications. In terms of volumes of synergies that could be realised then, even with this high-level analysis, we can be optimistic regarding the value that priority sectors would realise in engaging with industrial symbiosis activity.

In regard to drawing conclusions on Silesia’s readiness for industrial symbiosis then we use the readiness assessment produced as part of the EU Circlean⁴⁴¹ project as a framework.

Awareness of IS and Potential Benefits

Policy analysis concluded that no specific legislation or policy was driving industrial symbiosis (IS) uptake and awareness in both public and private sectors. A search on IS activity ⁴⁴²does reveal several examples in existence:

- The Tauron Group, a large energy and mining company, has synergies with chemical companies in the region. Here fly ash and gypsum, byproducts from coal fired power plants, are used by the construction (cement and aggregates) and chemical sectors.
- Katowice Special Economic Zone (KSEZ) promotes IS opportunities amongst its tenant industries, with one example being waste heat capture being used to generate energy for other manufacturing processes in the zone.
- ArcelorMittal Poland provides dust and slag from its steel production processes into the construction sector.

Initial Ideas of Where a Company Can Engage / Resources suiting IS / Processes Mapped & Targeted for IS

⁴⁴¹ <https://circlean-symbiosis.eu/the-project/>; accessed April 2024

⁴⁴² Kruczek, M., & Pichlak, M. (2022). Potential of Using Selected Industrial Waste Streams in Loop-Closing of Material Flows—The Example of the Silesian Voivodeship in Poland. *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4801. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084801>

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Given the examples in existence listed above, although no evidence has been identified of comprehensive work having been concluded in this area, then we can say that some work has clearly been concluded by industry or other actors to establish the synergies listed.

Internal Data Sources Identified for Quantification / Resources identified, quantified and characterised for IS

Only very high-level waste and material flow data has been identified as being publicly available. This lack of visibility will inhibit the uptake of industrial symbiosis. No technical data was available for the waste material flows to ascertain with certainty their suitability for IS application.

Check Costs, regulations and other technology specifications to be met for IS opportunities

As an EU members state the legislation has been adopted to drive waste elimination and circularity in industrial processes. A landfill tax regime is in place which will drive the commercial case for turning waste to resource.

Resources Prioritised for IS with Industry Buy In / All Resources Quantified and Posted on Matching Tool

No evidence of this level of advancement and visibility in relation to industrial symbiosis activity.

The lack of visibility of waste data at the required level of granularity, as well as a lack of a regional and national policy framework specifically driving IS activity clearly demonstrate more could be done in readiness for advancing industrial symbiosis.

The limited data that is available suggests that significant volumes of material are available, and some examples of industrial symbiosis are already in place involving the priority sectors of coal, steel manufacture, power generation, chemical production and construction. These examples can be used to more widely promote the benefits of industrial symbiosis and assist its advancement and uptake.

In conclusion, the Silesia region in Poland holds significant potential for industrial symbiosis due to its established complementary industrial base, supportive infrastructure, and available resources which have well established industrial symbiosis applications.

8. Methodology for T2.3 Replication Analysis

The first step of the replication analysis was to have a clear understanding of the three value chains of the demo cases (AshCycle, WaterProof and SYMSITES). The key information for the replication is as follows: the emitting industry sector(s), the receiving industry sector(s), and the maximum distance between two actors. To obtain these specifications, H4C demos were requested, and forms were completed. The value chains of the 3 projects are illustrated in Figure 52, Figure 53 and Figure 54.

AshCycle

“The AshCycle project provides tools for reducing the waste generation from the incineration of municipal solid waste (MSW), biomass, sewage sludge, or combinations of them by developing new utilization possibilities. The project will deploy exemplary pilot solutions of the Industrial-Urban Symbiosis (I-US) concept by demonstrating novel recovery methods for valuable elements from the ashes. Furthermore, the aluminosilicate-rich minerals recovered from the ashes are piloted as a feedstock for companies across value chains to obtain products for construction and wastewater treatment leading to increased resource efficiency and circularity”

From AshCycle website

Biomass Ashes

Sludge Ashes

MSW Ashes

Figure 52: AshCycle value chains.

WaterProof

“The WaterProof project aims at developing an electrochemical process that converts CO₂ emissions captured from consumer waste incineration and wastewater treatment facilities into formic acid to be used in valuable green consumer products such as cleaning detergents and the tanning of fish leather apparel. Additional products of the electrochemical process are peroxides that can be applied to remove pharmaceuticals and pesticides from wastewater. Furthermore, formic acid is used for the generation of acidic deep eutectic solvents (ADES), that can be applied to recover precious metals from wastewater sludge and incineration ashes. As the electrochemical process uses renewable energy, it contributes to a clean water cycle with zero-emission. WaterProof enables the closing of the waste(water) carbon loop and the shift from fossil to renewable carbon sources. It hereby supports the transition towards a climate-neutral Europe and an effective and truly circular economy.”

From WaterProof website

Value chain

Figure 53: WaterProof value chain.

Figure 54: SYMSITES value chains.

From the value chains, emitting and receiving industrial sectors were identified and extracted from public databases. Several industrial sectors are extracted from the E-PRTR database using the relevant NACE codes or E-PRTR codes. All the sectors and references are detailed in Table 18.

Table 18 : Industrial sectors extraction from public databases

Demo cases	Industrial sector	Role	Reference
AshCycle	MSW incinerator	Emitting	E-PRTR (EPTR code 5. (b) Installations for the incineration of non-hazardous waste in the scope of Directive 2000/76/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 December 2000 on the incineration of waste and NACE code E38 - Waste collection, treatment, and disposal activities; materials recovery or NACE code E39 - Remediation activities and other waste management services)
	Biomass incinerator	Emitting	Global Power Plant Database (GPPD) ⁴⁴³ (filtered by fuel=biomass)
	Sewage sludge incinerator	Emitting	E-PRTR (EPTR code 5. (b) Installations for the incineration of non-hazardous waste in the scope of Directive 2000/76/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 December 2000 on the incineration of waste and NACE E37 - Sewerage)
	Clay bricks producer	Receiving	E-PRTR (NACE code C23.3.2 - Manufacture of bricks, tiles and construction products, in baked clay)
	Cement producer	Receiving	E-PRTR (NACE code C23.5.1 - Manufacture of cement)
	Carbstone – Alkaline activated materials (AAM) producer	Receiving	E-PRTR (NACE code C23.6 - Manufacture of articles of concrete, cement and plaster)
WaterProof	MSW incinerator	Emitting	E-PRTR (EPTR code 5.(b) Installations for the incineration of non-hazardous waste in

⁴⁴³ Global Energy Observatory, Google, KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm, Enipedia, World Resources Institute. 2018. Global Power Plant Database. Published on Resource Watch and Google Earth Engine; <http://resourcewatch.org/> <https://earthengine.google.com/>

			the scope of Directive 2000/76/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 December 2000 on the incineration of waste and NACE code E38 - Waste collection, treatment, and disposal activities; materials recovery or NACE code E39 - Remediation activities and other waste management services)
	WWTP	Emitting	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive ⁴⁴⁴ (UWWTD)
	Leather tanning	Receiving	E-PRTR (NACE code C15.1.1 - Tanning and dressing of leather; dressing and dyeing of fur)
	Manufacture of cleaning products	Receiving	E-PRTR (NACE code C20.4.1 - Manufacture of soap and detergents, cleaning and polishing preparations)
SYMSITES (Greek case)	Olive industry	Emitting	E-PRTR (NACE code C10.4.1 - Manufacture of oils and fats)
	WWTP	Emitting	UWWTD
	Agriculture	Receiving	CORINE Land Cover (CLC), ⁴⁴⁵ 211, 212 and 213 land codes for agricultural lands
SYMSITES (Spain case)	Textile industry	Emitting	E-PRTR (NACE code C13 - Manufacture of textiles)
	Cosmetic industry	Emitting	E-PRTR (NACE code C20.4.2 - Manufacture of perfumes and toilet preparations)
	WWTP	Emitting	UWWTD
SYMSITES (Austrian case)	Meat processing industry	Emitting	E-PRTR (NACE code C10.1.1 - Processing and preserving of meat)
	WWTP	Emitting	UWWTD
SYMSITES (Danish case)	Agriculture	Emitting	CORINE Land Cover (CLC), 211, 212 and 213 land codes for agricultural lands
	Brewery	Emitting	E-PRTR (NACE code C11.0.5 - Manufacture of beer)
	WWTP	Emitting	UWWTD

⁴⁴⁴ "Urban Wastewater Directive Overview". European Commission : https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/urban-wastewater_en

⁴⁴⁵ European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service information; <https://doi.org/10.2909/71c95a07-e296-44fc-b22b-415f42acdf0>

All the extracted data is then imported on a GIS software, where geolocalized data is manipulated in order to replicate the industrial environment of the demo cases. To be considered as a potential replicated pilot, the maximum distance between two industrial sites is fixed to 10km, which corresponds to the mean distance between the different actors according to the demo cases. Results of the replication analysis are shown in Part 9.

9. Replication Analysis

9.1. SYMSITES

The results of the replication analysis of the SYMSITES pilots are illustrated in Figure 55, Figure 56, Figure 57, and Figure 58 for the Austrian, Danish, Greek and Spain cases respectively. Identified hotspots for each case, where the replication of the technology seems the more interesting, are listed in Table 19.

Table 19 : Identified hotspots for SYMSITES replication.

SYMSITES case	Identified hotspots
Austrian	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bretagne region in France ▪ Catalonia region in Spain ▪ Lombardy/Emilia-Romagna regions in Italy ▪ Liège/Antwerpen/Lille area in France and Belgium
Danish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lille/Brussels area in France and Belgium ▪ Tirlemont/Liège area in Belgium ▪ Bas-Rhin department in France ▪ Saxony region in Germany
Greek	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Veneto/Estern Emilia-Romagna regions in Italy ▪ Catalonia region in Spain ▪ Andalusia region in Spain ▪ Belgian et neerland flanders
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Province of Valencia in Spain ▪ Porto district in Portugal ▪ Lombardy region in Italy ▪ Province of Florence in Italy ▪ Lille/Courtrai/Roulers industrial cluster

The repartition of potential replicated SYMSITES pilots is show in Figure 59. A total of 1013 potential replicated sites (for all cases) were identified, 68% are concentrated in 5 countries:

- France (168 sites)
- Germany (150 sites)
- Spain (145 sites)
- Italy (134 sites)
- Belgium (93 sites)

Figure 55: SYMSITES (Austrian case) replication mapping.

Figure 56: SYMSITES (Danish case) replication mapping.

Figure 57: SYMSITES (Greek case) replication mapping.

DELIVERABLE 2.2

SYMSITES (Spain Case) replication pilots :

Cosmetic & Textile pilots - UWWTPs capacity within 30km radius :

- ◆ 64 500 - 135 400 EP
- ◆ 135 400 - 144 017 EP

Cosmetic pilots - UWWTPs capacity within 30km radius :

- ◆ 9 000 - 20 000 EP
- ◆ 20 000 - 85 280 EP
- ◆ 85 280 - 185 233 EP
- ◆ 185 233 - 473 500 EP
- ◆ 473 500 - 1 344 950 EP

Textile pilots - UWWTPs capacity within 30km radius :

- ◆ 0 - 198 000 EP
- ◆ 198 000 - 449 000 EP
- ◆ 449 000 - 796 500 EP
- ◆ 796 500 - 1 933 333 EP
- ◆ 1 933 333 - 2 570 000 EP

□ Territorial units

▭ T2.2 promising regions

▭ Selected clusters from T2.1

Density of replicated SYMSITES (Spain case) pilots :

0 250 500 km

Figure 58: SYMSITES (Spain case) replication mapping.

DELIVERABLE 2.2

Country	Greek case	Austrian case	Spain case	Danish case	Total
France	17	81	60	10	168
Germany	20	59	43	28	150
Spain	28	78	28	11	145
Italy	19	28	78	9	134
Belgium	7	40	36	10	93
Poland	5	27	0	10	42
Portugal	4	8	23	4	39
Netherlands	8	15	7	4	34
Czech Republic	2	10	12	6	30
Ireland	0	26	0	4	30
Denmark	2	19	1	7	29
Romania	4	6	5	9	24
Hungary	5	12	1	3	21
Slovakia	1	7	1	3	12
Sweden	1	6	0	3	10
Austria	1	5	1	2	9
Bulgaria	1	0	5	2	8
Finland	1	6	0	1	8
Norway	1	7	0	0	8
Slovenia	0	4	1	1	6
Greece	1	0	2	2	5
Croatia	0	1	0	3	4
Switzerland	0	0	3	0	3
Estonia	0	1	0	0	1
Total	128	446	307	132	1013

Figure 59: Number of potential replicated SYMSITES pilots per country

9.2. AshCycle

The results of the replication analysis of the AshCycle pilots are illustrated in Figure 60 for each value chain:

- Biomass ashes to carbstone -AAM: use of biomass ashes to produce carbstone and alkaline activated materials.
- MSW ashes to carbstone – AAM: use of MSW ashes to produce carbstone and alkaline activated materials.
- Biomass ashes to cement: use of biomass ashes to produce cement.
- Sewage sludge ashes to cement: use of sewage sludge ashes to produce cement.
- Biomass ashes to clay bricks: use of biomass ashes to produce clay bricks.
- MSW ashes to clay bricks: use of MSW ashes to produce clay bricks.

Identified hotspots for AshCycle pilot’s replication, where the replication of the technology seems the most interesting, are:

- Birmingham/Leicester area
- Cardiff/Bristol area
- French and Belgian Flanders
- Porto district
- Province of Roma

The locations of the potential replicated pilots are shows in Figure 61. 86% are concentrated in 5 countries:

- UK (55 sites)
- France (21 sites)
- Germany (9 sites)
- Belgium (6 sites)
- Italy (5 sites)

Figure 60: AshCycle replication mapping.

	Biomass ashes to carbstone - AAM	Biomass ashes to cement	Biomass ashes to clay bricks	MSW incineration ashes to carbstone - AAM	MSW incineration ashes to cement	MSW incineration ashes to clay bricks	Sewage sludge ashes to cement	Total
United Kingdom	2	7	27	2	1	16	0	55
France	2	5	3	3	5	1	2	21
Germany	1	2	1	0	4	1	0	9
Belgium	0	0	0	2	0	4	0	6
Italy	0	0	0	1	2	2	0	5
Poland	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	3
Portugal	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	3
Spain	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
Switzerland	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
Czech Republic	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Denmark	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Finland	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Ireland	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Slovenia	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Total	5	16	35	8	19	26	2	111

Figure 61: Number of potential replicated AshCycle pilots per country

9.3. WaterProof

The results of the replication analysis of the Waterproof pilots are illustrated in Figure 62 for each value chain:

- Formic acid to leather tanning: use of formic acid obtained from incinerator WWTP CO₂ for the tanning of textiles.
- Formic acid to manufacture of cleaning products: use of formic acid obtained from incinerator WWTP CO₂ for the manufacture of cleaning products.

Identified hotspots for WaterProof pilots replication, where the replication of the technology seems the most interesting, are:

- Lombardy region in Italy
- Charleroi/Brussel/Lille area in Belgium and France
- Ile-de-France region in France
- Vincenza area in Italy due to its high concentration of tanning facilities

The locations of the potential replicated pilots are shown in Figure 63. 93% are concentrated in 5 countries:

- Italy (25 sites)
- France (21 sites)
- Belgium (11 sites)
- Germany (10 sites)
- Spain (9 sites)

The “acid formic to leather tanning” replicated pilots are mainly located in Italy while the “acid formic to manufacture of cleaning products” ones are more equally distributed across western European countries as seen in the map in Figure 62.

Figure 62: WaterProof replication mapping.

	Acid formic to leather tanning	Acid formic to manufacture of cleaning products	Total
Italy	18	7	25
France	1	20	21
Belgium	0	11	11
Germany	2	8	10
Spain	0	9	9
Netherlands	1	2	3
Austria	1	0	1
Norway	0	1	1
Sweden	0	1	1
Total	23	59	82

Figure 63: Number of potential replicated WaterProof pilots per country.

10. Replication in High Potential Regions

The aim of this section is to analyse in detail the replication of value chains for the 3 demos cases (SYSMISTES, AshCycle, WaterProof) in the 5 most promising regions, in order to provide local stakeholders with examples of existing I-US projects. Potential replication pilots are mapped in each region to identify the most relevant areas. Examples of replication projects are presented via satellite views to give local actors a first concrete glimpse of such synergies.

10.1. Basque Country

Two SYMSITES replicated pilots are identified in the Basque Country with the Spain's case value chain. The potential pilots are located in Miranda de Ebro and Bergara cities. The mapping of these sites is shown in Figure 64. The replicated industrial environment of Miranda is illustrated in Figure 65.

Figure 64: Replication analysis mapping in the Basque Country

Figure 65: Identified replicated SIMSITES (Spain Case) pilot in Miranda.

10.2. Flanders

110 I-US replicated pilots are identified in the Flanders region. 94 of them correspond to the SYMSITES value chains and are concentrated in the Lille/Courtrai/Roulers cluster, and the provinces of Gentt and Antwerpen. 9 AshCycle replicated pilots are found in the Antwerpen, Oostende, Lens, Péruwelz, Saint-Omer and Dannes cities. Regarding the WaterProof value chains, they are located around the cities of Ieper, Roubaix, Charleroi, Gentt, Zele, Mechelen and Zevenbergen. The mapping of these sites and the value chains distribution are shown in Figure 66. 3 examples of replicated industrial environments for each I-US demo case are illustrated in Figure 67, Figure 68, and Figure 69.

Figure 66: Replication analysis mapping in the Flanders region.

Figure 67: SYMSITES (Spain case) value chain replication in Neuville-en-Ferrain.

Figure 68: Waterproof value chain replication in Gent.

Figure 69: AshCycle value chain replication in Antwerpen

10.3. Midlands

24 I-US replicated pilots are identified in the Flanders region for the AshCycle value chain. SYMSITES and WaterProof are not covered in this analysis since the UWWTD database used to identify these pilots has no data in the UK. The potential sites are mainly located around the cities of Birmingham, Leicester, Manchester, Leeds, and Hull. The mapping of these sites and the value chains distribution are shown in Figure 70. One example of a replicated industrial environment for valorisation of biomass and MSW ashes into clay bricks in the Cannock city is illustrated in Figure 71.

24 replicated sites identified for the AshCycle value chain

Note : SYMSITES and WaterProof replication analysis does not cover the UK because there is no data in the UWWTD database for this country

AshCycle value chain	Number of replicated sites
Biomass ashes to clay bricks	13
MSW ashes to carbstone - AAM materials	1
MSW ashes to clay bricks	10

Figure 70: Replication analysis mapping in the Midlands region (points corresponding to different value chains can overlap).

Figure 71: AshCycle value chains replication in Cannock.

10.4. North Rhine-Westphalia

24 I-US replicated pilots are identified in the NRW region. 20 of them correspond to the SYMSITES value chains and are concentrated in the North and East of the region. No AshCycle replicated pilots are found in this area. Regarding the WaterProof value chains, 4 pilots are identified in Mülheim an der Ruhr, Krefeld, Iversheim and Düren. The mapping of these sites and the value chains distribution are shown in Figure 72. 3 examples of replicated industrial environments for each I-US demo case project are illustrated in Figure 73 and Figure 74.

42 replicated-US demo cases identified in the NRW region

	Number of sites
AshCycle replication	0
WaterProof replication	4
SYMSITES (Danish case)	6
SYMSITES (Greek case)	4
SYMSITES (Austrian case)	5
SYMSITES (Spain case)	5
Total	24

Figure 72: Replication analysis mapping in the NRW region.

Figure 73: SYMSITES (Danish case) value chain replication in Mönchengladbach.

Figure 74: WaterProof value chain (leather tanning) replication in Duisburg.

10.5. Silesian Voivodeship

5 I-US replicated pilots are identified in the Silesia region. 4 of them correspond to the SYMSITES value chains, mainly are concentrated around Katowice, and one is located in Zywiec. No WaterProof replicated pilots are found in this area. Regarding the AshCycle value chains, 1 pilot is pointed out in Gnaszyn-Kawodrza. The mapping of these sites and the value chains distribution are shown in Figure 75. 2 examples of replicated industrial environments for AshCycle and SYMSITES demo cases are illustrated in Figure 76 and Figure 77. Regarding the SYMSITES examples, the Komagra facility produce canola oil and not olive oil.

Figure 75: Replication analysis mapping in the Silesia region.

Figure 76: AshCycle value chain (biomass ashes to clay bricks) replication in Gnaszyn-Kawodrza.

Figure 77: SYMSITES (Greek case) value chain replication in Tychy.

11. Conclusion

Through a comprehensive analysis of five promising regions identified in Task 2.1—Basque Country (Spain), Flanders (Belgium, the Netherlands, and France), Midlands (United Kingdom), North Rhine-Westphalia (Germany), and Silesian Voivodeship (Poland)—this report provides valuable insights into the potential for I-US development. The analysis covered various aspects, including local context, geographical landscape, social landscape, economic and industrial landscape, policy analysis, industrial material flows analysis, and infrastructure for I-US and symbiosis opportunities.

The results of this in-depth analysis offer a detailed understanding of each region's unique characteristics and potential for I-US as well as insights on the region's global readiness level for I-US implementation. By identifying supportive and inhibitive policies, mapping industrial resource flows, and recognizing specific symbiosis opportunities, this report equips local stakeholders with valuable information to explore and implement local I-US projects.

However, the study does have its limitations. The analysis lacks granularity in the typologies of flows, resulting in an absence of qualitative data. Additionally, the policy analysis was conducted at national and/or regional levels rather than at the city level, which may overlook local nuances and specific urban challenges. Furthermore, there is a notable lack of data on supply chain flows, which limits the ability to fully understand the potential for resource synergies and material exchanges and to propose very specific projects at this stage.

The findings from Task 2.3 highlight the potential for replicating the innovative value chains of H4C demo projects across Europe. By mapping the locations with similar industrial setups, the project identifies where these successful I-US models may be implemented. This replication analysis, grounded in detailed data from demo cases and European industrial databases, provides consortia with strategic insights for expanding H4C initiatives. By understanding where similar industrial and urban dynamics exist, stakeholders can effectively plan and execute new I-US projects, ensuring the scalability and sustainability of circular economy practices. The same approach could be systematically applied to future similar projects to assess its replicability. Lastly, a focus examination of the replicability of the demo projects was done for the five high potential regions. Preliminary results showed specific examples of potential for replication in them that could be explored by local stakeholders.

Despite the identified limitations, the insights gained are instrumental in guiding local actors to develop tailored strategies for establishing H4Cs. This not only accelerates the transition to a circular economy but also fosters sustainable regional development, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and resource-efficient Europe.

The findings and methodologies outlined in this report provide a solid foundation for future efforts in promoting industrial-urban symbiosis and the broader circular economy agenda. As local stakeholders leverage this knowledge, they will be better positioned to implement innovative solutions that enhance sustainability and economic growth in their regions

Annexes

Annex 1: NACE nomenclature used for the segmentation of the industrial landscape and the I-US potential analysis

Sector name	NACE codes correspondence
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	A1 to A3
Mining and quarrying	B5 to B9
Manufacture of food products; beverages and tobacco products	C10 to C12
Manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	C13 to C15
Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials	C16
Manufacture of paper and paper products; printing and reproduction of recorded media	C17 and C18
Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products	C19
Manufacture of chemical, pharmaceutical, rubber and plastic products	C20 to C22
Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	C23
Manufacture of basic metals and fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	C24 and C25
Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, electrical equipment, motor vehicles and other transport equipment	C26 to C30
Manufacture of furniture; jewellery, musical instruments, toys; repair and installation of machinery and equipment	C31 to C33
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	D35
Water collection, treatment and supply; sewerage; remediation activities and other waste management services	E36, E37 and E39
Waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery	E38
Construction	F41 to F43

Annex 2: List of the documents screened for policy analysis section.

Country/Region	Name of the document - EN
BE (Flanders)	The Chemistry/Plastics strategic agenda
BE (Flanders)	Gap Analysis
BE (Flanders)	Manufacturing industry Strategic Agenda

Country/Region	Name of the document - EN
BE (Flanders)	Vision 2050
BE (Flanders)	SSS strategy (the full document)
BE (Flanders)	Flanders: Strategy for Smart Specialisation 2.0 (UPDATE In 2023)
BE (Flanders)	Research Guide to Entrepreneurship & Innovation. The Flemish government budget for Economy, Science & Innovation
BE (Flanders)	The Flemish energy and climate plan 2013-2020
BE (Flanders)	Circular economy country profile – Belgium
BE (Flanders)	Leuven 2030
BE (Flanders)	Focus 2030
BE (Flanders)	Spatial Policy Plan for Flanders
BE (Flanders)	The Flemish coalition agreement 2019-2024
BE (Flanders)	Plastics Implementation Plan
BE (Flanders)	National Circular Economy Program
BE (Flanders)	National Energy and Climate Plan
BE (Flanders)	IMAGES OF THE FUTURE Flanders circular in 2050
BE (Flanders)	Natural Resources and Waste Plan
BE (Flanders)	Flemish Climate and Energy Plan 2021-2030
BE (Flanders)	ACTION PLAN CIRCULAR FOOD LOSS AND BIOMASS(RESIDUAL) FLOWS 2021-2025
BE (Flanders)	For a fair and effective industrial climate transition, Support measures for heavy industry in Belgium, the Netherlands and Germany
BE (Flanders)	Flanders in Action with the New Industrial Policy
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	German Resource Efficiency Programme
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Waste prevention programme - the federal government with the participation of the federal states
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Waste prevention programme - the federal government with the participation of the federal states: update
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Waste management plan North Rhine-Westphalia
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Sustainability Strategy North Rhine-Westphalia
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Industrial policy in changed times Safeguarding our industrial base, renewing our prosperity, boosting our economic security
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Federal Government's raw material strategy
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Process heat for a climate-neutral industry Impulse paper of the IN4climate.NRW initiative
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Climate-neutral industrial heat: strategies and prerequisites for transformation Discussion paper of the heat working group

Country/Region	Name of the document - EN
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Energy Supply Strategy NRW Energy Report North Rhine-Westphalia 2022
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Energiebericht Nordrhein-Westfalen 2022
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Waste Management Plan North Rhine-Westphalia, Sub-Plan for Hazardous Waste
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Industrial policy mission statement of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Carbon Management Strategy NRW
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	Status quo of recycling in metal production and processing in Germany
DE (North Rhine Westphalia)	CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN MATERIALS INDUSTRY: POTENTIALS AND NEEDS FRAMEWORK CONDITIONS FOR SUCCESS RICH TRANSFORMATION Discussion paper from the Circular Economy working group
ES (Basque Country)	Industrial development and internationalization plan 2021-2024
ES (Basque Country)	Euskadi Circular Economy Strategy 2030
ES (Basque Country)	Basque Country Waste Prevention and Management Plan 2030
ES (Basque Country)	SME aid program Circular 2021
ES (Basque Country)	Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024
ES (Basque Country)	Circular Economy in the Industry of the Basque Country - Diagnosis
ES (Basque Country)	Basque Country Environmental Framework Program 2030
ES (Basque Country)	Science, Technology and Innovation Plan Basque 2030
ES (Basque Country)	Environmental planning of the Basque Government
ES (Basque Country)	The Context: Sustainability at the Center of International, European and Basque Policies
ES (Basque Country)	Energy Transition Plan and Climate Change 2021-2024
ES (Basque Country)	STRATEGIC EMPLOYMENT PLAN 2021-2024
ES (Basque Country)	Bultzatu 2050: The Urban Agenda of Euskadi
ES (Basque Country)	Euskadi Energy Strategy 2030
ES (Basque Country)	Climate Change Strategy 2050 of the Basque Country
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Chemical sector sectoral report
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Metal sector sectoral report
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Construction sector sectoral report
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Sectoral report on the food and beverage sector
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Sectoral report on the mobility and logistics sector
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Sectoral report on the means of transport sector
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in circular economy - Sectoral report environmental sector

Country/Region	Name of the document - EN
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Sectoral report on the electrical and electronic equipment sector
ES (Basque Country)	Reports on sectoral keys in the circular economy - Sectoral report on the machine tool sector
ES (Basque Country)	Evaluation of cluster policies: the case of the Basque Country
ES (Basque Country)	Cluster policy of the Basque Country: lessons learned and challenges
FR (Flanders)	Waste Management and Prevention Plan for Haut de France
FR (Flanders)	3S Strategy for Haut de France
FR (Flanders)	Regional Strategy for economic development, innovation and cross-border relations
FR (Flanders)	Roadmap for CE
FR (Flanders)	Anti-waste law
FR (Flanders)	Le plan national de relance et de résilience (PNRR)
FR (Flanders)	Haut de France Climate and Energy Strategy
FR (Flanders)	Regional Land planning Plan
NL (Flanders)	National Circular Economy Program
NL (Flanders)	Spatial Strategy Zuid Holland Main messages
NL (Flanders)	NATIONAL POLICY ANALYSIS THE NETHERLANDS
NL (Flanders)	Circular Economy Implementation Programme
NL (Flanders)	Manufacturing Industry Transition Agenda
NL (Flanders)	Advisory Roadmap for Transition Agenda
NL (Flanders)	Raw Materials Agreement
NL (Flanders)	Circular Economy Vision to 2050
NL (Flanders)	Plastics Sector Transition Agenda
NL (Flanders)	Circular Strategy for South Holland
NL (Flanders)	Circular Economy Profile - NETHERLANDS
NL (Flanders)	OECD Report on CE in Zuid Holland
NL (Flanders)	CE Strategy of Zuid Holland-Updated
NL (Flanders)	Vision for Industry
NL (Flanders)	Final report on Circular Trading Platforms
NL (Flanders)	MMIP6: Closure of industrial chains
PL (Silesia)	Territorial Just Transition Plan for Silesia
PL (Silesia)	Circular Economy in the strategies and plans of voivodships in Poland
PL (Silesia)	Road Map Towards the Transition to Circular Economy
PL (Silesia)	Regional Revitalisation Policy for Silesia
PL (Silesia)	Low emission economy policy

Country/Region	Name of the document - EN
PL (Silesia)	Development Strategy Silesian Voivodeship
PL (Silesia)	Report on the implementation of the Waste Management Plan for the Silesian Voivodeship 2014-2016
PL (Silesia)	Regional Profile for Silesia
PL (Silesia)	Energy Policy of Poland
PL (Silesia)	From restructuring to sustainable development - The case of Upper Silesia
PL (Silesia)	Changing the mining industry in the heart of Silesia
PL (Silesia)	Technology Development Program of the Silesian Voivodeship for 2019-2030
PL (Silesia)	Waste management plan for Silesia
PL (Silesia)	Waste management plan for Silesia
PL (Silesia)	NATIONAL RAW MATERIALS POLICY
UK (The Midlands)	West Midlands' Circular Economy Routemap: Kickstarting the region's journey to a green industrial revolution
UK (The Midlands)	Waste prevention programme for England: Maximising Resources, Minimising Waste
UK (The Midlands)	Resources and waste strategy for England
UK (The Midlands)	Industrial decarbonisation strategy
UK (The Midlands)	Sixth Carbon Budget, Climate Change Committee (2020)
UK (The Midlands)	Birmingham City Council WASTE STRATEGY
UK (The Midlands)	Our Manchester Industrial Strategy
UK (The Midlands)	Investing in success - an Economic Strategy for Manchester
UK (The Midlands)	Greater Manchester Local Industrial Strategy
UK (The Midlands)	National Infrastructure Delivery Plan
UK (The Midlands)	Clean Growth Strategy
UK (The Midlands)	West Midlands Local Industrial Strategy
UK (The Midlands)	WM2041
UK (The Midlands)	West Midlands Plan for Growth
UK (The Midlands)	Delivering a Deeper Devolution Deal for the West Midlands
UK (The Midlands)	West Midlands Industrial Symbiosis Network
UK (The Midlands)	Manufacturing: Materials and Manufacturing Vision
UK (The Midlands)	Metals: Innovation action plan for aluminium in a circular economy, InnovateUK
UK (The Midlands)	Five Year Plan, WMCA
UK (The Midlands)	Home of the Green Industrial Revolution
UK (The Midlands)	Position Paper from The Resource Recovery from Waste programme: The National Materials Datahub Can Improve Governance for Better Material Use by Industry: An Evidence Briefing from the Resource Recovery from Waste Programme
UK (The Midlands)	Resources and waste strategy for England: monitoring and evaluation

Country/Region	Name of the document - EN
UK (The Midlands)	The 25 Year Environment Plan
UK (The Midlands)	The UK's Industrial Strategy
UK (The Midlands)	Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener

Annex 3: List of keywords used for screening/selecting the documents for in-depth analysis in the policy section

Keywords	Remarks
Industry	
Manufacturing	
Waste stream	Only in relation to industry/circular economy
Valorisation	Only in relation to industry/circular economy
Side stream	Only in relation to industry/circular economy
Processing	Only in relation to industry/circular economy
Any of the sectors identified in the cluster	
Governance	Only in relation to industry/circular economy
Innovation	Only if there is a circular economy/efficiency angle
Innovation ecosystem	Only if there is a circular economy/efficiency angle
Industrial symbiosis	
Data	Only in conjunction with industry
Wastewater	Only in relation to IS and I-US
Secondary/secondary raw materials	
Loop/Closed loop	
Resource management/resource use	